

**Peer relationships and the use of mobile instant
messaging applications as trusted supporting tools:
The case of doctoral students at UWS Campuses**

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ABSTRACT

The peer relationship framework (PRF) by Kram and Isabella (1985) has been confirmed to be one of the preferred frameworks for exploring peer relationships among doctoral students (Lee, Anderson, and Burnett, 2017; Terrion and Leonard, 2007). Despite its relevance, some important functions are either missing or inadequately defined. The use of MIM apps posited to be an important supporting tool among students of this decade (Abiodun et al., 2020; Radha et al., 2020; Wang, Huang, and Quek, 2018) is missing in the framework. Likewise, the concept of trust is inadequately represented in the sense that the framework described it as being unidirectional. Meanwhile, Lewicki, Mcallister, and Bies (1998) stated that an individual could trust a peer in one area of their relationship (academic support) and distrust the same peer in another aspect (emotional support). Hence, the reason for integrating the PRF with Lewicki's model of trust to study how MIM apps are used as supporting tools among doctoral students during peer relationships.

Using a single case approach, research data was collated from twenty-two UWS doctoral students from four out of the five UWS campuses. Both PhD and DBA students are included, and they all took part in the study's semi-structured interviews and focus group sessions. A follow-up interview, involving four of the twenty-two students, was also conducted.

The study found that the functions presented by Kram and Isabella (1985) in the peer relationship framework (PRF) – Developmental functions; Self-Disclosure and Trust, are important for describing peer relationships among doctoral students. It established that the use of MIM apps such as Microsoft Teams, WhatsApp, Zoom among others, is completely integrated into how these students cultivate their peer relationships. Also, the study affirmed that the intensity of the MIM app usage depends on the level of trust/distrust that exists among these groups of students. Based on these key findings, a new framework that can be used to

adequately explore peer relationships among doctoral students is developed. The thesis concluded by considering the implications for doctoral studies at the University of the West of Scotland. Some recommendations that will benefit the future policy of the university and other universities were also presented.

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ABBREVIATIONS AND THEIR MEANING

COVID-19 - A type of coronavirus discovered in 2019 known to be infectious and attack the respiratory system of its host with the potential of leading to fatalities especially if the host has a weak immune system or underlying health conditions.

DBA – Doctor of Business Administration, a doctorate designed to advance the business and managerial knowledge of professionals in the business world.

MIM apps – Mobile Instant Messaging applications such as WhatsApp, Facebook messenger, WeChat, Microsoft teams among others.

PhD – Doctor of Philosophy, a doctorate that helps people significantly contribute to the theoretical knowledge of a concept.

PRF - Peer relationships Framework developed by Kram and Isabella (1985)

SNS - Social Network Service, any internet-enabled platforms used for social interactions such as Reddit, Twitter, Facebook, Tumblr, Skype among many others.

THE – Times Higher Education, a data provider focused on analysing and giving insight on higher education.

UWS – the University of the West of Scotland whose five campuses were the case for this study.

WHO – World Health Organisation, United Nations’ agency dedicated to ensuring that a high standard of public health is maintained across the globe.

CHAPTER ONE - INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

It is no doubt that the level of formal support given to doctoral students is not as much as those at the undergraduate and master's degree levels. This is because students at their doctoral level are expected to have prerequisite knowledge of how to independently conduct and conclude a research study. While this may be true, one should be reminded that these are adults who would likely be engulfed in personal challenges that may impact their level of concentration. Thus, ending up needing a little bit of support to forge ahead with their doctoral studies. No wonder, scholars such as Lovitts (2002) and Gardner (2009) posited that personal challenges are the main reasons for drop-out among this group of students.

Aside from personal challenges, Castello et al. (2017) believed that reasons for dropping out of the doctorate also include the inability to balance studies with work; lack of sense of belonging; lack of motivation towards the study; insufficient resources such as funds or training options; lack of confidence in research skills; and stress and emotional breakdown. A similar conclusion was also reached by Wollast et al. (2018) who stated that internal factors such as marital status; grades from master's degree and availability of funds are the main determinant of the increase in drop-out rates. With a review of 163 articles on doctoral students' experience, Sverdlik et al. (2018) found that external factors such as poor supervision, lack of socialisation and financial issues and internal factors such as lack of confidence in writing skills, low motivation, and poor self-regulatory strategies all contribute to the reasons doctoral students do not complete their studies. While most of these studies explored the concept from the perspective of all doctoral students, the focus on international students by Laufer and Gorup (2018) indicate that in addition to all the factors mentioned above, international students still must deal with immigration pressure as well as adjust to the

cultural and academic differences that they may experience during their training. Laufer and Gorup (2018) referred to this as ‘othering’, and could be financial, academic, foreign, or social othering.

As important as understanding what the problem is, it is also important to begin to discuss solutions. Since the novel work of Lovitts (2002), more literature has explored areas that give a solution to the high drop-out rates among doctoral students. As expected, the majority has focused on an improved student-supervisor relationship while only a few had explored peer-to-peer relationships (Devos et al., 2017). The few authors who had worked on the latter (i.e., Byl et al., 2016; Laidlaw et al., 2016; Lee et al., 2017; Lindsay, 2015) emphasised that the ability to give each other informal support on either academic or non-academic issues emanates from the relationship developed among one another. According to them, this informal relationship does not only increase students’ capability to complete their studies on time but, also reduces drop-out rates. Apart from the supervisors, peers are the other group of people doctoral students interact with daily (Jairam and Kahl, 2012). Evidence has shown that interaction with fellow students either within or outside of the university could help doctoral students complete their studies, on time (Devos et al., 2017; Golde, 2000). As emphasised by Bair, Haworth, and Sandfort (2004), those who engage with their peers for support are more likely to complete their studies and mostly, happily compared to those who do not.

The student-supervisor relationship plays a significant role in the successful completion of a doctorate, but it might not be able to save a student from dropping out of the training especially if the causes are non-academic. An example is a major disruption caused by the emergence of COVID-19 across the globe in the year 2020. This deadly disease had killed over 4 million people (almost the population of Ireland) globally (WHO, 2021), as at when this project was completed. This led to governments all over the world closing their borders. Like many other countries, there were restrictions of movements in the United

Kingdom such that people were only allowed to go out for essentials such as shopping for food, medicine, and for exercising (Cabinet Office, 2020). Invariably, this meant that organisations including all universities were closed and students had to move from a face-to-face meeting to online support (UWS, 2020). The unprecedented time led to a unifying agitation among both home and international students from various perspectives. Firstly, those that depended on weekend jobs for maintenance were hit by financial constraints as their source of income had been removed. Secondly, those who had lost their loved ones to the deadly disease had to mourn without the support of others, as they were not able to be with the rest of their families to grieve together. With the unifying frustrations of loneliness and despair among students, the students resorted to different instant messaging platforms to continue to motivate and support one another. This is because the one person that could perfectly understand what the other student was going through was their colleague. In this instance, the supervisor might not be able to give the needed support to the students as they are likely to feel the effect of the pandemic differently. Nonetheless, it was a time to remember for everyone!

The importance of these types of student-to-student support through peer relationships has been emphasised in the literature but, the COVID-19 pandemic further re-emphasised its role in doctoral students' lives. When compared to the number of articles already explored on the role of the student-supervisor relationship, the role of peer relationships is still lagging (Devos et al., 2017), therefore, the current study helps to contribute to the discussion around peer relationships. Also, one of the aspects that have been rarely explored among doctoral students is how they use different instant messaging apps to support themselves through peer relationships. The few ones available were mostly conducted on undergraduates' participants or other levels of education (below doctorate) which is why this study references some MIM research work based on these other levels of education. Likewise,

this study draws its reference from the general literature on trust as none has been conducted on peer relationships concerning the use of MIM apps.

To explore the peer relationships among doctoral students, the peer relationships framework (PRF) by Kram and Isabella (1985) was used. This is because the framework allowed the study to understand the different types of peers that exist among doctoral students as well as emphasising the role of developmental functions (knowledge), self-disclosure and trust in developing peer relationships. Although this framework was originally used by its authors in a work environment, it has been successfully adopted for doctoral education research by researchers such as Terrion and Leonard (2007) and Lee et al. (2017) - the reason it is also adopted for this study.

The PRF by Kram and Isabella (1985) contains important elements needed for this research, but for it to appropriately explore peer relationships among doctoral students of this era, there is the need to consider an element of non-physical interaction which is mostly carried out via mobile instant messaging apps. It even became more relevant during the time this study was conducted as physical interaction was brought to zero and students had to rely on various instant messaging apps to connect and support one another. Since this involves non-physical relationships, the issue of trust becomes important. The concept of trust was highlighted in the PRF as being paramount to peer relationships, it needed to take a more central position than it was originally described in the original framework since the key part of communication (body language) is now missing in this type of online communication.

Trust is another function in the framework that has been highlighted as key to exploring peer relationships. In contrast to how it was presented in the Kram and Isabella (1985) framework, there is the belief that trust is not unidirectional since a student could have trust and distrust in the same student but based on different needs. With this understanding, this study hopes to modify the PRF by Kram and Isabella (1985) by introducing into the framework the use

of MIMs and the concept of trust as described by Lewicki et al. (1998). The two concepts are succinctly described under the next two sections below and explored in detail in the subsequent chapters.

1.2 The role of trust in peer relationships among doctoral students

As mentioned earlier, doctoral students are faced with challenges that are not only academic, and this translates to the understanding that supervisors' support may not be the most relevant during those times. This is because, students see their supervisors as the most influential part of their doctoral journey (Celik, 2013; Vella et al., 2000), they may prefer to keep away their emotional needs from them. On the contrary, these doctoral students could easily approach their peer (s) with whom they have developed a relationship for all sorts of support be it emotional or academic (Lindsay, 2015). They do this with the mindset of receiving the necessary morale boost that would help them forge ahead with their studies. However, it should be noted that the ability to self-disclose to one another does not just occur on day one of meeting each other, rather it develops or diminishes as their level of trust/distrust increases for each other (Proudfoot et al., 2018). That means, if they were able to develop a trusting relationship over time around academic issues, they would now be free to engage in a high or relatively good level of self-disclosure on that level. Yet, having distrust in each other for emotional support. Invariably, the level of trust/distrust influences the type of relationship that exists among doctoral students. Contrastingly, some students would have a distrust of both academic and non-academic issues (see Lewicki et al., 1998). Even though they have the right to how they perceive their colleagues, the aftermath of this is that this group of students tend to hold their problems within and could lead to negative emotions and a build-up of choking feelings to the extent of wanting to drop out from the doctorate. With this, two outcomes are possible. Firstly, the student may take a break (extension) to return another year to complete the doctoral study just as reported by THE (2019) that some students could end

up spending up to 10 years for a three-year doctorate. Secondly, the extension may lead to the student never returning to complete his or her studies – which is one of the challenges of doctoral education in this decade (Wegener, Meier, and Ingerslev, 2016). This is discussed in detail in the next chapter (Chapter 3).

As seen above, trust/distrust likely plays a significant role in the peer relationships experienced among doctoral students. Thus, the reason for its exploration in this study.

1.3 Use of MIM apps among doctoral students

Another key factor to note is that for students to be able to freely seek support during challenging times, the platform to be used must be easily accessible from both sides and the students must be confident that the response he/she receives would be prompted with a possibility for voiced and non-voiced conversations (Cheng, Fu, and Vreede, 2017). As of today, platforms that have been able to serve these purposes are the MIM apps installed on smartphones and the likes (So, 2016). Responses on these platforms are fast, easy, and prompt and could be confidential as smartphones are mostly locked with passwords or pins by their users. The MIMs found among doctoral students for supporting each other are WhatsApp, Facebook Messenger, Skype, Microsoft Teams, Zoom, Hang out among others. Although the lists are endless, the common ones before the COVID-19 pandemic were the first four mentioned above, while Teams and Zoom became popular among students during the pandemic due to their ease of use and multi-tasking features. This comes as no surprise because these two apps have unique functions that may particularly appeal to doctorate users. For example, a review of their functions reveals that Zoom does not require any form of registration with personal details while Teams has all the Microsoft office functions, features that are often needed by doctoral students. In addition, it is usually provided to students as part of their student IT account by universities.

Based on this background, it is important to understand how peer relationships occur among doctoral students via the MIM apps and to check if its inclusion in the modified PRF is feasible.

1.4 Purpose of study

The purpose of this study is to explore a new contemporary phenomenon of how doctoral students support each other using MIM Apps as trusted supporting tools. The study helps to fill the knowledge gap identified in the existing literature around peer relationships among doctoral students by considering the role of MIMs and that of trust/distrust. In addition, it addresses the missing functions in the PRF developed by Kram and Isabella (1985). Based on these aims, the research objectives are:

- To understand the concept of peer relationships among doctoral students at UWS.
- To comprehend the various MIM apps used by these students to enhance their peer relationships.
- To understand the influence of trust on peer relationships and the use of MIM apps as supporting tools.
- To propose guidelines on how the university can enhance peer-to-peer support through peer relationships among doctoral students.

1.5 Methodology

It could be seen from the objectives described above that the study was focused on having a detailed understanding of a new phenomenon of how trust among peers is cultivated using the MIM apps therefore, qualitative methodology was adopted. To ensure that participants have the flexibility to answer questions conversationally during data collection, a semi-structured interview was used (Galletta, 2013). In addition, the focus group method was adopted to explore group conversations and their effect on how the students react to the various questions being asked. It also helped to further emphasise the findings from the interview sessions.

The adoption of a qualitative approach rather than a quantitative or mixed-method is preferred because it permits the discovery and understanding of the collated information (Richards and Morse, 2012). The adopted research design made it possible to listen to and understand the actual views of the people going through the process of peer relationships, thereby increasing the richness of its outcomes (Silverman, 2015). Moreover, the participants chosen for the study have a mix of experience of peer relationships as their doctoral journey at UWS vary based on their area of specialisation and how long they have been on the study.

1.6 Structure of the Thesis

Chapter 2 reviews the existing literature on peer relationships, MIM apps and trust. It reveals that there is ample literature available on peer relationships among doctoral students with the majority identifying its importance, processes, and delivery. It adds that this concept is often examined alongside topics such as the drop-out rate among doctoral students, which is also explored in the literature review chapter of this project. One aspect extensively reviewed is the differences that exist among the different categories of peer relationships. Furthermore, the chapter identifies the major misconceptions around these categories by referencing the existing literature.

Another concept that will be explored in detail in this chapter is the concept of trust. The different models and their points of view are analysed in detail. The justification for choosing one trust model over the other is provided.

The literature review also highlights the role of MIMs on peer relationships while identifying the lack of literature that shows how trust influences peer relationships that occurs via these platforms. It also reveals the scantiness of studies on MIMs among doctoral students as well as the fact no study had investigated the impact of trust on using MIM apps for peer relationships among doctoral students.

Chapter 3, the methodology chapter, a concise explanation of the study's philosophical positions is provided. The choice of selecting the qualitative method and a case study design is discussed respectively. This is followed by a detailed description of the recruitment and sampling strategy, methods of data collection and analysis. The ethical issues considered for this study are also examined alongside the issue of validity and reliability.

Chapter 4 includes the analysis of the collated qualitative data which involves analysing the semi-structured interviews and the focus group sessions while identifying the main themes on the concept of peer relationships. This is achieved with reference to the three functions identified by Kram and Isabella (1985) – developmental functions; self-disclosure and trust (distrust was examined alongside this function). Due to the time the study is conducted, the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on peer relationships is also explored. Likewise, gender role is also examined as it was highlighted by the applicants as being important to the concept of peer relationships. This chapter benefits from discussing the various findings alongside their relationship with extant literature.

Chapter 5, a similar approach to chapter four is used to explain the different types of MIMs apps used among doctoral students as supporting tools, and how trustworthy these online supporting tools are. References are also drawn from the existing literature reviewed in chapter two.

Chapter 6 explores and discusses the different guidelines provided by the UWS doctoral students on how the university could help students in developing the required network of peer-to-peer support throughout their doctoral journey.

Chapter 7, discussions on how the study achieved its four objectives, research contributions to theory, policy and practice were highlighted. This is then followed by future implications of the study, a review of the research processes and the limitations of the study. There are also suggestions for future research.

CHAPTER TWO - LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter identifies the key issues that led to conducting the present study. It discusses peer relationships, trust, and internet-enabled platforms – MIMs - used among students to support one another. Understandably, the kind of support popular in the university system for doctoral students is supervisory and administrative supports. Albeit these are crucial to the attainment of success among doctoral students, it becomes important to also consider other forms of relationship such as peer relationships, an informal support system that could help boost the morale of these students (see Byl et al., 2016; Collings, Swanson, and Watkins, 2016; Devenish et al., 2009; Lee, 2008; Lindsay, 2015, Meschitti, 2019 etc.). This is because the non-completion rate among doctoral students in Europe is still over 30% (THE, 2019), this number is huge when compared to the 10% recorded some decades ago (Woodley, 2004).

As it stands, the literature on peer relationships among doctoral students is limited. However, the few ones available focused on specific aspects of the concept such as peer learning, peer support and peer mentoring. In some literature, these three concepts are addressed as social support (Jairan and Kahl, 2012), socialisation (Meschitti and Carassa, 2014); peer review (Lindsay, 2015), peer education (Byl et al., 2016); peer coaching (Robbins, 2015) and so on. Despite the different name tags, they are all referring to the informal help students provide to their fellow students. For these reasons, this study chose to focus on the three concepts (peer learning, peer support and peer mentoring) found to be the most popular in the literature, since it is not tenable to cover each of the peer relationships keywords found in the literature.

2.1 Enrolment, Attainment and Attrition among Doctoral students

The past few decades have experienced a consistent increase in the enrolment rate among doctoral students (HESA, 2021). According to the data released by HESA (2021), enrolment in the UK increased from 98, 525 in 2015/16 to 101, 350 in 2019/20 with an increment in each of the years in between. This is supposed to be great news for educational institutions as each year experiences an increase in the number of students enrolled for a doctorate in the UK but when compared to the level of attainment for the same period, a rethink would be necessary. For example, the year 2015/16 witnessed 98,525 doctoral students' enrolment and based on the general assertion that UK students are expected to complete their doctorate in three years, these students should have completed their work in 2018/2019. However, as shown in Table 1, only 24,870 students completed their course on time (early attainment), the rest of the students either extended their course (late attainment) or dropped out from the study (attrition). As of today, there is no official statistics on the actual drop rate of doctorate students across the UK, however, some studies have made efforts to estimate the drop-out rate from the data available on attainment rate. Palatinate (2021) conducted a study on ten UK universities to find out about late attainment among doctoral students between the 2015/16 and 2019/2020 academic years. Based on the data collated directly from the universities, they found that about 76% of the doctoral students complete their studies after their actual expected completion date which implies that 24% of these students drop out without achieving a doctorate. Similarly, Sowel et al.'s (2010) and Wegener et al. (2016) studies independently found that only 40-50% of PhD students complete their courses within 10 years of enrolment. As mentioned above, this challenge is not limited to the UK alone as the survey conducted by THE (2019) revealed that a third of every doctoral student in Europe does not complete their thesis within six years.

Table 1: Comparison of the enrolment and the attainment rate of doctoral students released by HESA (2021)

Year	2015/2016	2016/17	2017/18	2018/19	2019/20
Number of Enrolment	98,525	100,085	100,430	102,030	101,350
Number of Attainment (on time)	22,825	23,650	24,870	24,930	24,140

In addition to the UK/Europe experience, the high attrition rate among doctoral students has been reported in other countries such as Australia, Canada, and the USA for decades (Becher, Henkel, and Kogan, 1994; Bourke et al., 2004; Harris, 1996; Robbins, 1963; Youngman, 1994). When this situation was compared to a few decades ago, the report was completely different. Woodley's (2004) report stated that in the 1960s, only about 10% of UK students failed to earn a degree after three years of study and the drop-out rate was never seen as an issue as it was at a minuscule rate.

The attrition rate among doctoral students has now become a concern for higher education authorities and the governments (Wegener et al., 2016). To help abate the situations, many students and supervisors make efforts to prevent attrition as this is, no doubt viewed as a failure to all the parties involved (Ampaw and Jaeger, 2012; Lott, Gardner, and Powers, 2009; Lovitts and Nelson, 2000). The effect of the failure could even be more critical for those that had to drop out at a later stage of the degree compared to the earlier stage due to the huge investment (time, money, knowledge) that must have gone into the study.

Although there have been a few variations over the years, the identified factors for attrition among doctoral students have remained similar. Lovitts (2002) explored attrition among doctoral students using quantitative methods and interviews. She was able to identify that the problem was multi-faceted. One of the key features of the study was its ability to gather

information directly from the drop-out students who were asked to reflect on why they left the training. From the study, there was an understanding that not all attrition was bad because some students could decide that they have not made the right choice of study thus dropping out. Other factors could include serious issues such as academic, financial, and personal reasons.

On the other hand, Gardner (2009) listened to current students and faculty members and was able to affirm most of Lovitts' findings, especially personal reasons, as being one of the key factors for attrition. In contrast to the poor academic quality of students identified by Lovitts (2002), Gardner found that lack of motivation, initiative and ability was given by the faculty members as factors that led to attrition among the doctoral students. Other areas that have been explored around attrition among doctoral students include supervisor relationship (Becher et al., 1994; Nettles and Millet, 2006; Devine and Hunter, 2017); socialisation experience (Gondalez, 2006), race (Ellis, 2001), low-quality resources in university due to poor funding (OECD, 2016), poor selection process of candidates (Bekova, 2019), and insufficient student support (Becher et al., 1994; Devos et al., 2017; Golde, 2005) among others. However, it should be noted that the proposition that personal reasons are one of the key factors that lead to attrition has long been confirmed by Rudd (1986) who cautioned policymakers of that time that the failure to complete studies may not solely be because of academic problems but also due to other student issues. This statement was later supported by Lovitts' (2002) report. Comparatively, Wright and Cochrane's (2000) research on 3,579 doctoral students between 1984 and 1993 revealed several factors affecting completion rates. The type of academic subject being studied, the quality of students and access to research grants were the main ones highlighted. According to their results, gender did not influence timely completion. Meanwhile, the study by Bowen and Rudenstine (2014) suggested otherwise. It stated that women have a higher attrition rate than their male counterparts due to other

commitments they may have. These other commitments make them rely on perseverance and intrinsic motivation to complete their studies (Castro et al., 2011), and this does not often work. Sverdlik et al. (2018) who explored the factors that influence completion rate, found that although there are external and internal factors affecting completion rate, they are all connected. As an illustration, a student facing financial constraints may not have the motivation to work on his project. Invariably, he could be seen as a nonchalant student by his/her supervisor, thereby affecting their relationship.

In understanding the factors that lead to attrition, researchers dedicated resources to reviewing each of the above-mentioned factors to provide a long-lasting solution to the high attrition rate among students. Swinnerton-Dyer (1982) suggested the provision of resources for better support of students, better supervision, and penalising departments and universities with low submission rates would reduce the attrition rate. Harris (1996) and Youngman (1994) independently produced a list that also reiterated those already highlighted in Swinnerton-Dyer's (1982) recommendations. Lee (2008) advanced the work of Brew (2001) and Pearson and Brew (2002) to explore one of the key factors that have been identified to influence attrition rate: supervisory support (Berry 2017; Subramanian et al., 2013). Their findings proposed five approaches to improve this relationship and they are i) Functional – students' understanding of how to manage their project time; ii) Enculturation – students are guided on how to join the academic community; iii) Critical thinking - here, students are trained on how to be an independent thinker of their work; iv) Emancipation – this is about mentoring and coaching the students on how to engage in questioning and upgrading themselves, and v) developing a quality relationship which involves inspiring and caring for the students. In a later publication, Lee, and his co-author Aitchison (Lee and Aitchison, 2009) admitted that even though the functions identified in the above model has been widely useful, these students are still generally left on their own to learn the rules and adjust accordingly. Also, one of the groups

of students who suffer the most from this assumed independence is the international students as they had to grapple with cultural differences alongside academic challenges among other factors (Laufer and Gorup, 2018).

Despite these proffered solutions, the attrition rate for countries such as the USA and the UK within six years has still not fallen massively below 50% (NSF, 2018; THE, 2019). The reason might not be far-fetched as the reality is that even though the availability of functional supervisory support is essential when other important factors are lacking, there is a tendency for the doctoral student not to succeed. Meschitti's (2019) argument was that, undoubtedly, the supervisory arrangement is one crucial formal support that must be provided by the university. However, for a successful doctoral experience, the remaining factors have to be provided and managed as well. Just as mentioned by Nordentoft, Thomsen, and Wichmann-Hansen (2013), formal support might not be sufficient in ensuring a smooth doctoral experience without the likes of outstanding ethics of care such as peer learning and peer support. Of course, this is alongside the support provided by their supervisors (Jazvac-Martek, Chen, and McAlpine, 2011). Therefore, to reduce the drop-out rate among doctoral students, researchers are now beginning to explore other forms of supports that may be of help. To reiterate, existing literature confirmed that peer relationships are one form of informal support that could help in this instance, and it is analysed in detail below.

2.2 Peer relationships and their components - Peer learning, Peer mentoring and Peer support

2.2.1 Peer relationships as a general concept

Even though this is a relatively new concept in doctoral education, it has been widely explored in areas outside this domain. Its study outside the education system has been largely due to its helpful role among people going through one challenge or another (see Naslund et al., 2016; Berndt and Ladd, 1989; Conner et al., 2018; Solomon, 2004).

Within the education system, peer relationships have also been confirmed to be important. Dennis, Phinney, and Chuateco (2005) conducted a study on 100 ethnic minority college students using a longitudinal approach. The study found that there is a positive correlation between peer support and academic performance. That is, those who could socialise well with their peers have a better GPA than those who do not have these relationships. From the perspective of students with disabilities, Burgstahler (1997) emphasised that although having mentoring schemes are important because the creation of an enabling environment for informal peer support groups would not only help to empower disabled students but also provide them with adequate information sharing and creation of a sense of belongings through friendships.

Within the university system, a detailed explanation of how peers support each other was given by researchers such as Boud, Cohen, and Sampson (2014) and Hadjioannou, Shelton, and Dhanarattigannon (2007). With a focus on five students who met regularly as a study group, the latter found that students were able to support one another emotionally, academically as well as in professional development which in turn translated to on-time completion of their training. Their findings on emotional support are similar to what was put forward by Jazvac-Martek et al. (2012) that even those that are independent still need some emotional support from their peers for the enhancement of their confidence level. Becher et al. (1994) submitted that the first year is the most vulnerable for students' dropouts and it is similar to the outcome of Lovitts and Nelson (2000) who found that over 30% of dropouts was reported to occur in the first year of study of doctoral students. For Nerad and Miller's (1996) research, their position was that the highest rate of drop-out is normally within the first two years of doctoral studies. Meanwhile, Wegener et al. (2016) maintain that even those who remain enrolled up to the final stage may find the writing phase most daunting for them. The reason is that they are expected to be

independent with their research even though they may lack the confidence to successfully achieve this without extra support. Therefore, having a good relationship with colleagues, who understand exactly how one is feeling, is important as they would understand the best way to support one another.

2.2.2 Importance of Peer relationships among Doctoral Students

There is no doubt that students may generally face study-related exhaustion which includes tiredness, emotional deficiency, and fatigue. Peer relationships which include the likes of peer support, peer learning, and peer mentoring have been affirmed to benefit doctoral students in different ways (Berry, 2017; Boud and Lee, 2005; Hadjioannou, Shelton, and Dhanarattigannon, 2007; Lee et al., 2017, Lovitts, 2002; McPherson, Punch, and Graham, 2018).

Chui et al. (2014) conducted an interview, with 12 doctoral students in APA-accredited counselling psychology PhD programme across the United States, to understand the importance of peer relationships among these students. For this study, a peer relationships scale was used to measure the students' closeness with their peers. Just like other scholars, they found that peer relationship was less formal and more open, and the sharing of knowledge facilitated improved training experiences for the students. Similarly, Hadjuionnou et al. (2007) emphasised that peer relationships with fellow doctoral students not only help to improve their academic writing but also contributes to better dissemination of non-academic information, reduction in loneliness as well as emotional support (Bettinson and Haven-Tang, 2021). Emotional support in the sense that they can comfortably discuss their challenges with their peers compared to when they have to discuss this with their supervisor. Moreover, every student feels lonely at some stage during their study but the ability to engage in some sort of support helps to reduce its effect (McLaughlin and Sillence, 2018). Simply put, students can deal with the challenges experienced during their doctorate by forming a network

of social relationships (Ernest and Cacioppo, 1999). In addition to reducing loneliness, evidence has also shown that peer relationships enhance the well-being of students (Doody et al., 2018) which could invariably enhance the timely completion of doctoral studies (Boud and Lee, 2005; Lindsay, 2015; Minor et al., 2013). A study found that students who seek help from peers have a lower level of burnout in their career ten years onward compared to those who did not (Salmela-Aro and Read, 2017).

Despite these affirmations, peer relationships research is only gradually receiving the deserving attention among researchers as more evidence continues to reveal that it is one of the most reliable support available to students. It is not unexpected that the pace of attention in this area is slow. This is perhaps based on two reasons. Firstly, doctoral students are expected to be confidently independent at this stage (Berry, 2017). Secondly, attention on peer relationships among doctoral students is a non-traditional approach in higher education settings but no matter how slow, the most important is the fact that it is gradually gaining the desired attention.

The section below clarifies the differences between the three peer relationships concepts (peer support, peer learning and peer mentoring mentioned above).

2.2.3 Clarifying the differences between the concepts of peer relationships

The confusion around the interchangeable use of peer relationships terms such as peer learning, peer mentoring, peer coaching, peer support in the non-education system, is dated as far back as the 1970s (Gray, 1988). Despite the early warnings that researchers should ensure more clarity around the meaning of the different peer relationships terms, the problem could still be found in many academic writings today. To this extent, the likes of Gibson (2005) and D'Abate, Eddy, and Tannenbaum (2003) warned that insufficient clarity would make it difficult to understand the comparison and differences between the various functions of the peer relationships mentioned earlier.

The truth is that although these different terminologies may be close in meaning, there are still some differences between them and, the lack of clarity on the types of peer relationships has made it difficult to identify appropriate interventions for the challenges surrounding these concepts (Chao, 2009; D'Abate, et al., 2003; Gray, 1988). Just as mentioned before, it was observed that the commonly used terms are peer support, peer mentoring therefore, for consistency purposes, this study sticks to these three terms throughout the project.

To provide some clarifications, the definition of 'peer' and 'relationship' was examined. According to the Cambridge dictionary (2020), a peer is defined as, 'a person who is the same age or has the same social position or the same abilities as other people in a group' while a relationship is simply, 'how two or more people feel and behave towards each other. The existing literature has also made efforts to define some of these key concepts. To Kram (2001), peers are partners and developers, providing psychosocial support and engaging in information sharing and development of knowledge. With these definitions, peer relationships could then be described as how people of similar age or abilities relate with each other. It could be deduced that for any form of support, mentoring or learning to take place among peers, there is a need to have a relationship of some sort. The various elements of peer learning, peer support, and peer mentoring are examined next.

2.2.3.1 Peer support

Toda (2005) defined peer support as the utilisation of available social resources among students of the same age or social conditions. This concept has been in use all around the world as far back as the 70s, although majorly in lower-level schools. In the UK, peer support became popular around the early 1990s and it was reported to have focused on primary school students before being extended to other areas such as community services and young offenders (Baginsky, 2004). With an extension of ideas from the UK, Australia also kick-starts what was known as the provision of moral guidance, help, and advice to students by members of school

staff who were assigned different roles. These roles would later be upgraded to the provision of a care-enabled environment for a student to seek help whenever it is necessary. In short, James (2011) maintains that peer support became famous for helping students because it was contextual and does not believe in one-size-fits-all principles. With slightly different approaches, studies on peer support in schools have been explored in different parts of the world (i.e., Canada, USA, Finland, Italy, Saudi Arabia, South Africa among others) (Cowie, 2009). As an example, Japan runs a programme known as Japanese Peer Support where students are trained and are expected to train the junior students (Cowie, 2009).

There was an emphasis on the fact that peer support plays a key role even during peer learning (Doody et al., 2018). That was why researchers with interest in this area advocated for adequate provision of platforms that would encourage this type of help among students in a higher education institution (Lindsay, 2015; Wolff et al., 2013) due to its informal nature (Laidlaw et al., 2016).

Adopting Lee's framework (2008) and Latona and Browne's (2001) framework respectively, Lindsay's (2015) research was able to confirm that peer support, alongside some other factors (such as emotional and financial support, great supervisory arrangements, departmental support, peer review of thesis, encouragement from fellow students), positively influence the doctoral experience. Just like other researchers, Lindsay (2015) has been able to use her study to emphasise the importance of one of the key aspects of peer relationships among doctoral students.

Importantly, it should be noted that the descriptions given under this subsection are synonymous with the various kinds of general, emotional support that students could provide for each other. Thus, the reason for grouping them under peer support in this study. However, Lindsay's use of peer review relates closely to how peer learning is described in this research and other reviewed literature in this area.

2.2.3.2 Peer Learning

According to Topping (2005, p. 631), peer learning is ‘the acquisition of knowledge and skills through active helping and supporting status equals or matched companions’. Similarly, Boud et al. (2014) defined peer learning as the process by which students engage with each other in learning activities to increase their academic capabilities. They added that it could take place in a formal or non-formal setting. Formal in the sense that the university (or supervisor) may be the organiser of the peer learning sessions. Meanwhile, informally as it could be organised by the students themselves either for a particular number of students or for the whole group. Whichever approach is adopted, this form of peer relationship allows students to gain new knowledge and skills from each other without feeling pressured. This is as a result of being able to regulate their learning pace by themselves without the interference of any university official.

One of the comprehensive studies conducted on peer learning among doctoral students is that of Meschitti (2019). Her research was on how peer learning improves the academic capabilities of doctoral students in a Switzerland university. This one-year long ethnographic research used the socio-constructivist conceptualisation theory of learning inspired by the Activity theory (developed by Lev Vygotsky in 1980). The participating team was made up of 10 members – two research fellows; one senior researcher; a chair and six PhD students who were mainly international students and at different stages of their research. Data was collated through observations and in-depth interviews methods. The study reported that during the weekly meetings, the students were allowed to direct the activities which may include reviewing and commenting on each other’s work or having a discussion around any preferred topic. With this approach, the doctoral students felt encouraged to explore more outside the peer learning sessions and would most likely look forward to the next meeting. Another feature was the

diversity of knowledge among the group members – they all had their expertise in different areas of research and were able to share this to improve one another’s project. Most importantly, it was found that there was less pressure as they all seem relaxed going through the process since they were solely in charge of the learning pace. The study concluded that organised peer learning created an enabling environment for doctoral students to want to work hard on their projects. It should, however, be noted that the conducive conditions (living cost was covered), including a dedicated workspace, also helped the students. One of the possible controls mentioned in the study was the fact that the student-participants had the same supervisor, and this might have contributed to the ease of ensuring that all the students attended the meetings.

When this outcome feedback is going to the one conducted among other postgraduate students, a similar outcome was found. An example is a research by Byl et al. (2016) that examined the perception of first-year postgraduate students on how peer learning improved the academic and social integration of the students. Twenty-five individual interviews and five focus groups were conducted between the spring and winter periods. The result shows that activities such as meet and greet, team building, and informal ‘befriending’ scheme helps to enhance their social integration processes. Besides, sessions involving peer education, peer modelling, and physical or online peer counselling also helped improve their academic achievement. A comparison between these two comprehensive studies indicates that irrespective of the level of education, every student will benefit from supports provided by their peers whether it was organised formally or informally. This is because a student who is confident to relate with fellow peers for help academically and non-academically will be confident enough to progress in his/her project except in case of unavoidable emergencies. Also, the review under this subsection has shown that peer learning could either be formal or informal depending on the approach used.

2.2.3.3 Peer mentoring

Byington (2010) defined mentoring as a relationship in which a mentor guides a person (mentee) through support, advice, and feedback. Similarly, Parsloe and Wray (2000) defined mentoring as a means of exchanging ideas, knowledge, and support to bring out the best in the mentee. In addition to being an exchange, there is a need for it to be reciprocal as much as being a form of relationship. An encompassing definition was given by Kram (1983) who described peer mentoring as a relationship between two people of similar age or experience helping each other whether formally or informally to enhance psychosocial functions and career-related functions. Lee et al. (2017) added that peer mentoring is a function that contributes to the development of the individuals involved in peer relationships. Simply put, both the mentor and the mentee are expected to gain from the peer mentoring processes. As highlighted in their studies, benefits such as emotional support and on-time completion of studies are some of the benefits of peer mentoring. Husband and Jacobs (2009) emphasised that the provision of a positive learning environment; encouragement of self-regulated attitude to learning provided by peer mentoring leads to an improvement in the academic achievements of the students as well as an improvement to the motivation and confidence level of both the mentor and the mentee. Collings et al. (2016) also contributed to the understanding of the role of peer mentoring. They found that there is a positive correlation between functions such as academic achievement, mental support, satisfaction, and the peer mentoring scheme.

By adopting Kram and Isabella's (1985) model which is one of the regularly cited frameworks for peer relationships, Terrion and Leonard (2007) were able to conclude that the adoption of peer mentoring schemes leads to both career enhancement and psychosocial improvement for students. The career enhancement includes confidence and motivation in self-enhancement especially when both mentor and the mentee are on a similar programme. In terms of

psychosocial supports, functions such as enhanced communication skills, supportiveness, and trustworthiness were found.

It should be noted that even though peer coaching is one of the popular terms used interchangeably with peer mentoring, Gottesman (2009) warned that coaching among peers should not be a process involved with supervision and evaluation rather it should be seen as a process where peers observe and give feedback to each other to improve their capabilities (readers are referred to Foltos 2013; Knight 2007; and Robbins, 2015 for further understanding of the concept of peer coaching).

In sum, the review under this sub-section suggests that peer mentoring needs to be a well-designed process to achieve its goals and objectives. These formalities may also be expected during peer learning but not as streamlined as peer mentoring (see Meschitti, 2019). For these reasons, it could be said that peer mentoring is usually a planned process carried out with the awareness of any of the university authorities, could involve academic or non-academic issues. Peer learning, on the other hand, is mostly conducted or approved by one of the institution's authorities (mostly the supervisor) to improve the academic capability of a group of doctoral students. It could, however, be organised informally by the students for the same purpose. Peer support is the informal peer relationships whose priority is on providing the emotional support needed to boost the morale of the other doctoral colleague(s) along with other general supports.

As this area of study gains acceptance, it is important to identify the differences that exist between these terms to ensure that its users are able to adopt the recommendations proposed for each of them without mixing them up. Having said that, the three forms of peer relationships reviewed here have been confirmed to have positive effects on doctoral experience when adopted correctly. However, some studies (such as Chui et al., 2014; Jairam and Kahl, 2012; Lindsay, 2015) independently found that aside from helping each other, some students

found peer relationships toxic as they might often be pressurised to act in a particular way whenever they are among their peers. In an interview with thirty-one doctoral students, Jairam and Kahl (2012) found that apart from the positive influences on the students' social support system, negative influences such as competition, and peer pressure were also present. Nevertheless, as it is with every other situation, the concept of peer relationships is expected to have both positive and negative sides but what is most important is the fact that its positives have been confirmed to outweigh its negatives (see Chui et al., 2014; Lee et al., 2017; Lindsay, 2015). A summary of the different concepts of peer relationships discussed here is given below in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Proposed interpretation of the meaning of Peer support; Peer learning and Peer mentoring as used in this thesis (Source: the author, adapted from the cited studies above)

Another point to note is that the review of the literature on peer relationships among doctoral students reflects the one-sided approach adopted during data collection. In that, most researchers focus on collating data from students on the conventional doctorate – PhD. While this has helped to understand this group’s perspective, it may not necessarily represent the views of other doctoral students such as DBA, EdD, DHSC among others. This is because the structure and the approach towards each of the programmes are completely different from each other thus, may likely require different approaches. Using the Doctorate in Business Administration (DBA) students in the UK as a reference, they are expected to spend a compulsory one year in the classroom learning about various concepts of business management and scientific research, with no assigned desk space. This is different for the PhD students who are expected to have a desk space or an office to themselves, where they are expected to

commence work on their project as early as their day one in the university. Moreover, DBA students focus on the practical concepts and are generally being trained to become future leaders of businesses, unlike the PhD students whose focus is on the theory that underpins their area of studies while being trained to ideally become academics. These differences would likely influence their views on peer relationships. Therefore, it is also important to explore peer relationships among non-conventional doctoral students. To help fill this gap, this study included both PhD and DBA students for a detailed understanding of the concept from both types of doctoral students. In this study, the DBA students of UWS were choosing to serve this purpose for two reasons. Firstly, it was not feasible to recruit all the different disciplines studying for a doctorate at UWS as students could not be recruited face-to-face as at when the study was conducted (study relied only on those that responded to invitations via emails). Secondly, compared to other non-conventional doctorates, the DBA is the only doctoral training ongoing at the London campus (the only UWS campus outside Scotland). Therefore, the analysis for this study might not be complete if the doctoral students in that part of UWS are ignored hence the reason for their inclusion.

2.3 Kram and Isabella's 1985 peer relationship framework (PRF)

The PRF is one of the recognised frameworks for studying peer relationships among doctoral students and thus its adoption for this study (Lee et al., 2017). The framework was originally developed to highlight the existence of relationships other than mentorship in the workplace. Referencing previous studies (i.e., Dalton, Thompson, and Price, 1977; Hall, 1976; Kram, 1983), Kram and Isabella (1985) argued that albeit mentoring helps employees in both career and personal development, other relationships also contribute to the development of members of an organisation. The study added that, while mentoring could provide career enhancement

by providing work exposure, guidance, sponsorship and counselling, its formal nature makes it susceptible to putting the mentees under the pressure of obeying the mentor due to fear of demotion which could eventually lead to a loss of trust over a while. Due to these shortcomings, these two researchers decided to explore a less formal alternative to a mentoring relationship. To actualise their aim, they interviewed 15 key people in an organisation followed by an interview with work colleagues identified to be their peers in one way or the other. In total, 25 relationship pairs were explored. It is worth noting that there was an emphasis on ensuring that the participants represented the three different career stages (early, middle, and late).

The study was able to highlight the differences between mentoring and peer relationships that existed among work colleagues as described in Table 2 below. They found that unlike conventional mentoring, which is often dominated by the senior worker, peer relationships are mostly characterised by mutual emotional support, personal feedback, and friendship. The study also found that different career stage influences the needs and concerns of colleagues. Most importantly, Kram and Isabella's (1985) findings showed that there are three different types of workplace peers - Information Peer, Collegial Peer, and Special Peer – with each of them depending on factors such as trust, developmental functions, and self-disclosure (Figure 2). Their submission was that trust played a huge role in the categorisation of these peer types. *Information peer* involves those that share information about work with little emotional support or personal feedback, characterised by a low level of trust. *Collegial peer* engages in moderate emotional support, feedback, and confirmation. Here, there could be personal discussions outside work such as family among other things such as weather and holidays etc. *Special Peer* was noted to be the most intimate among the three identified peer relationships as there is a high level of trust between these pairs. Thus, leading to high self-disclosure and invariably,

having the highest level of psychosocial support. According to the authors, these types of colleagues discuss everything with one another without any doubt of being backstabbed.

Table 2: Differences between mentoring and Peer relationships (Kram and Isabella, 1985)

Mentoring Relationships	Peer relationships
<p>Career-enhancing functions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sponsorship ▪ Coaching ▪ Exposure and visibility ▪ Protection ▪ Challenging work assignments 	<p>Career-enhancing functions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Information sharing ▪ Career strategising ▪ Job-related feedback
<p>Psychosocial functions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Acceptance and confirmation ▪ Counselling ▪ Role modelling ▪ Friendship 	<p>Psychosocial functions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Confirmation ▪ Emotional support ▪ Personal feedback ▪ Friendship
<p>Special attribute</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Complementary 	<p>Special attribute</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Mutuality

Figure 2: Three types of peer relationships and their primary functions as identified by Kram and Isabella (1985).

Due to the credibility of the Kram and Isabella (1985) framework, researchers in higher education have adapted it to understand how peer relationships work among doctoral students. For example, Lee et al. (2017) explored the perception of doctoral students of their peer relationships using the PRF. Unlike the work setting investigated by Kram and Isabella (1985), the focus of these researchers was on higher education. The participants were doctoral students at the School of Information, South-Eastern University (case study university name not provided). To ensure adequate representation of the 12 interviewed participants, gender and country of origin and year of study were considered through ‘purposeful convenience sampling’ (p. 117). Their findings confirmed Kram and Isabella’s (1985) conclusion by identifying the three types of peers proposed in the PRF. However, Lee et al.’s (2017) research brought another dimension to the framework by identifying another type of peer - *dysfunctional peers*. As described in their study, the peers in this type of relationship do not relate or communicate with each other due to their differences in personal and academic views.

Based on the successful adoption of the PRF by Lee et al. (2017), it was also used in this study. By adopting this framework, the researcher was able to understand the nature of support the UWS doctoral students give to each other through peer relationships. This further helped to understand how trust influences the peer relationships developed during the use of MIM apps as supporting tools. Meanwhile, the identification of the roles of trust could not have been possible without the review of the major theories of trust which is discussed next.

2.4 Definitions and review of the main theories of trust

As mentioned earlier in the review, any discussion on peer relationships would most likely involve mentioning the issues of trust therefore it is important to explore the concept (Gill et al., 2016; Kanthak and Hertel, 2016; Mayer et al., 1995; McNight and Chervany, 1996). Trust

had a concept that has been at the centre of many research foci as far back as the 1950s (Lewicki et al., 1998), and as the interest across all disciplines increases, so does its descriptions (Yamagishi and Yamagishi, 1994). Most researchers give at least two definitions of trust in their study and have to admit that trust has varying meanings (Blomqvist and Stahle, 2000; Williamson, 1993). To this extent, the concept of trust was once named a ‘confusing potpourri’ (Shapiro, 1987, p.625).

One of the earliest definitions of trust was given by Barber (1983), where he defined it as reliant on a person or thing. While some of the definitions of trust are a good starting point, they are not encompassing enough, therefore, missing out on key features of trust. For example, Barber’s (1983) definition has not been able to clarify that trust requires at least two parties and that it is reciprocal (see Whitener et al., 1998). Secondly, it has not emphasised the importance of ensuring that trust should never involve any form of coercion. One of the early definitions that tried to capture these key terms was the one provided by Gambetta (1988) who stated that trust may exist amid the risk of uncertainty, ignorance and could even be based on unknown or unknowable actions but should never take place in a forceful environment. It is therefore believed that when defining the concept of trust, these key points should feature whether directly or indirectly.

A few scholars (i.e., Mayer et al., 1995; Mishra, 1996; Rousseau et al., 1998) have tried to infuse these features in their definitions with a unique consideration for the term ‘vulnerability’ used in a very early definition by Read (1962). According to this scholar, trust is when the trustor has the confidence that his interest is protected and that they could share their vulnerability and be confident that it is safe in the trusting relationship. Rousseau et al. (1998) defined trust as a psychological state that consists of the intention of accepting to be vulnerable

to others' actions with the belief that the other individual/group have positive intentions towards them.

From a multidimensional perspective, Mishra (1996) believes that trust could only take place when one party is willing to be vulnerable to another group concerning their reliability, concern, openness, and competence. However, a change in one dimension would trigger a change in the levels of the other dimensions. On a similar note, Mayer et al. (1995) based their definitions on two beliefs (i) perceptions that the other person has Ability, Integrity, and Benevolence; and (ii) the propensity to trust. Thus, defining trust as the willingness to be vulnerable to the other individual based on their ability, integrity, and benevolence. Another definition that implies vulnerability is that from Misztal (1996) who maintains that people tend to trust others due to their belief in them despite the uncertainties that may be involved. For Sheppard and Sherman (1998), trust is about having faith in the actions of the other person(s). Whitener and colleague's definition emphasised that trust takes place only when the agents involved would be benevolent to each other (Whitener et al., 1998). One of the definitions considered from the context of peers is that of McAllister (1995) whose opinion reveals that trust is about the 'evidence that a peer's behaviour is consistent with norms of reciprocity and fairness and that the peer follows through on commitments' (p.28). In appendix A is the table that summarises the definitions of trust as provided by scholars over 50 years.

Despite the seemingly comprehensive descriptions given above, McNight and Chervany (1996) maintain that these definitions have not still considered all aspects of trust. With this in mind, they conducted a comprehensive review of 60 research papers on trust. Their review revealed that most of the definitions were contextual and intended to set out a more unifying meaning, they regrouped all the definitions identified in the 60 reviewed papers into three categories – (i) Impersonal/Structural, those definitions that described trust as being an

institutional entity and not a personal feature (e.g. Garfinkel, 1963; Shapiro, 1987a) (ii) Dispositional, those definitions that believed trust is connected to the personal features of its trustor and recipients (Rotter, 1967; Wrightsman, 1991); and (iii) Personal/Interpersonal, those that believe trust either exist between two individuals or among groups in a particular situation.

As it is almost impossible to cover all aspects of trust, the authors (McKnight and Chervany, 1996) followed the advice of Sutton and Staw (1995) by ensuring that they focus on their area of interest. They developed six constructs, as shown in Figure 3, which are Trusting Intention, Trusting Behaviour, Trusting Beliefs, System Trust, Dispositional Trust, and Situational Decision to Trust. For illustration purposes, when person A has a *trusting belief* in person B, the person will have a *trusting intention* to depend on them. This will, in turn, reflect on how they behave towards person B (*Trusting behaviour*). What has just been described is more characteristic of trust that may exist between specific persons, the remaining three constructs move to a more general position. As the name implies, *system trust* is about having a belief in an established, unbiased structure. On the other hand, *dispositional trust* is about having a generally positive view of trusting people. Finally, a *situational decision to trust* is when a person has made up his/her mind on whether to trust due to an expected positive outcome irrespective of their understanding of the recipients. They developed more on their research position by using this model to explain the difference between trust and distrust in their 2001 publication - Trust/Distrust beliefs; Trust/Distrust Intentions; Trust/Distrust-related behaviour; Disposition to Trust/Distrust; and Institution-Based Trust/Distrust (see McKnight and Chervany, 2001).

Figure 3: McKnight and Chervany, 2001 model on trust

A recent publication by Gill et al. (2016) argues that the likes of McKnight and Chervoney's (2001) description of trust is based on inputs of trust and its relations to trustees. To give a different perspective, their study was focused on providing a more output-based definition thus defining Trust as 'the expectation that others can be relied upon, demonstrated through one's readiness to talk about issues with which one experiences feelings of vulnerability' (Gill et al., 2016; p. 106).

By the year 2000, Gambetta had focused on trying to explore the concept of trust from a different point of view. He viewed trust as being symmetrical to distrust (also referred to as blind trust). According to his illustrations, peoples' general expectations from others could be described as a threshold on a probabilistic distribution. To describe the continuum of trust, a number line was developed with 'complete trust' represented with one (1) and 'complete distrust' denoted by zero (0) while the mid-point of uncertainty is 0.50 as shown in Figure 4 below. According to this number line representation, a person is said to be trustworthy when the line is towards 1, that is the probability that the trustee will be of positive behaviour to the trustor is high. On the contrary, the person is seen with distrust when the probability is low, that is when the number line is towards 0. As said earlier, there is a point of uncertainty where no one is sure of the outcome of the trusting relationship. Gambetta (2000) also posits that trust should not involve coercion or force of any kind, people should have the freedom to exit, betray, and defect from the trusting relationship at any time. Finally, there is the belief that trust

could help allay fear during uncertainty and when the actions of the other person (s) are unknown. To sum it up, he defined trust (or, symmetrically, distrust) as:

‘a particular level of the subjective probability with which an agent assesses that another agent or group of agents will perform a particular action, both before he can monitor such action (or independently of his capacity to be able to monitor it) and in a context in which it affects his own action’ -
(Gambetta, 2000, pp. 218-219).

Figure 4: Trust model by Gambetta (2000)

There may not have been an agreed definition yet, but it would seem all components have been identified such that recent scholars now build on or re-produce the terminologies already produced by the past researchers. For example, Adjekum, Ienca, and Vayena (2017) reiterated the components of trust as identified by Baier (1986) which are Trustor, Trustee, and Task to be fulfilled. PytlikZillig and Kimbrough (2016) only broadened the terms by adding that it would also involve risk-taking, voluntary involvement by trustor with a positive expectation.

To avoid repetition in the name of producing an original definition of trust, the advice of Barney and Hansen (1994) would be embraced, and it states that whatever the stand is, there is a need to establish confidence that will ensure that none of the agents involved would take advantage of the other party's vulnerability. Similarly, Sutton and Staw (1995) advised that since the possibility of a single study covering all aspects of trust is untenable, researchers should identify and succinctly justify its preferred position. Based on this understanding, the rest of this section identifies the

different theories of trust and gives clarity on why the preferred model was chosen to make up the conceptual framework of this study.

To start with, Mayer et al.'s (1995) model of trust (Figure 5) is one of the widely accepted theories of trust in the 21st century. Having reviewed 23 articles and books, these authors concluded that trust has three important functions: Ability; Benevolence and Integrity. *Ability* involves having the skills and features needed for the completion of a task, just as mentioned earlier. This function is domain-specific since it refers to the technical skills required in a specific field. *Benevolence* is when a trustor is willing to do good to the trustee without necessarily having a motive to be rewarded with some form of gain. The third feature is *Integrity* – this is when the set of values of the trustor aligns with that of the trustee. That is both the giver and receiver of trust have certain principles that align with each other. Another key point from this model is that whoever is willing to engage in a trust relationship must be ready to take the risk that comes with it. Despite the acceptability of this model, there were limitations. Firstly, the model seems to suggest that trust is unidirectional. That is, a trust could only happen from the trustor to one specific receiver. This assumption was amended in their article published in 2007 (Schoorman, Mayer, and Davis, 2007) where there were detailed explanations of how trust could happen from both sides of its recipients. The 2007 publication also maintained that trust and distrust are opposite of each other despite the argument by some researchers (mostly Lewicki et al., 1998) that they are of two different entities and should be addressed separately.

Figure 5: Mayer et al.'s (1995) model on trust

The trust model by Lewicki et al. (1998) was not to dispute Mayer et al.'s (1995) position on trust but to propose that distrust is a different concept and should not be addressed as the opposite of trust. According to Lewicki et al. (1998, p.439), 'trust is the confident positive expectations regarding another's conduct while distrust is the confident negative expectations regarding another's conduct in a context of personal risk'. They maintained that trust and distrust are not simply the opposite of each other since it is possible to trust as well as distrust the same recipient in different circumstances. It should also be mentioned that this position aligns with most earlier views on the context of trust (e.g., Deutsch, 1958; Mellinger, 1956; Read, 1962). According to Lewicki et al. (1998), trust could exist in four different forms: Low Trust/Low Distrust; High Trust/Low Distrust; Low Trust/High Distrust; High Trust/High Distrust. They asserted that a low level of trust does not automatically translate to a high level of distrust as they are characterised by different attributes. For example, while a low level of trust is bound to be with no hope, no confidence, passivity, hesitance, and no faith, a high level of distrust is made up of cynicism, vigilance, fear, watchfulness, and scepticism.

For clarity purpose, Lewicki et al. (1998), as illustrated in Table 3 below, emphasised the importance of a relationship and how actually, it is multifaceted. They illustrated that the relationship that exists among individuals would influence their level of collaborations on different occasions as they may simply trust each other on a particular project due to their skills

(High trust), but still have a distrust on personal issues. This will translate to a high distrust in that perspective leading to one form of their typology - *high trust/high distrust* (calculus-based trust). Invariably, those within *low trust/low distrust* are ambivalent and non-committal since there is nothing to trust or distrust among them; simply put, they have little or no relationship. This could also be called deterrence-based trust (Rousseau et al., 1998). Before Lewicki et al.'s work, Kramer's (1994) comprehensive work on paranoid cognitions had also helped shed light on the nature of distrust among group members and organisations. His findings revealed that students with a significant level of paranoia are generally suspicious of others and have a high level of distrust. In this case, distrust could also be a personal issue which means it does not matter the actions of the other members of the group, these types of people would always be suspicious of other people's actions as they would always feel the other person is out to harm them (High Distrust). Relating this assertion to Lewicki et al.'s (1998) illustration would imply that these types of people would often belong to the *low trust/high distrust* (also known as a security-based trust) spectrum no matter the effort of their colleagues and vice versa for those with a low level of paranoid (low distrust). Of course, the preferred typology in any group would be a *high trust/low distrust* (identification trust) as this would facilitate a maximum level of cooperation among people leading to a good chance for success in a relationship. This type of trust is referred to as relational trust by Rosseau et al. (1998). However, as mentioned by Lewicki et al. (1998) and other scholars, maintaining this form of trust requires a high level of commitment and time from both the giver and the receiver.

Table 3: Lewicki et al.'s (1998) four Quadrants used to explain the levels of trust and distrust

High Trust	High Trust	High Trust	
	Low Distrust	2	4
Low Trust	Low Trust	1	3
	Low Distrust	High Distrust	
	Low Distrust	High Distrust	

From the four-by-four representation above, it could be seen that people in Quadrants 1 and 4 would always make a decision based on what they have calculated to be the best for them – Quadrant 1 prefers to be aloof from the other person(s) while Quadrant 4 would decide to be involved in the trusting relationship while being vigilant of any misdemeanour. In contrast, Quadrants 2 and 3 involve people who invest their emotions in the trusting relationship by relying upon and believing the previous interactions in return for a positive expectation (Quadrant 2). The investment of emotions in Quadrant 3 is like that of 2, with the difference being that under Quadrant 3, the trustor would always have a negative perception which could be difficult to change.

To further this model, Dietz (2004) made efforts to explain that trust should have some flexibility and should show the varying degree that may exist in a relationship. They aimed to demonstrate that trust is not static as it moves from one continuum to the other. They developed

Having reviewed some key theories on Trust, the Lewicki et al. (1998) model is the most suitable for this study due to two reasons. Firstly, it identifies that trust and distrust are different. For doctoral students, peer relationships are developed from different perspectives, and it is important to accept that a student may trust his/her colleagues for support on some perspectives but have a distrust in the same person (s) on other issues. Secondly, it provides realistic trust issues applicable to doctoral students in the UK compared to, for example, Dietz's (2004) with many extreme continua such as defence-based and institutional-based types of trust that may not be useful in the context of this study.

Furthermore, the trust model fits well into the explanations for Kram and Isabella's (1985) PRF since different levels of trust (i.e., high trust, low trust, high distrust, low distrust) influences the type of peer relationships that may exist among doctoral students. Since this study was about understanding how trust influences the categorisation of peer relationships using MIM apps, Lewicki et al.'s (1998) model of trust was adopted for exploring that aspect of the research objective.

2.5 Online Communication and the types of MIM Apps used among doctoral students

The existing literature shows there are three types of online communication – interpersonal communication, group communication and mass communication. Interpersonal communication is a situation where two people exchange information. Group communication is the second form and just as the name implies, is how a group of people interact in such a way that there is a collective consciousness on how to behave in the group. Even though there will always be variations in the level of contributions from different members of the group, they are expected to be open and sincere with one another. The third one is mass

communication involving interaction with several audiences. The first two can be found among the users of SNS (Social Network Service) and instant messaging while, the last one is only common on social media where information is sent out with the hope of reaching as many audiences as possible (Park et al., 2016). Mass Communication, such as Twitter is one of the SNS popular for this purpose (Aharony, 2012). This platform is often adopted by politicians such as the Presidents/Prime ministers and top officials of different countries like the United States of America and the United Kingdom for disseminating vital information to their residents (Fisher et al., 2019).

It should be noted that when compared with physical interaction, online communication especially interpersonal and group communication, tends to start slowly and, as the conversation deepens, individuals begin to identify their roles in the group and gradually release more information (see Gretry et al., 2017 for an explanation on role theory). Putting this description into the context of peer relationships, mass communication does not exist among students to students, but interpersonal communication could be found between two peers using one or more of the online communication platforms to interact with one another. Likewise, group communication is present among them but could only be found as a group chat where peers communicate and support one another in the absence of or in addition to a face-to-face meeting.

The point being made is that with the availability of online platforms, communications have become easier thereby making people cyber citizens. That is, people could communicate with others who are thousands of miles away from them without having to travel an inch from their current location. This has made the dissemination of opinions and perceptions a lot easier since most of these online communication tools have functions that allow sharing of documents, pictures, and even videos with just one click (Cheng et al., 2017). Although people visit the

virtual world for different reasons such as buying and selling of products, entertainment, political reasons, and/or averting loneliness through friendship (Correa et al., 2010; Lin and Huang, 2012), Jones and Fox (2009) found that the primary reason for visiting the web is for communication. Except, when necessary, communication no longer needs to be physical as information can now be shared instantly via the hundreds of online platforms available for use (Lin and Huang, 2012; Luo and Hancock, 2020; Ogara, Koh, and Prybutok, 2014).

As the name implies, instant messaging is one of the online communication methods that guarantee a quick and easy connection with the recipient(s) (So, 2016). As emphasised by So (2016), it is a form of Over-the-Top (OTT) service that could either be desktop instant messaging (PC IM) or MIM (So, 2016; p.2). Even though the advent of a smartphone made instant messaging more accessible through mobile phones, instant messaging has been in use as far back as the days of Sixdegrees.com and Napster in the early 1990s when the world wide web was first introduced (Linge and Sutton, 2015). Instant messaging had always been appealing to its users due to many reasons. Firstly, it helps its users avoid the negative aspect attached to a face-to-face conversation thereby worrying less about people's body language or the fact that they may be judged by the listeners (Pierce, 2009). Secondly, this less-confronting medium is a good platform for some personality traits such as introverts or people with social anxiety as they are able to spend more time thinking through their ideas as well as editing them before sending them to the other end (Schouten, Valkenburg, and Peter, 2007). The existing literature in this research area has shown that the adoption of instant messaging had always helped to build a non-discriminatory relationship among its users (Lundy and Drouin, 2016). This is because people can express themselves exactly how they feel in what Habuchi (2005) called, the 'zone of intimacy'. During an instant messaging just like any relationship, it is expected to find unique language usage, feedback, understanding, sense of mutuality, and contributions of/to new ideas (Clark and Brennan, 1991). In terms of personal achievements, it

has been recorded to have a positive influence on people's well-being and achievements especially among the disabled (Burgstahler, 1997). The only shortcoming of using instant messaging during the 1990s' era was that it was only accessible through the computer thereby making it not very accessible.

When compared with the desktop instant messaging apps that were only accessible through computers, today's instant messaging apps could easily be installed on smartphones, tablets, and other advanced mobile gadgets (Quay-de la Vallee, Selby, and Krishnamurthi, 2016). The smart features of these gadgets such as a touchscreen and a fast operating system are developed in a way that could accommodate multiple software applications thereby making it easier for people to constantly stay connected via these platforms. To this extent, people (including students) are now found to constantly check their mobiles to access updates; which has even become an addiction for some (Kim, 2017; Yu and Conway, 2012). Apart from surfing for general information, these gadgets are also used for important purposes. Students are now able to use it to share academic information such as articles and e-books among other things. This form of learning is what some scholars refer to as m-learning (Alshammari, Parkes, and Adlington, 2017; El-Hussein and Cronje, 2010; Liu and Hwang, 2009). Secondly, students who needed peer support can easily send out their request with the assurance that the message would be promptly received since they are now constantly online ready to spontaneously start or respond to conversations (Cheng et al., 2017; Lenhart et al., 2015; Mefolere, 2016; Mouakket, 2019).

Many researchers have expressed interest in understanding how instant messaging helps improve both social and academic lives (Quan-Haase, 2008) and they have found that it is a viable means for communicating among peers. The challenge is that most of the studies on MIM apps has been on their importance on teaching and learning and are mostly conducted

among undergraduates (see Gronseth and Hebert, 2018; So, 2016). Therefore, this study would be one of the first few to explore the MIM usage among doctoral students in relation to trust. The few ones conducted among students are reviewed below.

The likes of Timmis (2012) and Bouhnik, Deshen, and Gan (2014) were able to indicate MIM apps' usefulness during peer-to-peer support among students beyond the four walls of the classroom. Using two groups of third-year undergraduates in a UK university, Timmis (2012) found that even though the specific platform created for the study (known as Sig) was for group work, the instant messaging conversation reflected a lot of peer support among students such as comparison of progress, and emphatic feelings towards one another. According to their findings, the students were keen to ensure everyone succeeded in the assignments and there was a lot of effective support and collaborative practices. Most importantly, they were able to share their anxieties and their confidence. These findings were supported by many later studies but again, they were based on undergraduate studies such as Bouhnik et al. (2014) who mentioned that peers tend to create a new MIM or continue with the existing one even after their group work to continue their conversation.

With active users of over 3.6 billion for the year 2020, and a projected active user of 4.41 billion in 2025 (Statista Research Department, 2021a), it is pointless to refute the fact that these MIM apps have influenced how people communicate daily (Lundy and Drouin, 2016). Just as said before, these MIM apps are now in their hundreds as their developers continually try to out-perform each other by creating new ones with supposedly unique features. Some of the popular MIMs today are WhatsApp, Facebook messenger, Voxer, Viber, Skype, Instagram, Imo, IM+, Discord, Telegram, Kik, Snapchat, WeChat, Line, Signal, and Band (Hill, Chandler, and Beaton, 2020; Corpuz, 2019). Towards the end of this study, Zoom and Microsoft Teams

also joined the list of popular MIMs, especially among students thus their inclusion in this review.

Latest reports suggest that MIM apps such as WhatsApp, Facebook Messenger, and WeChat have the highest number of users with more than 2 billion, 1.3 billion, and 1.2 billion respectively while QQ/Telegram users sum up to over 1 billion in the third quarter of 2021 (Statista Research Department, 2021b). Putting this into context, three-quarters (5.5 billion) of the world's estimated population for the year 2020 (approx. 7 billion) are active users of just five of the popular MIMs (United Nations, 2020), that is by all means a huge number.

Despite the popularity of the above MIMs, not all of them are popular among the doctoral students of the UK especially those studying at UWS. Therefore, the five popular ones, in no order of preferences, are examined below:

2.5.1 Facebook Messenger

This is an IM app, whose parent company (Facebook) has recently changed its name to *Meta* (New York Times, 2021). It can be installed on smartphones for various student-to-student support (Gray, Annabell, and Kennedy, 2010). When used among students, it is mostly on a big scale such as having a group that consists of a whole cohort in what Salminen (2014) referred to as a 'course community group'. When compared with some alternatives such as Moodle, Salminen, (2014) stated that Facebook was preferred due to the convenience attached to setting it up, installed user base, and acceptance by all students. Junco (2012) added that the use of Facebook for peer supports enhances students' engagement.

This IM apps is indeed easy to use for connecting with other doctoral students on a larger scale, however, the security issues that have been tagged with the use of Facebook has reduced its level of acceptance among doctoral students of this decade such that only general conversations take place on this MIM app (Forbes, 2021; Hekmah, 2018).

2.5.2 WhatsApp

This MIM app is available on smartphones and other similar gadgets where users can connect to other users using the internet. It does not incur extra cost to maintain the mobile internet-based application, other than the use of mobile data. It is a popular app among UK students due to its instant messaging and ease of use (Al Abdullateef, Pasley, and Chesney, 2021). It can deliver real-time images, audio, and video recordings alongside delivery notifications. It also could accommodate voice and video calls for individuals or as a group (WhatsApp Features, 2021). To emphasise the key role played by WhatsApp for peer-to-peer support, Willemsse (2015) whose study was on student nurses highlighted that WhatsApp is widely present on students' phones (accessibility) and it is a platform that helps to connect students for information and support during placements, a period where students are usually away from the university. Similarly, Abiodun et al.'s (2020) concluded that students connect with other colleagues via WhatsApp to share their worries which invariably helps to prevent the anxiety that is naturally associated with placement.

This MIM app. was always considered highly secured due to its encryption ability however, they began to lose the public's trust when the company released updated Term of Conditions in January 2021, where it tried to enforce on its customers a data-sharing agreement with Facebook; its parent company (see WhatsApp Privacy Policy, 2021 for the TOC release). The company later released a new statement renouncing their initial statement, however, due to the high level of distrust the public has in the company as mentioned earlier (see Forbes, 2021), many of their customers still went ahead to seek alternative MIM apps. As a result, WhatsApp started losing its customers to other MIM apps with related functions such as Telegram and Signal (Irish Times, 2021). The Telegram boss (Pavel Durov) confirmed via their Twitter handle that under 72 hours of WhatsApp statement, its MIM app. has received about 25 million new users from across the world (Telegram messenger, 2021)

2.5.3 Telegram

Normally, Telegram would not have had a place for review among the first five preferred MIM apps for online communication among doctoral students, but with the new developments from WhatsApp as discussed above, researchers might have to start considering its usage among students especially among doctoral students. This is because people, including doctoral students, would not want to compromise anything around their privacy and confidentiality (Hekmah, 2018). Moreover, the app is known to have some unique privacy-enhanced features such as the ability to lock chats and end-to-end encryption (Telegram, 2021). To confirm its increasing popularity, Dean (2021) reported that Telegram active users increased by 150 million under 15 months between April 2020 (400 million users) and July 2021 (550 million users), a number that has continued to increase daily. Thus, it might be worth looking out for how students use this app to their advantage as they are already joining the platform in their millions.

2.5.4 Zoom

Zoom is a multi-function app that also performs the function of mobile instant messaging (Zoom, 2021). Although it performs functions similar to Skype and WhatsApp, however, it became really popular due to its easy way of connecting people without having to register or provide sensitive details such as mobile numbers as they are found with its alternative MIM apps mentioned earlier (Wang et al., 2018). Although it was created in 2011, it became a key source for connecting people during the COVID-19 pandemic as it was the platform used to either catch up with family and friends or engage in formal meetings with work or school colleagues (Serhan, 2020). It is free for any engagement not longer than 40 minutes, but when it is more than this duration, then a pricing tag is attached to its usage (Zoom, 2021). According to its operators, this app has features such as the ability to record and transcribe meetings locally

or to the cloud. It allows for HD video and audio; built-in collaboration tools that allow sharing of screens by multiple participants; changeable background, filters, polls, hand raising among many other unique and engaging features (Zoom, 2021)

2.5.5 Microsoft Teams

Microsoft Teams, which also became popular during the pandemic, is not entirely a MIM app rather, it is more of a multi-purpose online communication tool (Microsoft, 2021). It is mostly used as a desktop instant messaging app (PC IM), however, as it is now one of the main sources of connection between educational institutions and their students, it is also used as a MIM app for easy connectivity among its users (Poston, Apostel, and Richardson, 2020). Kristof (2020) argues that this platform is currently the most famous among the available online education tools. This is because as face-to-face teaching became limited, institutions had to re-strategise on how to continue teaching and learning to ensure that students' learning was not affected to a damaging extent. As confidential details might be shared and discussed, there was the need to have a communication medium that is safe and reliable, and Microsoft Teams seems to provide this function (Liu, Min, and Ji, 2011). Henderson and his nine other colleagues (Henderson et al., 2020) from Royal Free London NHS Foundation Trust in 2020 highlighted the importance of using the Microsoft Teams to connect with and train doctors during the first wave of the pandemic. According to these authors, the platform allowed the seniors to guide doctors on what and how to do things thereby building their confidence to perform their primary function which was to keep patients alive. From a teacher's perspective, Liu et al. (2011) researched how Microsoft teams have been a saviour to teaching during the COVID-19 pandemic. In an interview with 37 professors of engineering, he found that most (three-quarters) of the professors found Microsoft Teams useful due to their essential features and its configuration in a user-friendly manner. They, however, warned that, unlike other MIMs,

Teams requires a strong internet connection for it to be usable. In addition to its use for teaching, students, especially those in higher education also connect with their peers using this platform (Radha et al., 2020).

Table 4: Comparison of the five MIM apps popular with doctoral students

	Security	No of users allowed (for free)	Voice/Video function	Unique features
WhatsApp	Highly compliant	256 group chats/ 8 group calls	Present including voice note	End to end encryption, WhatsApp web on desktop.
Facebook Messenger	Compliant	250 group chat/ 8 group calls and 50 in a ‘messenger room’	Present	Payment possible; makes reservations for business owners.
Zoom	Compliant	Up to 500	Present	Background adjustment, playback voice calls, invite people by email
Microsoft Teams	Highly compliant	Up to 10,000	present	Background adjustment, call me features, link to other apps especially Microsoft office

Telegram	Highly compliant	up to 200,000	Present including voice note	Lock chats, GIF and YouTube search.
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From the table above (Table 4), it is seen that these five apps have some features in common, and as it could be seen, each of them has at least one feature that makes them a preference over the other.

2.6 Use of MIM apps among doctoral students

The various roles of mobile apps have been documented to enhance learning among students (see Gronseth and Herbert, 2018; Nitza and Roman, 2016). It has also been documented to help improve the interactions that could exist beyond the four walls of the classroom (Bouhnik et al., 2014). With a focus on one particular MIM app – GroupMe (GroupMe, 2021), the interaction on the mobile app among 29 masters and doctoral students were studied by Gronseth and Hebert (2018) with a follow-up interview with four of the 29 participants. Analysis was done using the GroupMe Posting Analysis instrument and a Google Sheets formula =COUNTA (SPLIT (C2, “”). The study found that most (71%) of the students’ conversations was around academics, while 26% of the discussion was around things like access to course content; 2% on reading app suggestions while just 1% was around family-related matters. While the participants narrated the positive impact of this platform, some of the participants mentioned that the interactions could become irritating due to having to receive too many messages (Gronseth and Hebert, 2018). Nonetheless, this study was able to offer a useful insight into the importance of MIM apps to postgraduate students and it is one of the very scarce articles to have considered doctoral students when it comes to exploring MIMs as a supporting tool among students. However, the concept of its exploration is limited as it has

only considered one out of the different MIMs available for students' use. Understandably, the GroupMe app. could have been the most popular among the participants but they would most likely have other apps which they use in interacting with one another. Also, the study has not explored how this app. is used as a trusted supporting tool. The current study helps to fill these identified gaps by not only providing the needed flexibility for students to mention the various apps used for supporting one another but also finding out how trustworthy these supporting tools are.

Apart from the study above, not much research has been conducted on the use of MIM apps among doctoral students but a few them had been conducted among students at lower levels such as undergraduates. Butgereit (2007) examined how Mxit, a MIM app, developed in South Africa helped to improve students' performance in mathematics. They found that the app. greatly enhanced after-school learning. Similarly, Gasaymeh (2017) surveyed 152 first-year students to understand the role of WhatsApp among university students. They found that the use of WhatsApp was widely accepted by the students due to its ease of use and usefulness. Similarly, Carpenter and Green (2017) conducted a survey on 240 educators who uses Voxer with their colleagues. Their findings show that these adults found the app. useful for staying connected with peers.

As this is UK-based research, it is important to review existing studies that have been conducted on the use of MIMs among UK doctoral students. Apart from not being available, even those conducted among undergraduates in the UK were limited. One of the few found was the study by Khatoon and Walmsley (2015) on dental students at the University of Birmingham. Their study showed that the students used MIM apps for short and quick messages with WhatsApp being the most preferred due to its ability to enhance group work as well as the 'seen and read tick' feature.

To fill an identified gap of lack of theoretical perspectives for analysing how MIM use contributes to learning among students, Tang and Hew (2019) investigated the utility and usability of MIMs. This was conducted among 25 postgraduate students using WeChat and they found that these students use MIM for a range of activities such as communicating with peers and boosting their social presence. Understandably, this was conducted in an Asian university and WeChat is the most famous among them, it would have still benefitted from considering more than one MIM platform to give the students the flexibility to also discuss other ones they use for interacting with one another. This gap is filled in this study. Similarly, Hill and Fitzgerald (2020) reported that WhatsApp was one of the routes used by students for seeking support and out of all the MIM apps available to them, students preferred WhatsApp due to its easy access to others.

Just as mentioned in Gronseth and Hebert's (2018) study reported that not everything is positive around the use of MIM as some learners find the pop-up notifications they receive outside school hours unpleasant.

2.7 Role of trust on the use of MIM apps for peer relationships

As of when this study was conducted, it can be arguably said that no study has explored the role of trust in relation to the use of MIM apps for peer relationships among doctoral students. Therefore, little or no literature is referenced for this section. However, a review of the background of these two concepts affirms that before the advent of these communication tools, the exchange of personal details would always have to involve physical consent and people tend to have a lot of control over what they share with others and most importantly, they could still retrieve it as soon as any suspicion (high distrust) comes in. However, this is no longer the case today because the price to pay for being part of a global village is to accept that it would only take a click for important information to be shared with other recipients (Dwyer, Hiltz,

and Passerini, 2007; Fogel and Nehmad, 2008; Mouakket, 2019). Additionally, retrieval is no longer feasible once the information is sent out since those recipients could have easily stored the information in another online location without the knowledge of the informant. Realistically, there will always be a form of distrust when sharing sensitive information via these online platforms. However, before the information is shared, the sender must be able to guarantee that there is a high level of trust and a low level of distrust before the information is passed on to the receiver (s). In simple terms, there is a need for an assurance that the keeper of the shared information would ensure that confidentiality is respected by keeping the information safe and not betraying the trust that exists between them. That is, trust is not secure until the trustor can be confident that his/her information shared via these platforms is safe, to a large extent.

Another area where the role of trust becomes central can be found among virtual teams that have to work together despite being miles apart. Since physical interaction would not be possible among these groups of people, they will all rely on trusting each other's technical and interpersonal skills to be able to achieve something tangible in their assignment. That is, having a high level of trust/low level of distrust in each other's knowledge before there could be cooperation and coordination for achieving success (Ford, Piccolo, and Ford, 2016; Kanthak and Hertel, 2016). Virtual teams among doctoral students increased during the pandemic as they were often asked by their professor to handle a short project of which, there would be the need to meet and execute the project virtually therefore, high trust/low distrust in technical skills is paramount in that instant. Even when academic assignments are not involved, interactions on the online platforms also requires a high trust/low trust around emotional support as they could at some point share personal or sensitive details (Bharathi and Goswami, 2014). Hence, the need to trust that this information is safe and will not be disseminated without their consent.

2.8 Impact of COVID-19 on students

Even though this was not originally intended to be part of the literature of this study, it has become important to include it in the research since the data collection process for this study was conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020.

As introduced in Chapter One, there is no doubt that COVID-19 has affected all areas of life including doctoral students' education arrangements. Just like other sectors, the normal ways of running different programmes and events in universities across the globe were disrupted (Byrom, 2020). Inductions, which was usually the first opportunity for the new students to meet and interact with their tutors as well as learn more about their new learning environment, was also cancelled. Many face-to-face seminars usually organised for students were postponed indefinitely and this also included various extra-curricular activities that would normally be in place to welcome students back to the university. To the extent, as the new academic session (September 2020/2021) approaches, everyone involved including university officials, parents, and students were faced with the anxiety of how to adjust to the new guidelines of having all lectures online except for when it is completely unavoidable. Most importantly, people were worried about how to ensure they did not contract the deadly virus when they eventually went to university. While it might have been easier for returning students, new students especially international students were the most affected. This is because apart from having to deal with the stress that comes with COVID-19, this group of students also have to deal with many other issues such as cultural adjustments and, settling down into the UK education system among many other things. These issues specific to international students, it is argued, make starting or returning to the university during the COVID-19 pandemic more challenging for international students than for their British colleagues who likely have most of their supporting system here in the UK and do not have to do any cultural adjustment. Many international students were left in a fix when universities had to inevitably close their campuses to reduce the spread of the

virus. This is because these students do not have any other accommodation outside the campuses and if they think of returning to their home country, they will have to worry about the immigration rules around their visa and international travel restrictions (THE, 2020; UWS, 2021). If they eventually travel back to their home country, they may not have access to the right tools such as books, the internet or even the enabling environment that may help them efficiently progress in their learning thus their studies may be interrupted (THE, 2020).

To protect the staff and the students, universities moved all events to their chosen online platform which means that all physical extra-curricular activities such as conferences, and workshops etc. were postponed indefinitely (Sahu, 2020). Since the universities (i.e., UWS) decided to move all activities online, students especially those not tech-savvy became even more reluctant to fully engage with their learning. Based on a survey of 1,500 students from a public university in the USA (United States of America), Aucejo et al. (2020) found that the academic results of students dropped during the pandemic as over 50% of the students agreed that they were studying at a reduced rate of at least an hour, and more than 35% of them are either considering withdrawal from their courses; change of course or delay in graduation. With the pandemic, students who were due to gain work experience through placement; internships or volunteering could no longer do so thereby limiting their practical experience (Waterson, 2020). From these circumstances, Buheji and Buheji (2020) concluded that the current learning situation faced by students would significantly affect graduate employability post-pandemic.

A survey of over UK 5,900 doctoral researchers and research staff conducted by SMaRteN (Student Mental Health Research Network) and Vitae a few weeks after the announcement of the lockdown revealed that: (i) over 50% of the respondents indicated that the pandemic had a negative effect on the major stages of their research work. Even though Byrom (2020) stated that their quantitative study could not ascertain causation, the findings from their study showed

that doctoral students experienced poorer mental wellbeing during the pandemic. According to Byrom's survey, four in five researchers expressed worry over their mental wellbeing as a result of their inability to make tangible plans. To support this position, Marelli et al. (2020), in their anonymised web-based survey, researched 400 participants (307 students and 43 staff members in an Italian university). They found that the students were experiencing a reduced amount of sleep compared to their sleeping hours before the pandemic. They further highlighted that the level of insomnia has increased from 24% to 40% as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic. The symptoms of depression and anxiety were also noted to be 15% and 27% respectively.

Similarly, an investigation into the impact of COVID-19 conducted in China in the early part of 2020 by Dong and Bouey (2020) indicated that a few months into the pandemic, many students were noted to be struggling with their mental health stability. They added that the factors found to increase or reduce the mental health of students include having a stable family, living with parents in urban areas. These features were found to be buffers against anxiety during the outbreak but having a close relative contracting or dying from the virus is an independent negative factor that increases anxiety (Dong and Bouey, 2020). Another study was conducted in mainland China to investigate the psychological impact of Covid-19 on students. Using an online questionnaire, Cao et al. (2020) surveyed 509 students and their study found that the level of anxiety and depression during the pandemic had increased, therefore, recommending that regular psychological interventions should be in place for students.

Hill and Fitzgerald (2020) who were also postgraduate students relayed how challenging it was for them to engage with learning as their institution moved to online teaching during the pandemic. Similar to the findings from the previously reviewed literature, they relayed that they found it difficult to combine the struggle that comes with life during lockdown with

learning thus limiting their sense of belonging that would have been derived from a face-to-face session. However, Lee et al. (2021) in a recent study posited that students' ability to cope with the effect of COVID-19 is not as bad as it is being reported by most studies. Perhaps, he argued, this is because his report shows that his participants were able to carve out strategies around technology as a coping method, in what could be termed as being digital natives (Tran et al., 2020). For clarifications, digital natives are described as those who do not find the constant updates and new versions of technology problematic, that is, they are acquainted with the use of computers and the internet for their day-to-day activities (Dingli and Seychell, 2015).

As it could be seen from the review above, students' ways of doing things were disrupted during the COVID-19 pandemic and it led to loneliness, stress, anxiety and even depression for a lot of them. Thus, as students go through these stages, their peers could form one of their best support systems since these groups of people were also going through the same journey; another reason this study is important.

2.9 Towards a conceptual framework

Research that has explored peer relationships among doctoral students have used Kram and Isabella's (1985) framework as their research model. While this has helped to illuminate how these groups of students support each other through peer relationships, the adoption of the framework does not reflect the specific role played by each of its key functions. For example, although trust was mentioned in the framework to be essential for a positive peer relationship how this is achieved is not still clear. Understandably, the framework was originally developed for work colleagues however, if it was to be accurately adapted for doctoral students as it is now being used by researchers, the central role of trust is needed. Not including a key concept of trust – distrust, makes the framework too unidirectional for making meaningful conclusions on peer relationships among doctoral students. This is due to the nature of doctoral studies

where students do not meet often, they rely on trust to develop relationships that might then lead to one form of support or another. Furthermore, they are able to trust a colleague on academic issues and have a distrust in the same colleague when it comes to emotional support vice versa. Based on these assertions, this study has included the trust model by Lewicki et al. (1998) into the PRF for a succinct explanation of the role of trust and distrust in peer relationships among doctoral students. To reiterate, the inclusion of the Lewicki et al. (1998) trust model in Kram and Isabella's (1985) PRF gives a new dimension to how the concept of trust is addressed when exploring peer relationships among doctoral students.

Also, in this technology era, relationships among peers especially doctoral students would hardly be adequately discussed without mentioning the key role played by the MIM apps. Just as said earlier, unlike the work colleagues who were the original participants of the Kram and Isabella's (1985) PRF, doctoral colleagues work in solitary and may not see each other in a long time. The implication of this is that these students rely on non-physical means for communicating and supporting one another, and one of the popular platforms used for this purpose is the MIM apps. Thus, its inclusion in the conceptual framework to understand the operational nature of these apps in peer relationships among doctoral students.

The insertion of Lewicki et al.'s (1998) model on trust and the concept of MIM apps into the PRF does not intend to undermine the existing framework rather it aims to adequately represent the factors that constitute peer relationships among doctoral students of this decade. In addition, the inclusion also helps to answer the research objectives on the use of MIM apps for peer relationships and the role played by trust during the usage, which has rarely been explored in the existing literature.

Based on the explanations given above, the original framework by Kram & Isabella (1985) is modified, for the first time, in the following ways:

- (1) Expanded the existing trust function to include low trust, high trust, low distrust, high trust (as described by Lewicki et al., 1998).
- (2) Added the use of MIMs as an important means of peer-to-peer communication among doctoral students.
- (3) Added peer-to-peer support as the reason for engaging in peer relationships.
- (4) Maintains all the key functions found in the original framework.

The proposed modified framework is given below in Figure 7, with a detailed description of each of the concepts provided in the next subheadings.

Figure 7: Conceptual framework developed from the PRF by Kram and Isabella (1985) and Lewicki et al.'s (1998) trust model.

2.9.1 Self-Disclosure

Self-disclosure is the process of making the self-known to others (Jourard and Lasakow, 1958, p.91). That is a situation where an individual makes him/herself vulnerable to others (individual, groups, organisation) by disclosing what was initially a personal experience (Joinson and Paine, 2007). The concept of self-disclosure has always been as it occurs in face-to-face circumstances but as the presence of technology becomes more prominent, scholars' attention began to shift to the exploration of disclosure through internet-mediated platforms (Walsh, Forest, and Orehek, 2020).

Disclosure in any relationship tends to help to solidify the bonds that exist therein between two or more individuals (Stanton and Low, 2012; Tskhay and Rule, 2014) and helps to increase the trust in the relationship (Proudfoot et al., 2018). The more the trust in a group, the better the self-disclosure among them and the stronger the legitimacy of its membership (McKenna et al., 2007). According to Proudfoot et al. (2018), the downside of self-disclosure is how much one can trust those at the receiving end such that what is being disclosed does not end up being used against the giver of the information. Even though similar cases are being reported daily, research has shown that people are still tempted to reveal more when behind the computers as this tends to give them some sort of satisfaction (Luo and Hancock, 2020; Zang, 2017). Someone going through depression could be lifting him/herself by relaying their experiences with others thereby leading to personal relief and possibly happiness. However, when it goes the other way, the result could be tragic (Cuijpers, Riper, and Andersson, 2015). It is not said that people should not self-disclose, however, to do this without having to regret it requires spending some time to build trust in the relationship.

To understand the motives behind why people, engage in self-disclosure on MIMs, Mouakket (2019) adopted the Use and Gratification theory and identified the need for interactions,

entertainment, information sharing, perceived escapism as the main reasons people self-discloses on these apps. They also found that gender plays a huge role in self-disclosure as women tend to be more sensitive and are more willing to share more personal information to stay connected and to make friends happy. And if used appropriately, self-disclosure on MIMs helps to reduce loneliness among its users (Kim, 2017).

Doctoral students, especially at their writing stage, tend to have a limited face to face interaction with their colleagues therefore, understanding how much is self-disclosed and what influences this decision during peer relationships was important to this study.

2.9.2 Developmental Functions

According to the framework, these functions are about sharing information to increase technical knowledge. The provision of support in developmental functions is key among doctoral students as it will not only improve their research skills but will also increase their confidence level. Doctoral students are known to have a different level of expertise in different areas of research, therefore using each other's strengths to improve their academic weaknesses is crucial for their progression.

This would also help to boost the psychosocial functions of the doctoral students such as providing emotional support, personal feedback, confirmation, and friendship (Kram and Isabella, 1985). The emotional boost is especially essential for those members that may be feeling overwhelmed and lacking the confidence to advance in their work. Hence, the reason developmental function was explored in this study.

2.9.3 Mobile Instant messaging applications (MIM apps)

It is not complete to explore the PRF in 2020/21 without considering the use of technology as a communication tool. Understandably, it was not included in the Kram and Isabella (1985)

framework as this model was proposed over three decades ago, before the advent of today's various advanced mobile messaging applications (Zhang et al., 2019). However, it is important to consider this as part of the tools of engagement in peer relationships among doctoral students as that is where most of their communication takes place, especially during the pandemic.

The different types of instant messaging apps as well as how trustworthy they are for sharing information among doctoral students was explored in this study.

2.9.4 Trust/Distrust

It is paramount to understand how trust not only determines the type of peers that exist as investigated in the extant studies but, also, how it affects students' use of MIMs for supporting each other which is absent in the existing studies. The latter is important as the use of MIM apps for interaction among today's students is paramount (Hill and Fitzgerald, 2020). As there is little or no current evidence of how trust towards the use of MIM apps influences peer relationships, the inclusion of this in the PRF helps to fill the identified research gap.

Trust is central in this study due to its direct influence on all the functions mentioned under this section. With many data breaches being committed with peoples' information, there is now the need for great care in what type of information is shared on any online platform. This is because a little bit of argument with a supposed friend could lead to leaking of personal conversations, audio, and video chats within one second. Depending on the nature of the shared documents, this single action could permanently damage the victim's life. Therefore, as maintained by Lewicki et al. (1998), the sharer (in this case doctoral students) must be able to identify where the level of trust or distrust on a particular issue of discussion is, to know what type of information is discussed or shared with those at the receiving end. For example, if student A has a high trust/low distrust in student B on developmental functions but low trust/ high distrust in discussions around family issues, the former would only seek help from student B on matters

relating to academic issues and stay away from anything relating to family issues to avoid a huge disappointment. The doctoral students within the low trust /low distrust cell may not have anything to trust or be suspicious of as they do not tend to have a relationship (Lewicki et al., 1998). Ultimately, the degree of trust and distrust doctoral students have in one another could inform the level of support given to each other and thus, the type of peer relationships that existed among them.

2.9.5 Peer relationships among doctoral students

As discussed earlier, the role of peer relationships for doctoral students is unquantifiable. It is beneficial to understand how these students support one another through peer relationships and find out how the use of mobile instant messaging apps as a trusted tool helps to enhance this relationship. Extant literature has established that this type of relationship is beneficial to doctoral students' social and academic achievement. Yet, none has arguably explored this concept with regards to how it is carried out through MIMs and the influence of trust on it. This research helps to fill that knowledge gap.

To reiterate, Kram and Isabella's (1985) framework identified three types of peers – information, collegial, special peers. However, with the review of the extant literature on peer relationships, one would suggest the presence of another type of peer. With the inclusion of Lewicki et al.'s (1998) model on trust, it is posited that there could be another type of peer characterised by low trust and high distrust. This study explores the proposition that such a type of peer exists which was not identified by Kram and Isabella.

2.10 Chapter Summary

From the discussions above, the key elements considered were the concept of peer relationships and how it helps to support doctoral students during their training. The major framework reviewed for this is Kram and Isabella's (1985) framework used to investigate peer

relationships among employees which were later adapted by Lee et al. (2017) for doctoral students. The review revealed that most of the existing literature on peer relationships among doctoral students had focused only on the traditional route doctorate – PhD. Thus, the reason it is important to also include those on non-traditional routes such as the Doctorate in Business Administration (DBA) students. Also, it was established that online communication technologies such as MIM apps are increasingly becoming a popular supporting tool among doctoral students.

The position of the literature led to the understanding that it was important to understand how doctoral students use MIMs for building their relationships as well as for supporting each other. This area was explored alongside the trust model since it is also important that the users of these apps trust the other parties with whom they are communicating before, during, and after using these online platforms.

The methodology used for data collection is examined in Chapter Three in detail while analysis of results is discussed in chapters four, five and six of these documents.

CHAPTER THREE – RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

As discussed in Chapter 2, the study of peer relationships among doctoral students is steadily becoming popular among researchers however, there are still some areas not studied. While researchers such as Byl et al. (2016), Meschitti (2019) as well as Topping (2005) have conducted related studies in this area, none of the work relates peer relationships to the use of MIMs as a trusted supported tool thus the essence of this study.

Another unique feature of this study is its ability to collate data from both PhD and DBA students as the reviewed studies have mostly focused on PhD students alone. Doing this gives a boost to the data from the study as references are drawn from both the traditional routes (PhD) and non-traditional routes (i.e., DBA) whose structure and ideology are completely different from each other. This is because the DBA students have their first-year session receiving lectures and doing coursework while the PhD students start their research from the first year, with no coursework involved.

According to Flick (2018), a good research design comprises goals, conceptual framework, research questions, philosophy, methods, validity among others, and each of these stages must be handled with honesty and rigour. Also, the strengths, weaknesses, and limitations of the adopted design should be clearly stated (Creswell and Miller, 2000). This advice was carefully followed as the purpose of this chapter is to discuss the research philosophy in comparison with other philosophies and to outline the research strategy. The research method, data collection method, and analysis and limitations of this research were also explored with detailed justifications for choosing one strategy over another. While this was ongoing, the researcher also ensured she anticipated what might go wrong and planned on how to minimise or avert it

(Barbour, 2013), since putting all of these in place helps to set the pace for good quality research (Jones, Torres, and Arminio, 2013).

3.1 Theoretical perspectives

Some social researchers believe that a researcher's philosophical position influences the approach for seeking knowledge while others believe it should be the other way round. Benbasat, Goldstein, and Mead (1987) warned that care must be taken when using this kind of approach. Instead, the main concern of a researcher should be how to ensure that the methodology adopted accurately answers the research question(s) (Ratner, 2002)

According to May and Williams (2002), real knowledge is determined by the philosophical position of a researcher, and they could be in two forms – ontology and epistemology. Ontology is about people's understanding of the nature of reality (Burrell and Morgan, 1979). As described by Ritchie et al. (2013), ontology is concerned with what theoretical perspectives an individual has towards the nature of reality. There are two major theoretical perspectives on the nature of realities – objectivism and subjectivism (Ratner, 2002). Those who believe a researcher should be separated and independent of the research are objective as they are sure that social phenomena and their meanings exist independently of the social actors (Ritchie et al., 2013) That is, there is a reality out there and it is independent of the knower. For the subjectivists, social phenomena and interactions are dependent on each other; they are not static and are not external to the knower (May and Williams, 2002). This interprets to mean that reality and the knower rely on each other to function. As rightly put by Gohertz and Mahoney (2012), whichever approach is adopted towards understanding life and its interpretations, as soon as 'one asks about the meaning of a concept, one is asking about the nature of reality which is nothing but ontology' (p. 207).

Epistemology, on the other hand, is defined by Rosseau (1992, p.109) as ‘the nature, validity, and limits of inquiry’. In sum, it is about how knowledge could be acquired. The methodology is another theoretical perspective that affects how research is conducted. It is defined as the research plan or design that informs the methods selected for a study (Ritchie et al, 2003). As a result, the methodology of a study provides the rationale for the method of data collection selected for this research.

3.2 Examples of Theoretical perspectives

Although there are different approaches to understanding epistemology, it is beyond the capacity of this project to give an in-depth description of all of them. Therefore, for consistency in this study, positivism, post-positivism and interpretivism are explored.

3.2.1 Positivism

Those with positivist epistemological beliefs postulate that the natural and social worlds are operating in a strict reality that could only be discovered through empirical enquiries (Miles and Huberman, 1994). As mentioned by Crotty (1998), the essence of positivist research is to investigate and establish facts and truth through objective means. They believe knowledge should be gained through deductive means.

Due to their objective position and large data, it is usually possible to generalise the outcome of their study to a larger population than their actual population sample (Creswell and Poth, 2018).

3.2.2 Post-positivism

Just like the positivists, the post-positivists have the assumption that researchers must be objective when reporting the outcome of the study as they are not able to influence any part of the process (Ellaway, Kehoe, and Illing, 2020). They, however, differ from the positivists in that they maintain that even though reality exists, it cannot be known in an actual sense.

3.2.3 Interpretivism

Interpretivism, on the other hand, maintains that gaining knowledge of the world relies on the interpretation or the understanding humans attach to their actions. It is a subjective way of thinking and they are of the notion that the social world could not be studied from outside, but rather from the inside. Moreover, knowledge is gathered through the interpretations given to a particular situation by the social actors (Gadamer, 2008; Silverman, 2016; Gray, 2020).

Unlike post-positivists, they gather people's accounts of a phenomenon to understand how it is interpreted by those directly involved.

With this understanding, it could be said that the general expectation is that those with the objective ontology would go along the route of positivism or the other flexible positivism routes, post-positivism (see Yin, 2017) and would follow the quantitative approach to their studies. On the contrary, those with subjective ontology tend to adopt the qualitative approach (interpretivist or constructivist). Different from these opinions are some who argued that it is also possible to be ontologically objective and epistemologically a constructivist or interpretivist (Barad, 2007). In Frazer and Lacey's (1993) words, 'even if one is a realist at the ontological level, it is still possible to be an interpretivist at the epistemological level because our knowledge of the real world is inevitably interpretive and provisional rather than straightforwardly representational' (p.182). In an actual sense, researchers are allowed to be flexible in their philosophical stand so long this would help to answer their research question.

3.3 Research's ontological and epistemological position

Due to the novelty of this project (understanding the role of trust during peer relationships via MIM platforms), and the development of a new theoretical framework relevant for adequately exploring peer relationships among doctoral students, it is ideal to have adopted the interpretivist epistemology and not the positivist perspective. The adoption of the interpretivist epistemology will make it possible to understand the reality and the interpretations given to the

new phenomenon by the group of students involved. Therefore, to carry out all of these without being involved in the data collection would be close to being impossible. As mentioned by Goffman (1959), humans are endowed with outstanding characters and beliefs which could only be understood through interactions and interpretations. Thus, for this study, the aim was achieved when the interactions among the social actors (participants) provided a rich description and an exact mirror of their social world and its meaning (Miller and Glassner, 2016). It should however be noted that due to the interpretive position of this study, the conclusions drawn were based on the researcher's interpretations which may be different from the ones provided by another researcher.

3.4 Qualitative method design

Research could either be qualitative, quantitative, or mixed methods. The mixed-method was not considered for this study due to its combination of two paradigms with contrasting philosophical backgrounds, which could sometimes distort the truthfulness of a research's philosophical position (Sandelowski, 2012).

This study adopted the qualitative design as this is the most appropriate for answering the proposed research question. Patton (2002, p.39) summarises that when a study intends to 'understand a phenomenon in context-specific settings, such as 'real-world setting [where] the researcher does not attempt to manipulate the phenomenon of interest', a qualitative study is the best research design to be adopted. The use of qualitative design for this study permits the researcher to have the needed contact with the real setting of the study. In other words, the researcher was able to have a rich understanding of how the participants made sense of peer relationships and interpret how their behaviour was influenced by this understanding (Bell et al., 2018; Miles and Huberman, 1994). Furthermore, a qualitative approach was selected because it helped to gain an understanding of people's motivations and behaviour towards a situation in their natural environment (Gray, 2020).

It is true that if the quantitative approach was adopted, this study would have been able to verify the relationship between the research's variables (peer relationship and the use of mobile apps) however, it would not have been able to provide an opportunity to understand what and how the outcome was derived, which was the goal of this study. Moreover, the aim of this research would not have been fully met if the quantitative method was used for two reasons. Firstly, there would not have been an opportunity to explore, narrate and describe the participants' experience, and the research would not have been comprehensively answered (Locke, Spirduso, and Silverman, 2013) due to the predetermined nature of quantitative research design. Secondly, due to its adoption of experiential methods and standardised measures to test hypotheses, this study cannot adopt the quantitative research method due to its focus on understanding a particular group's perception about a phenomenon thus, cannot adopt a quantitative research method which is based on the (Bogdan, Knopp, and Biklen, 2007; Denzin and Lincoln, 2011). A summarised comparison of the qualitative and quantitative approaches is given in the table below.

Table 5: Comparing the features of Qualitative study with that of Quantitative study

Qualitative study	Quantitative study
Aim at finding out different truths	Aim at finding out one truth
A researcher is subjectively involved in the processes.	A researcher is not involved to ensure objectivity.
The researcher becomes clearer as the research advances.	The researcher is clear of its aim and objectives from the start of the study.
Data collated could be in the form of objects, words or pictures.	Data is numeric.
Data is collated by observations, interviews etc.	Involves the use of questionnaires, surveys etc.

Rather, this study requires a paradigm that gives room for new ideas to be developed and integrated into the real context of the study through constant construction and reconstruction of thoughts (Robson and McCartan, 2016; Maxwell, 2013). These flexible features of qualitative study make it a suitable approach for the current study.

It is important to emphasise that each of the paradigms discussed here are important in the research world. On some occasions, the research questions of a study may need only a quantitative approach or mixed methods but on some occasions, only the qualitative will be needed to address a research problem (see Denzin and Lincoln 2008; Patton, 2002). With the above comparisons between qualitative and quantitative approaches, one would admit that this study is best explored using the qualitative approach since this study was developed for understanding how peer relationships among doctoral students are narrated in a way that permits the speakers to tell their stories in their way (Barbour, 2013).

3.5 Theories for a case study

The peer relationships that exist among doctoral students at UWS campuses was used as a case study. Galliers (1991) suggested fourteen methodologies conform to either a positivist or interpretivist paradigm (see Table 6) when considering the adoption of a case study. This study has adopted the case study under the interpretivist approach for the reasons explained above.

Table 6: Galliers’ (1991) list of methodologies and their paradigm under positivist and interpretivist

Positivist	Interpretivist
Simulation	Reviews
Forecasting	Descriptive/Interpretive
Field experiments	Futures research

Laboratory experiments	Roleplaying
Theorem Proof	Action research
Surveys	Subjective/argumentative
Case studies	Case studies \diamond

It is important to clarify the study's position as Salmon (2018) and Gibbert and Ruigrok (2010) lamented that one of the reasons a case study is not revered is because most of its researchers hardly justify the reason for selecting the design other than due to having a bounded setting. According to Salmon (2018), case study researchers should at least adopt one of the recognised approaches to a case study (i.e Yin, 2017, Stake, 1995 etc.). Or perhaps, clarify that they would be developing a new interpretation for their methodology classification. With the absence of one of these, the study may lack substance as it will not seem to have a methodological base. Table 7 shows the strengths and weaknesses identified in Salmon's (2018) review.

Table 7: Comparison of the strengths and weaknesses of published case studies as reviewed by Salmon's (2018) review.

Strengths	Weaknesses
Implementation process detailed.	A weak explanation was given on the setting.
Precise objectives stated.	Information about the collection of data is poor.
Detailed explanations are given for measures used for the outcome.	Data sources are not clearly stated.
-	Insufficient details about the theoretical stand of the Study

Since the aim of this study is to gain an in-depth understanding of the research problem, the case study method is indeed the most suitable (Patton, 2015). One of the key reasons for

adopting a case study for this project is because it allows the subjects to be observed or interviewed within their natural environment (Yin, 1984; 2017; Merriam, 2009; Stake, 1995).

This will not have been achieved through other methods such as the experiment which control different variables by isolating its participants in a prepared environment (Zainal, 2007).

Following Salmon's (2018) suggestions, the type of case study adopted for exploring the research question is explained in this section. Some of the prominent theories for a case study for educational research are proposed by Robert Yin; Robert Stake; and Sharan Merriam (Yazan, 2015). To start with Robert Yin's definition, he described a case study as an empirical enquiry that uses multiple sources of evidence to investigate a phenomenon within its real-life boundary (Yin, 1984). His approach to a case study focused on scope, process, and methodological features (Harrison et al., 2017). To a realist and a post-positivist such as Yin, the ability to ensure objectivity in methodology and generalisation of results is synonymous with achieving success and therefore, he reiterated the use of triangulation to eliminate as many errors as possible (Carter et al., 2014). He stated that a case study could be single (Type 1, one unit of analysis and Type 2, with multiple units of analysis) or multiple (Type 3, one unit of analysis and 4, with multiple units of analysis). (Yin, 2011). However, there was an obvious preference for the latter since this can help to explore real-life scenarios with different sources of evidence (Zainal, 2007). Nevertheless, he mentioned that a single case has its importance as it is the resort when there is no other case for replication. Even though Yin has not explicitly stated his philosophical stand, his approach makes it clear that he is moving towards positivism according to the analysis by Crotty's (1998).

Stake (1995) is another influential personnel on the work on a case study. He defined it as 'the study of the particularity and complexity of a single case, coming to understand its activity within important circumstances' (p. xi). From Stake's definition, one could deduce that his approach is more flexible than that of Yin as he laid more emphasis on the importance of rigour

and robustness and what is being studied. Unlike Yin’s post-positivist position, his approach to a case study is based on his relativist and constructivist/interpretivist position (Harrison et al., 2017). He advocates for discovering meanings and understanding people’s experiences in their specific context. He underlined the role of a researcher and maintains that context would influence the interpretation of the case. He recommends the use of interviews, observations, and document reviews for data collection.

As seen in Table 8, it could be said that rather than using the same terminology used by Yin to represent his identified types of case study, Stake (1995) differentiated them into intrinsic and extrinsic case study - Instrumental and Collective case study design respectively. An intrinsic case study is used to examine a case with an effort to solve the individual issue for its own sake. An Instrumental approach is used to examine a certain pattern of behaviour among a small group while a collective case study involves more than one case which may or may not be physically connected. Similar to Yin’s position on multiple case studies, Stake (1995) maintains that when conducted with enough rigour, instrumental and collective cases can lead to generalisation.

Table 8: Classification of case study designs based on Yin's and Stake's Typologies

Focus	Purpose of the study	Design Type to choose from		Author
Internal	Conducted for solely informing the individual case.	Intrinsic	N/A	Stake (1995)
External	Used for projecting beyond the case itself.	Instrumental	Collective	
		Type 1 & Type 2	Type 3 & Type 4	Yin (2014)
		Intrinsic	Embedded	
		Single case	Multiple cases	

Lastly, with a focus on the outcome of the study, Merriam (2009) defined a case study as an in-depth description and analysis of a bounded system (p. 40). Her concept was supported by another scholar, Flyvbjerg (2011), who argues that only Merriam's (2009) definitions capture all the key points of a case study among the three revered authorities of the case study strategy. She advocated for careful planning and execution. Her suggestions for analysis are descriptive, thematic, content analysis.

In recognition of their different approaches, Yin (2017) suggested that a researcher could select any philosophy that would best answer their research aims and objectives and the researcher's view of the world. A position that further gave this study the flexibility of choosing the most appropriate approach for this study – case study. This is discussed in detail below.

3.6 Design approach to the study

Following Brown's (2008) advice, this study carefully considered all three seminal approaches and how best they will help answer the research question. Since this study focused on the doctoral students in different campuses of one university and aimed at extending the outcome beyond the individual case, it is said to be a unique case study that has drawn its ideas from the three authors - Yin (2017), Stake (1995), and Merriam (2009) referenced above (see Table 8 above). This position confirms the statement by Brown (2008) that a good case study could benefit immensely by combining Yin's emphasises on rigour, the pragmatic nature of Merriam and enriched interpretation encouraged by Stake. Although the intent of the study was not to generalise findings or make big claims over small data but, being an embedded case study conducted with lots of rigour and robustness, openly addressed subjectivity and regular self-reflection, generalisation was still possible (Denzin and Lincoln 2011; Miles and Huberman, 1994; Stake, 1995).

Having reviewed the strength and weaknesses of published case studies as highlighted in Table 6 above, this study ensured that Yin's (2017) recommendations for producing a good project are followed. This was done by ensuring that the study is:

- Complete
- Significant and practical in application
- Composed in an engaging manner.
- In consideration of alternative perspectives

3.7 Research Context

This study was conducted at the University of the West of Scotland (UWS). The university was appropriate as its campuses cover different geographical areas of Scotland - West and South-west of Scotland (Paisley, Ayr, Dumfries, Lanarkshire) as well as having one campus in the capital city of the United Kingdom – London (UWS, 2020). Each of these campuses has different features that make them appealing to its students. For example, while Lanarkshire campus is powered by 100% renewable energy, the Ayr is one of UWS campuses with the greenest space as it was developed in partnership with Scotland's Rural College (SRUC) and in consultation with Historic Scotland, Scottish Natural Heritage, and the Scottish Wildlife Trust (UWS, 2020). In fact, up to today, UWS remains the biggest education provider in Dumfries. Taking an effect from its location as being the preferred destination for international people in Europe (City of London, 2018), the London campus also attract lots of international students.

Apart from the differences in their geographical location, each campus is known for a different academic area of study, which makes the university even more appealing to many international students. In total, the international student community is made up of around 3,000 in number,

from 141 countries across the world. With the total number of students at UWS being 19,000, it means that there is an average of one international student to six home students (UWS, 2020).

The university currently has over 1,200 postgraduate research students with 798 doctoral students enrolled in different disciplines across four academic schools: Business and Creative Industries; Education and Social Sciences; Computing, Engineering and Physical Sciences, and Health and Life Sciences (Doctoral College, 2021). To enrol for a doctorate, a master's degree with a good grade is required. While the London campus only enrolls DBA students (School of Business and Creative Industries), the remaining campuses enrol students for various doctoral training that cuts across the four academic schools listed above.

3.8 Rationale for selecting PhD and DBA students as research participants

Even though the Doctoral College of UWS enrolls students for a range of doctoral courses, this study selected DBA students as a representative sample for a non-traditional route to support its PhD (traditional route) samples for a few reasons. Firstly, the London campus only enrolls DBA students which means that non-inclusion of the DBA students would translate to an exclusion of samples from that unique campus. Furthermore, the researcher was a DBA student at the London campus before transferring to PhD in Business and Creative Industries (in Paisley) at the start of the second year. This transfer allowed her to experience the differences between how MIM apps are used for peer relationships among the doctoral students in these two campuses. Thereby, increasing the interest in knowing how peer relationships differ among doctoral students across the five UWS campuses. Secondly, the DBA group is the ideal representative in that the programme structure is different from that of the PhD starting from how students are recruited, enrolled up to the submission of their final thesis. These differences in structure are highlighted next.

While the prospective PhD students are required to go through interviews and approval of a research proposal during the recruitment processes, the DBA students develop their research proposal at the end of the second year as the first year is for a compulsory one-year coursework session. The DBA students' progress to their second year based on passing their first-year coursework while their PhD colleagues rely on passing their transfer event. During their period as students, the former is not assigned a research office or space while the PhD students have a shared space where they could commence their research from their first day at the university. Although they are both required to submit a final thesis at the end of their training, the requirement is a 60,000-word document for the DBA students while that of the PhD students is about 80,000 words (see Table 9 for a summary) (UWS Regulatory Framework, 2020/2021).

Table 9: Differences between the structure of PhD and DBA programmes at UWS

PhD	DBA
Acceptance depends on the approval of the research proposal	A research proposal is not needed
First-year is research	First-year is coursework
Office space appointed	No office space appointed
Transfer event needed to progress to year 2	Coursework to be passed to progress to year 2
At least 80,000 words for final submission	At least 60,000 words for final submission

Despite the differences highlighted above, one thing unifies them all - reliant on mobile instant messaging apps for peer-to-peer support. Even though the university administration is always available to provide support, these students would rather turn to their easily accessible apps to ask questions rather than go through the protocols of asking questions from the university officials. However, a comparison with the PhD from an insider perspective suggests that the peer relationships that occurs via the MIM apps become more intense for the DBA students in

the second year as these students at this stage are now expected to become more independent with their project. Also, both types of doctoral students engage in varying levels of support depending on what is being discussed. This could range from very formal discussions such as sharing journals or links to useful projects to discussing trivial issues such as their experience in a shopping mall to even discussing crucial things like visa issues, getting NI, opening bank accounts among others for international students.

For the different reasons highlighted here, it is no surprise that the doctoral students at the UWS campuses rely hugely on mobile messaging apps for support during their doctorate programmes. Therefore, they were the ideal group of students to explore for this type of study.

3.9 Recruitment and Sampling strategy

The initial sampling strategy planned for this study was purposive sampling, a nonprobability technique that permits the researcher to select the participants based on their ability to provide as much information as possible on the phenomenon being studied (Etikan, Musa, and Alkassim, 2016; Zikmund, Carr, and Griffin, 2013). However, another nonprobability sampling technique (convenience sample) which focuses on collecting data from those that are accessible, was included. This is as a result of the setback caused by the COVID-19 pandemic where the only way to access people was online. Hence, after recruiting colleagues from the DBA cohort, the remaining doctoral participants were those that responded to the announcement made on the peer reflection forum, a section of the university website managed by students for supporting one another. Due to the approach used in recruiting participants, more DBA students participated in the study than their PhD colleagues, and this was of the reasons for the overrepresentation of the DBA students.

To capture information from students with different philosophical views as well as at different stages of their studies (early-middle-late stages), it was ensured that the doctoral students included both the PhD and DBA students and from different disciplines. This was important

for comparing opinions from different categories of doctoral students at UWS. The London campus DBA students, who were the researcher's former colleagues, were informally informed through the WhatsApp group created for their cohorts and were subsequently sent a formal letter of invitation (see appendix B) via their student emails. As mentioned earlier, the peer reflection forum was used to recruit the rest of the participants. From these two platforms, students across different disciplines were recruited for the study however, they were all from four (London, Paisley, Lanarkshire, and Ayr) out of the five campuses. The researcher was unable to recruit anyone from Dumfries, the smallest of all the campuses, as there is currently no doctoral student aligned with the campus (Doctoral College, 2021).

The initial plan was to follow Namageyo-Funa et al. (2014) suggestions that a few of the students should be met face-to-face before the meeting to give clarifications on the nature of the study. However, as the study was conducted during the lockdown in the UK, this step was carried out virtually. Another challenge was how to recruit an adequate number of students during the lockdown. However, the responses from the students were positive and spontaneous which was because the students were naturally interested in the topic of the project (based on the feedback from the participants). In total, 22 participants were recruited for the study. Out of this, 20 of them participated in the individual interviews while 15 took part in the focus group. As shown in Table 10a and 10b, while some students only participated in the interview sessions, some participated in both the interview and focus group sessions. On the other hand, some only participated in the focus group alone, all based on their preferences. This mix gave the data fresher perspectives just as described by Barbour (2013) that a mix of fresh (those participating in one of the two sessions) and old ideas (those participating in both sessions) give fresher perspectives to the data collated from a focus group as their level of knowledge around the context of the study differs.

Table 10a: Characteristics of the interview and focus group PhD participants

Participant's code	Year of study	Campus	School	Gender	Sessions attended
Mr	1	Paisley	Law	Female	Interview (Int)
Sh	3	Lanarkshire	Pharmacy	Female	Int & Focus
Mo	1	Lanarkshire	Health and Life Sciences	Male	Int & Focus
Mi	1	Lanarkshire	Health and Life Sciences	Male	Int & Focus
Cl	3	Paisley	Business	Female	Int
Ta	2	Paisley	Education and Social Sciences	Female	Int & Focus
Fa	2	Ayr	Not indicated	Female	Int

Table 10b: Characteristics of the interview and focus group DBA participants

Participant's code	level of program	Campus	Campus	Gender	Session(s) attended
Ik	1	Paisley	Education and Social Sciences	Male	Int & Focus
Ab	2	Paisley	Business	Male	Focus
Cr	2	London	Business	Female	Int
Sa	2	London	Business	Female	Int

Ku	2	London	Business	Female	Int & Focus
Uc	2	London	Business	Female	Focus
Ni	3	London	Business	Female	Int & Focus
Nt	2	London	Business	Female	Int
Th	3	London	Business	Male	Int & Focus
Ch	3	London	Business	Female	Int & Focus
Li	2	London	Business	Male	Int
Ra	3	London	Business	Female	Int & Focus
Kh	1	London	Business	Female	Int
Ka	2	London	Business	Male	Int & Focus
Ad	2	London	Business	Male	Int & Focus
Di	Grad.	London	Business	Male	Int & Focus

Note: The two tables describe the characteristics of the participants with table 10a being for all PhD participants while table 10b includes the DBA participants. Five of all the participants are in year 1, eleven in year 2, six are in year 3 and one has completed his doctorate. In terms of campuses as seen above, there are nine participants from the Scottish campuses and fourteen from the London campus. Although not indicated, it is worth noting that 5 are home students while 18 are international, and there are 9 males and 14 females.

3.10 Data collection method and procedure

For a qualitative study, methods such as observational fieldwork, individual interviews, focus groups, documentary analysis, visual methods, video clips, artwork and photographs are used for collating data (Barbour, 2013; Gray, 2020; Ritchie, et al., 2013). Interview and focus groups have been chosen as the research method types for this study to be able to uncover how doctoral students at UWS engage in peer relationships using MIM apps.

3.10.1 Interview method

The interview method of data collection is popular among qualitative researchers due to its ability to capture information from verbal communication and spoken narratives. Through this

method, the informants for this study were able to express their views on the topic of interest (Carey and Asbury, 2016; Ritchie, et al., 2013). Gray (2020) posits that individual interview remains the most effective tool for understanding people's perspectives on a phenomenon. Furthermore, it allows a researcher to directly listen and record how an individual gives their reflective perspective on a particular event or topic (Barbour, 2013; Gray, 2020). Specifically, a semi-structured interview, and not an unstructured or structured interview, was adopted for this study as it gives the researcher the flexibility of making alterations as necessary throughout the session (Barbour, 2013). That is, it allows sufficient opportunity to respond to the participants based on their individual needs during the interviews, as well as allowing the researcher to have a set idea of what to discuss while retaining the ability to adapt and react appropriately.

Regarding numbers, Guest, Bunce, and Johnson (2006) suggest that although researchers should aim at 25 individual interviews, they need to make an informed decision on when to stop whenever new information is no longer being detected. Other researchers added that even though data saturation could be attained with a smaller number, for richness, it might be advisable to aim at figures between 12 and 20 (Dibley, 2011; Fusch and Ness, 2015). Hence, 25 semi-structured individual interviews were planned for this study, however, on getting to the twenty-one session, no new information was being gathered and the transcripts were starting to repeat what has been said before. This implies that data saturation has been reached and the interview sessions were stopped at that stage. This decision was supported by extant research on peer support (see Kram and Isabella, 1985 and Byl et al., 2016) whose studies were conducted with over 20 participants respectively.

Due to the circumstances (COVID-19 pandemic) around when these interview sessions were conducted, it became important to do a follow-up interview after eight months with five participants that mentioned the thought of dropping out of the programme. However, one of

the students did not respond to the email invitation until the analysis was complete thus, the analysis of the follow-up interview was based on transcripts from four participants. In terms of duration, the 20 individual interviews lasted between 40- 60 minutes; the focus group was in the range of 110 minutes while the follow-up interviews were between 15 – 33 minutes.

While the interview guide (as found in appendix D) was used as a prompt for the inquirer, the interview sessions started with general questions that would interest the participants, and gradually extends to open-ended questions with the flexibility of asking follow-up and probing questions for further clarification (Cooper and Schindler, 2006).

3.10.2 Focus groups

To find out if a focus group was suitable for research, four things must be considered: the purpose of the study, the participants' interest, and that of the researcher, in addition to what result is expected and the appropriateness of the method (Morgan and Krueger, 1993). Since the aim of this study was to provide an answer to how doctoral students engage in peer relationships using MIM apps and the role of trust in them, a focus group method is suitable for use.

Moreover, being interpretive research, this approach helps to understand how communication between the participants during the sessions could enhance in-depth and varying responses through expressions and interactions (Barbour, 2013; Coule, 2013). As described by Gibbs (1997), Morgan (1997), and Carey and Asbury (2016), a focus group is one unrivalled method that allows a researcher to understand the dynamics of thoughts going on in a group. The conversation allows for an in-depth understanding of why and how other people's opinions could shape the responses of the others in the group. Therefore, the use of this method adds breadth to the study. Also, the interactions and criticisms that developed during the group sessions are important for informing the conclusions that would be drawn for this study

(Kitzinger, 1995). This was not the first time the researcher would be conducting a focus group session (successfully conducted during master's degree with a distinction awarded), however, she still ensured to engage in intense research and watched workshops conducted by experts in the field such as Krueger (2015) and Morgan (2016) etc.

This study follows the guidelines provided by Krueger and Casey (2015), which states that informants of focus groups must have some features in common (homogeneity) as well as some varieties. As expected, they were all on their doctoral training, but they belong to different levels in their programme and different campuses to ensure some variations. Coincidentally, this position aligns with that of Kram and Isabella (1985) and Lee et al. (2017), the two main studies used for developing the conceptual framework for this study. Since recruiting the right number of people for a focus group is a major issue, the participants were over-recruited by at least 20% in case someone withdraws his/her participation at the last minute (Barbour, 2008; Bryman and Bell, 2015; Morgan, 2016).

To ensure a variety of ideas and prevent an overkill of data collection, this study ensures it stays within the expert range of six to nine participants for the two focus group sessions. (Barbour, 2008; Braun et al., 2019; Flick, 2018; Morgan, 2016; Young, 2019). Specifically, the first group session conducted in June 2020 comprised six participants while the second session which took place in July 2020 consists of nine students. As it must have been observed, the second focus group was bigger compared to the first one. This is because the students invited for over-recruited as mentioned above, all participated but since, this number was still within the expert recommendation of six to nine participants for focus groups (Bryman and Bell, 2015). Also, it was not difficult to manage the group as they were all passionate about the topic thereby making them speak from their heart throughout the session. It should be noted that the focus group participants do not know each other as the researcher specifically split the

participants into two sessions based on their different cohorts/levels or campuses. Thus, the bias or reluctance to share their exact feelings during the conversation was eliminated.

The topic guide (appendix E) that was developed for the group session served as a memory prompt for the researcher, therefore, allowing an in-depth discussion of the phenomenon. The formulation of the questions followed discursive flexibility (semi-structured questions) (Morgan, 2016). To gain an in-depth understanding of the phenomenon, the participants were allowed to control the directions of discussion with the researcher only required to guide and redirect conversations (Coule, 2013). This is because being in the focus group session means the power of the moderator is reduced when compared with a one-to-one interview (Wilkinson, 2004).

The protocols developed for both interview and focus group sessions were field-tested with professionals (i.e., supervisor and a PhD graduate friend) to ensure that the guides that would later be constructed were of the highest standard consisting of succinct and clear descriptions (Babour, 2008; Kvale, 1996; Morgan, 2016). Their feedback was used to review the interview leading to the removal or rephrasing of unnecessary questions and the addition of more probing questions. The detailed questions included in the interview and focus group guides are found in appendix D and E respectively. The interview and focus group sessions were recorded using the recorder on a laptop and that of a smartphone as a backup. To have a clearer recording of the step-by-step approach (date and time of the sessions) to how the sessions were conducted, observational notes were taken. The notes were also helpful during transcriptions as the researcher was able to go back to specific dates to double-check the participant that used a particular statement as shown in Figure 8. There was no need to worry about a suitable location for conducting the interview and focus group sessions as they were all conducted online (video) via Skype and Zoom with the recorded transcripts saved on the UWS OneDrive.

Figure 8: Observational Note taken during fieldwork

3.11 Internet-mediated research challenge

Just as mentioned in Chapter Two, the advent of technology has made a non-physical interview possible through the availability of internet-mediated platforms such as emails, Skype, Facebook messenger, WhatsApp, Zoom, Microsoft, among others. It is also now possible to conduct an online focus group through these platforms (Markham and Baym, 2008). This type of research is grouped under Internet-Mediated Research (IMR) and according to the British Psychological Society (2017), IMR is defined as:

“.... the remote acquisition of data from or about human participants using the internet and its associated technologies.... They may be reactive (where participants interact with either the materials, as in an online survey or the researcher, as in online interviews).” (BPS, 2017, p.3).

The use of internet technologies for qualitative research has been ongoing for a long time however, they were often used when participants lack mobility or are miles away from the researchers (Deakin and Wakefield, 2014). By the start of the 2020 pandemic, the reasons became different. A lot of researchers who had planned for a different face-to-face method of

data collection had to restructure their initial plan as the level of uncertainty around when normal physical interactions would be possible again was extremely low. This uncertainty affected many research works including the current study leading to exploring the best alternative to a face-to-face interview. This is no doubt an online data collection translating to ensuring that the ethics application form submitted to the Ethics Committee at UWS indicates that the researcher understands the pros and cons of online data collection and is willing to abide by all the stipulated standards of collating data through that platform.

No doubt, these new forms of data collection provide easy access, no travel cost, and are also convenient for both the researcher and the participants, but they do come with their challenges (Cheng et al., 2017; Flick, 2018; Silverman, 2016; Sugiura, Wiles, and Pope, 2017). As stated by Han et al. (2014), online participation is one of the challenging sessions to control because most participants would prefer to play a passive role. These authors informed that only one per cent of people are naturally active during online sessions, the remaining ninety-nine per cent prefers to stay largely passive. So, to ensure the participants were mentally available throughout the session, an enabling environment that could help to build rapport and trust were created by introducing the topic and some ground rules (Roulston, 2009). To solve the challenge of passivity, the researcher ensured the participants were engaged throughout the sessions by regularly asking prompting and probing questions to allow the participants to elaborate and clarify their explanations (Cohen, 2013). Secondly, all individual interviews as well as the focus group sessions adopted a video interview. The engagement that comes with the use of this format is high because the participants could see who they are having a chat with (Weller, 2016). Interactive approaches such as the use of pen and paper and the use of virtual thumbs were also adopted to keep the participants alert throughout the session but well spread across the sessions to avoid putting them under unnecessary pressure. The use of interactive approaches might not have been possible if audio interviewing was used hence, another

advantage of conducting online interviews using a video approach. In terms of ethics, the highest standard was maintained throughout the study and is discussed in detail in one of the later sections of this chapter.

Contrary to the position of Hamilton (2014) that some people might struggle with the technicalities of connecting to online sessions (his argument was based on the use of Skype), this was not the case with this study as the participants only needed to click on the link sent to them for the session through Zoom and Skype meet. That eliminated the challenges of registering personal details before using these platforms. The only challenge was with using the free version of Zoom which stops conversation as soon as it gets to 40 mins, a duration which was below all of the recorded sessions for this study.

3.12 Data analysis

The data from this project was analysed using thematic analysis. Thematic analysis is one form of the technique used for analysing qualitative data. As described by Braun and Clarke (2006, p. 79), it is a method for identifying, analysing, and reporting patterns within data. Its function is to give meaning to chunky data by organising the key point and describing the process (Boyatzis, 1998). It is a suitable method for analysing interviews and focus groups as it helps in two major ways: (i) interpreting facts and making an argument (ii) capturing the important points in such a way that helps to address the research question(s) (Braun et al., 2019). Moreover, the main criticism of thematic analysis is the fact that it gives a weak interpretation if not used within a theoretical framework, however, it was adopted for this study, over the likes of Template analysis; Content analysis and Discourse analysis, since it was used within a theoretical framework.

The analysis stage started with ensuring that the conversations were transcribed in such a way that produces an error-free transcript with none of the informants' data revealed (Green and Thorogood, 2014). Despite being time-consuming, the transcription was done by the researcher

to ensure familiarity between the inquirer and the collated data while ensuring that there was no form of data cleaning as this could change the meaning of the transcript (Lewis, 2015).

3.12.1 The phases of thematic analysis

One of the simplest ways of starting the process of thematic analysis is through coding. Codes are the most basic segment or element of the raw data or information that can be assessed in data, and it is the way of grouping and regrouping information systematically as they share similar features (Saldana, 2015). There is a range of software programmes available for helping with qualitative data, however, they are only able to assist but would never be able to analyse the findings, at least as of now.

One of the widely used approaches for analysing data is the three-stage strategy recommended by Miles, Huberman, and Saldana (2013) – data reduction, data display, and data conclusion or verification. For data reduction, the researcher engaged in selecting, simplifying, and transforming all data that are written up in field notes or transcriptions. Here, the researcher adopted the suggestions by Ryan and Bernard (2003) by looking out for participants' verbal and non-verbal expressions, use of terminologies, as well as how their discussions around a topic shift. As expected, this process was ongoing by continuously revisiting the transcript for more coding until the analysis was completed (Saldana, 2015).

The second stage (data display) started by organising and reorganising the codes collated from stage one. It was vague at first, but as the researcher carefully went through the themeing process, the meanings of the phenomenon gradually began to emerge (Kvale and Brinkmann, 2009). Here the codes were grouped and regrouped until different categories were formed. Finally, the data conclusion is of the view that during the previous stages, patterns, regularities, casual flows that helped in answering the research questions were highlighted using a colour highlighter. While these were being identified, the researcher maintained an open mind to

quickly spot any changes that may follow. She began to search for themes and review the potential themes. Next, the researcher worked out how codes relate, how they differ, and what connects them (Braun et al., 2019). They were then arranged into a theme categorised based on their relationships with the help of a reflective analytic memo. This is followed by producing a report which included writing up the outcome of the analysis while using extracts from the transcript to support the interpretation.

Throughout these stages, it was ensured that the codes and themes informed all the functions of the conceptual framework which were around peer relationships, use of MIMs and trust/distrust. Some important functions such as the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic also came up and they were grouped under one theme. As proposed by Smith and Osborn (2008) and Smith and Shinebourne (2012), three copies of the transcript were created. The first section contained an actual copy of the transcript; the second one contains key points in the interview transcript while the last column copy contained the final theme for analysis. As the analysis was ongoing, the researcher was conscious of those themes that may seem too obvious at the first glance as this could be interpreted as more of the researcher's stand than the participants' opinion.

The transcribed version of the interviews and focus group sessions was read three different times and this eventually led to generating at least fifteen themes. While reading, the researcher looked out for how the participants gave their narration, spoke about their experience, different plots, and the wider context around their explanations. This was followed by note-taking on different codes by shading them with a different highlighter and then arranging them into different themes. As the analysis process was ongoing, the highlighted texts were regrouped under one form while using the main theme that has emerged as their headings. Finally, the transcript was revisited to affirm that the identified themes are tenable and to ensure that the broader context of the participants' interpretations is well-represented.

For example, to arrive at one of the themes tagged “Impact of COVID-19 on UWS doctoral students”, the transcribed documents were read three times highlighting codes that relate to feelings around COVID-19. They were then regrouped under four categories based on the relationship between the codes. For example, three participants mentioned their challenges around online resources/learning, and they were regrouped into the “Struggle with virtual learning” category. This process of regrouping into categories was repeated for those codes and since they were all referring to how the pandemic has impacted them, they all fit under a theme titled “Impact of COVID-19 on doctoral students”. The analytical process used for identifying the themes for this research is provided in the diagram below (Figure 9). This is the process used for identifying all the themes that emerged for this research.

Figure 9: The analytical process used for identifying the themes for this research

3.13 Ethical considerations

The general abstraction regarding ethics includes guidelines such as ensuring that participants are fully informed about what is to be expected in clear terms, and their right to withdraw at any time of the study is made clear (Markham and Buchanan, 2017). Also, a researcher must avoid putting the participants at risk or making unreasonable demands on them, and their anonymity and confidentiality must be always respected (Singh, 2012; Ritchie et al., 2013).

As proposed by Ritchie, et al. (2013), there are basic expectations researchers are expected to follow, and the current study ensured it was of the highest ethical standards by following the ESRC, Economic and Social Research Council guidelines. Below are the principles set aside for this purpose:

- the research was conducted with integrity and transparency.
- Research aimed at maximising the benefit for individuals and society and minimising risk and harm.
- independence of research was maintained, and conflicts of interest were avoided.
- the rights and dignity of individuals and groups are respected.
- wherever possible, participation was voluntary and appropriately informed.
- lines of responsibility and accountability were clearly defined.

In addition to these robust guidelines, the researcher had to manage some impromptu situations due to the ever-dynamic nature of human participants (Bryman, 2016; Ryen, 2011; Silverman, 2016; Kvale, 1996). No wonder Kvale (1996) and Ritchie et al. (2013) insist that in addition to the use of general ethical codes, qualitative research would still benefit from the consideration of what works best for the participants of a particular study. Therefore, the study ensured that while the general guidelines were followed as highlighted earlier, the use of leading or confrontational statements were completely avoided and replaced with more gentle words. The

latter is important because the onset of the 2020 pandemic demanded a huge consideration of people's emotions.

As explained before, since the interview was no longer possible face to face, ethics for online research had to replace the physical approach guidelines that were earlier planned for the study. The same interview guide was used for the follow-up interview, so the same ethical guidelines were followed for the whole study. Below is a stage-by-stage description of how ethical issues were considered and resolved throughout the study.

3.14 Stages of Research and ethical issues

Planning stage: This period is possibly central to the success of the study itself as it sets the scene for other stages to follow. It involved a detailed review of the literature and the identification of the research gap in the existing literature. To help produce detailed documentation, the researcher developed a research plan (see Figure 10 below) that served as a guide throughout the study. There was an intense engagement with the literature to be sure that no previous study was replicated under the guise of having another research topic. This guided the researcher to formulate a good, feasible research aim and objectives. At that time, there was a simultaneous development of a research framework for the study. This was then followed by a plan on how to engage in fieldwork and analysis of data generated and finally, drawing of conclusion from the findings. At each stage, the researcher ensured there was a detailed discussion around the feasibility of the approaches with the supervisor to make necessary amendments as required. The plan also considered the importance of ensuring that all the cited work in the report were accurately acknowledged.

Before concluding the plan, there was deep thought on how to recruit participants and succinctly relay the intention of the research without withholding any information. Being an internet-mediated study, there were considerations on how to ensure confidentiality and

anonymity of the participants even after the study had ended. This is discussed later in this chapter.

Figure 10: Step by step research process that guided this study

Fieldwork stage: The key ethics to consider at this stage is the issue of anonymity, confidentiality and informed consent as many researchers have reported how this ethical dilemma may lead to legal battles as a result of not handling the data collection stage with care and sensitivity (IRE, 2019). These three ethical issues are discussed in detail below:

3.15 Anonymity and Confidentiality

This is about making sure that the identity of the participants is always protected. Even though the researcher took maximum care to ensure that the anonymity of the participants was maintained, those who know the participants may be able to identify them using the excerpts from this dissertation. Hence, the reason for using mnemonics to represent participants' names as well as the removal of all the information that could act as a hint for identifying the participants.

Confidentiality could be difficult to maintain in a focus group due to the number of people involved (Barbour, 2008). Therefore, ground rules are important in keeping the participants within the context of the group questions (Wilkinson, 2004). The moderator also ensured that personal details and sensitive issues were not discussed during the session. Even though these are students from the same university, there was not much worry about sensitivity since the aim of the research is on how they support each other. Some of the transcribed versions of the individual interview and focus group were reviewed by a few participants for necessary modifications before their analysis. The same process was repeated after the interpretation of the outcome, which was based on the themes that emerged from the study.

Apart from being ethical, maintaining confidentiality and anonymity is also a legal requirement in the UK under the Data Protection Act 1998 and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) policy. This policy mandates that every individual residing in the European Union must always respect the private boundaries of other individuals. It should be noted that this policy is still obtainable even after Brexit (Gov.UK, 2020) so it must always be respected.

3.16 Informed Consent

This is another important aspect of ethics in practice. To actualise this, the researcher ensured that the participants understand what the study entails and provide them with full information about what it means for them to take part in the project (Nijhawan et al., 2013). As a result, when composing a letter of invitation to participants, the researcher was clear with answering the following questions: what the aim of the research is, who is participating, what information is needed, for how long, who would help to review the study on completion, and how the data would be handled. In addition to this, the study also ensured that the following guidelines highlighted by the ESRC (2020), BPS (2017) and IRE 3.0 (2020) were followed:

- Written documents were obtained from all participants via emails or MIM platforms such as WhatsApp and Skype. They also consented during the online briefing that took

place before each of the online meetings be it interviews or focus groups to ensure that these consents are traceable (Bechmann and Kim, 2020).

- Participants were assured of their confidentiality and anonymity by asking them not to mention their names during the online sessions, and for those who did, it was not included in the transcribed version. For security purposes, the information was saved on a private passworded laptop as well as on the UWS OneDrive and discarded on the completion of the study.
- The researcher's welfare, as well as that of the informants, were ensured especially during the focus group session by requesting that the participants stay within what is discussed and not mention sensitive issues such as ethnicity, sexual identity, political discussions or share disturbing contents such as violent graphics whatsoever (Association of Internet Researchers IRE, 2020).
- Participants were reminded regularly that their participation was voluntary, and they could withdraw whenever they feel uncomfortable.
- During the debriefing session, it was ensured that all questions raised by the informants were answered to the best of my ability and with all honesty.

Also, throughout the study, the researcher stayed sensitive to the non-verbal expression of the participants and rephrased the questions when necessary. Above all, the primary ethical norm which says a researcher must have *respect for persons, beneficence and justice* were strictly followed before, during and after the study (Markham and Buchanan, 2017). The UWS principles of good practice (Honesty, Rigour, Transparency, Respect, and care) were also obeyed throughout the project. Below in Figure 11 is an image of the completed form showing that the researcher ensured that participants gave their full consent to participate in the study, a copy of the uncompleted one is found in Appendix C.

CONSENT FORM

TITLE OF STUDY: Peer relationship and the use of mobile instant messaging applications as trusted supporting tools: The case of doctoral students at UWS Campuses.

(Please tick the appropriate box)

Consent statement	Response	
I have read the information provided and I understand them	YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
I received enough information on this study	YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
I understand that I can withdraw from this study at any time	YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NO <input type="checkbox"/>
And I do not need to give a reason for my withdrawal	YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NO <input type="checkbox"/>
I understand none of my details will be used at any point in time	YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NO <input type="checkbox"/>
Only my anonymised response will be used for the study	YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NO <input type="checkbox"/>
I voluntarily agree to take part in this study	YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NO <input type="checkbox"/>

Signing the consent form

Signature of participant

Printed Name:

Date: 2/07/20

Please tick one: DBA PhD School business

YEAR: 1 2 3 Other

Investigator details

Name: Ayodeji Adebayo Signature:

Contact details: 800358889@studentmail.uws.ac.uk, 07961903396

Supervisor's details

Name: Carolyn Gray Email: carolynn.gray@uws.ac.uk

Figure 11: Participant's completed form showing her consent to voluntarily participate in the study

Analysis and Writing Stage: During the analysis and writing stage, the researcher ensured accountability, transparency, and trustworthiness with how the data was handled and interpreted (Gallagher et al., 2016; IRE, 2020). She constantly upheld her integrity standards by avoiding fabrication (an invention of fake data), falsification (existing data illegitimately altered) or plagiarism (the use of another person's work without their acknowledgement) (Singh, 2012).

Also, as an interpretive qualitative study, the researcher's presumptions are unavoidable. However, with constant reflection, she was able to recognise her values and involvement

throughout the research. The approach used by the researcher to ensure reflexivity, credibility, and quality of the study is discussed next.

3.17 Reflection

The reason for taking up research could be one or more of the following: personal goal, career development, research goals, accomplishing a status, understanding a phenomenon, and/or intellectual goal (Maxwell, 2013). Each of these goals has the potential to influence the outcome of a qualitative study especially if it was interpretive research such as this study. Therefore, a qualitative researcher must constantly engage in reflexivity. According to Hess-Biber and Piatelli (2012), reflexivity is a process of engaging in a review of one's actions and values that are being preconceived as research is being conducted. Conscious acknowledgement of one's assumptions and how they influence research outcomes is essential in a qualitative study.

The methods adopted for this study's data collection involved interactions between the participants and the researcher. It is, therefore, important to regularly identify and justify every alternative relegated for the others during interpretations. To do this, the researcher ensured she engaged in continuous reflexivity to stay conscious of her actions and ensure the influence from her interpretations on the research outcomes is identified (Flurey 2015). The researcher acknowledged that her previous assumptions that peer relationships are beneficial to doctoral students might influence the responses expected from the participants. However, with adequate reflection, she was able to have an open mind to whatever responses were given and avoid insisting or leading questions to justify her prior position. There was also a rigour of interpretation by ensuring that during the research process, the following questions were addressed: Why do I have this perception; How did I know this; So, what; and what led to that conclusion? (Markham and Buchanan, 2017). As suggested by this scholar, research journals

were also kept throughout the study as well as keeping dates on each entry (see Figure 12 for evidence of this).

Being an insider provided a settling and calm environment for the participants, enabling them to better communicate with the researcher (Mercer, 2007). However, researching as an insider comes with the possibility of taking key discussions for granted because of the proximity with the participants (Kanuha, 2000). Also, there could be a lack of objectivity as the participants were fellow doctoral students. To curb this, the researcher constantly reminded herself of her inquirer position and not as a friend or colleague. She regularly self-reflected on all her steps and feelings throughout the study to avoid any oversight (Coule, 2013). She also ensured to take a balanced view throughout the enquiries (Mercer, 2007). For example, when the students were describing their feelings of being isolated, it might feel as though the researcher should comment however, the constant reflexivity helped her remember that the informants' stories are separate from hers and she just needed to listen to theirs at that particular time.

During analysis and interpretations, the regular reflection also helped the researcher not to take for granted the privileged position of interpreting the life events of another person therefore, tried to be honest throughout those stages (Brown and Gilligan, 2013).

Figure 12: Reflective notes compiled during the fieldwork

3.18 Triangulation

To Bryman (2004), triangulation is a way of enhancing the understanding of a subject. Golafshani (2003) and Carter et al. (2014) added that triangulation could also be used to improve the validity and reliability of a study. The two positions are right as they both suggest that it is a way of controlling any bias thereby leading to the establishment of a valid proposition (Mathison, 1988). This could mean using more than one method or data or even mixing quantitative and qualitative (Salkind, 2010). Just as stated earlier, this study did not consider mixing qualitative and quantitative approaches due to the problems that may ensue in the cause of justifying the different philosophical positions (Barbour, 1998). Rather, triangulation for this study was affirmed with the use of two methods of qualitative paradigm (interview and focus group) for data collection.

3.19 Issue of Rigour

Similar to the concept of trust reviewed in the literature review, trust is also an important aspect of conducting qualitative research (Denzin and Lincoln, 2000; Christians, 2000; Connelly, 2016) because the validity and reliability of a study is “how much can we trust your study”. According to Connelly (2016), the audience must be able to have trust in how a study is being conducted, collated, analysed, and interpreted. Seale (1999) added that a reliable study is a study with a high level of trust since the trustworthiness of research is synonymous with concepts of reliability and validity. However, these two terms are rarely used in describing a qualitative study because its researchers (especially the naturalists) believe that the terms are rooted in a positivist approach. However, social researchers still admit that there is a need for some checks on the quality of a project, thus the rigour for this study is explained under the preferred criteria proposed by Lincoln and Guba (1985; 1994): credibility, confirmability, dependability, transferability, and authenticity.

In practice, the readers want to be sure that the study was conducted with as many standards as possible (Connelly, 2016). Unlike the quantitative approach where credibility involved the construction of the standard instrument, this study ensured adequate documentation of all the stages involved as well as declared how they were able to manage all forms of bias throughout the research (Myers, 2019). Specifically, the researcher was able to answer YES to the following questions: did the researcher ensure the participants were adequately engaged in such a way that reflects their reality? Was the outcome checked with the appropriate authorities? Was the researcher able to reflect on her bias and put in necessary measures to minimise or prevent this? Were the collated data questioned and revisited a couple of times to ensure correct reporting? All these questions were succinctly addressed in this chapter and throughout the other chapters of this report. In addition to succinctly documenting all the processes of data collation, analysis, and interpretation involved in this study, the researcher double-checked the outcome with the study participants and the supervisors. Going through these steps confirm the credibility of this study (Connelly, 2016; Miles et al., 2013).

The basic meaning of dependability is the ability to rely on the quality of the research just like the reliability in a quantitative study (Denzin and Lincoln, 2011). Even though it is understandable that qualitative study is contextual, it is part of the expectations that researchers keep notes of all the steps that led to the collation of data to ensure the dependability of the study (Connelly, 2016). To ensure this, the interview outline (appendix D) is made explicit such that it could be replicated by another researcher although it is worth mentioning that the exact wordings or gestures may be different.

Qualitative research is often criticised for its low transferability strength. This is because, unlike the quantitative research whose results could be transferred (generalised), qualitative research lacks this strength because of its small sample size especially in a single/intrinsic case study (Stake, 2005; Yin, 2017). However, this study has ensured there is a provision of a

detailed discussion on why specific questions were asked, where the collation took place, and how the collected data was analysed and interpreted. This way, the study was able to affirm transparency and honesty, an important element in trusting the results from the study (Cope, 2014; Ritchie et al., 2013). Thereby, providing some chances for transferability.

According to Connelly (2016), authenticity helps to enhance the audience's understanding of the project, and it is unique to qualitative studies. Schouten et al. (2007) suggested that it can be achieved by the appropriate sampling of participants and ensuring that this is again, well-documented. This was achieved by appropriately sampling the participants and ensuring that the processes involved were again, well-documented.

3.20 Limitations of the study

As Gray (2020) put it, no research is perfect, and researchers need to be sincere about the limitations and weaknesses of their studies. Just like any other qualitative study, generalisation of the results was not possible to avoid being over-ambitious as the number of informants would have to be tangible enough to be able to represent all the doctoral students in the UK universities. This is in addition to the fact that its data were collected purposively/conveniently, and not randomly (Miles et al., 1994). Moreover, qualitative studies are most likely suggestive rather than conclusive (Dey, 2003) therefore, the study focused more on producing an outcome that reflects an in-depth understanding of the concept of peer relationships among doctoral students, and not necessarily for generalising its outcome. Perhaps, the generalisation would have even been more realistic if a larger sample size was used. However, this was not possible due to some students' reclusive attitude at the time of data collection for this study (understandably triggered by the COVID-19 pandemic). Although Patton (2002) and Gray (2020) stated that multiple cases could be generalised due to its ability for replication of ideas but because this is a single case study, generalisation is again impossible.

Although to increase its quality, more than one campus was used (embedded) but only four out of the five campuses of the university were represented. This is because the students that showed interest were only from those four campuses as there are currently no doctorate students enrolled at Dumfries. It is important to note that being a pandemic period, physical recruitment was not possible so the research could only rely on online recruitment thus, the reason for accepting only those that showed interest via this medium. In this study, there were more DBA students than the PhD students as again these were the people that showed interest during the two months of online recruitment for this study. This, perhaps, was because the DBA students were once colleagues of the researcher. Also, they are more of a community than PhD students because of the nature of the programmes so it was a lot easier to recruit from the DBA community compared to the PhDs. Understandably, this meant that DBA students would be more pronounced than their PhD colleagues. However, the analysis was fair in terms of interpretations by always balancing the opinion from the two sides.

Being interpretive research means that the conclusions from this study rely on the researcher's perceptions before conducting the research. These pre-existing thoughts were managed through constant reflection as discussed earlier. It would not be far-fetched to say there was an inbuilt bias since all the participants were colleagues from the same institution. However, the researcher ensured that the highest level of professionalism was observed throughout the interview and focus group sessions by focusing on being an inquirer throughout the sessions.

3.21 Chapter summary

This chapter gave a detailed discussion of the philosophical position of the study as well as the strategy adopted for conducting the study. It was established that the justification for adopting a case study design is crucial as some researchers (i.e., Gibbert and Ruigrok, 2010; Salmon, 2018) have lamented how past studies have always chosen case studies without theories to back it up. In addition, a study that is regarded as being credible, authentic, and transferrable must

give succinct explanations for each of the processes taken throughout the study including recruitment, data collection method, the process of analysis of data as well as the ethical considerations put in place for the research.

The results and discussion are discussed in detail in the next three chapters based on the main themes that emerged from the interviews and focus group which are strongly influential on the research objective.

CHAPTER 4 – FINDINGS: CONCEPT OF PEER RELATIONSHIP

This chapter describes the concept of peer relationships based on the perception of UWS doctoral students. The analyses are with reference to the PRF by Kram and Isabella (1985). In addition, the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic and the role of gender on peer relationships are described. A qualitative approach (semi-structured interview and focus group) was adopted for the data collection of this study since this aspect of the research aimed at elucidating how doctoral students support each other through peer relationships.

As described in Chapter Three, the data are presented as a series of discussions from the semi-structured interviews exploring themes with rich descriptions before being given a presentation while referencing relevant pieces of literature. Although there are varying subordinate themes and supplementary elements, the five main themes identified in this chapter are below:

Figure 13: Summary of the main themes for Chapter 4

The study adopted the use of mnemonics to ensure that the identities of the participants were protected. Since transcription is ‘only as good as the methods used to create it’ (Powers, 2005; p.9), some punctuation formats were adopted for this research. A symbol [...] was used to represent ineligible words or part of the transcript not relevant to the study and [.] for end of utterances (Braun and Clarke, 2013).

This chapter is one of the three parts of the result and analysis section, and the other parts are discussed in Chapter Five and Chapter Six, and although they help to answer the research objective (1), they also inform the recommendations later provided in Chapter Seven.

4.1 Theme 1: Developmental functions

The purpose of creating a relationship with colleagues is to be able to support each other (Kram and Isabella, 1985) but again this will depend on the doctoral students' attitude towards his/her journey. While some think that their relationship with their peers was *empowering* as they were able to either gain emotional support, improve their academic capability, or receive proper guidance on the journey, some believe peers' role in their journey has been *trivial*, that is, their colleagues have not been able to influence their capability in any way. Meanwhile, some others find peer relationships *overwhelming* and a big burden for them and wish they were never involved in it. These three attitudes to developmental functions are explored in detail below.

4.1.1 Empowering

This is where the highest developmental function takes place. Here, the students are willing to improve the capability and knowledge of one another in all ramifications. Empowerment among doctoral students could be one of the following: seeking *peer support* such as emotional support, information about their course, transfer events, ethics application, feedback on academic or non-academic issues; engaging in *peer learning* where students learn from each other's academic knowledge and experience or through *peer mentoring* where colleagues

support each other professionally. Each of the three concepts is analysed in the sub-section below.

4.1.1.1 Peer support

The participants here such as Nt, Sh and Ku emphasised the importance of having general or emotional support from their colleagues. They felt this support has helped to make their doctoral journey smoother and more peaceful:

Sometimes you just want someone to listen and give feedback right away even if it makes sense or not. That's what we need in order to escalate to a better level. – Nt

....my colleague who started with me, we were supporting each other. Like, even if he doesn't know grounded theory still, I know he will sit and listen to me... It's that kind of bond, I don't know if everyone can get it, but that was very special, I would say - Sh

So, it is like a group feeling which is really something that we cherish.... [skipped], the ultimate goal seems more achievable if you are part of a bigger group than walking alone. – Ku

A doctoral student who has the support of his/her colleagues is assured that whenever he got stuck, there is someone to quickly check things with. Just as described by participants Nt and Sh, they always knew there was someone there to listen to their problem and assure them that things would be okay because this peer understands how they feel at that moment and genuinely wants to be of help. That feeling of being valued is what participant Ku says is crucial when peer support is present. This term might sound trivial as it is an informal type of peer relationship, however its presence among doctoral students is a good source of motivation. In Lee et al.'s article (2017), he narrated that students often find solace in fellow students when

things become tough for them especially with their supervision. That is what peer support is about, and since it is known that doctoral students go through one challenge or the other, the presence of peer support makes the peers feel valued and cherished. Thus, having other reasons for not quitting their training especially when the going gets tough. One could possibly refer to this type of peer relationship as the confidence booster.

4.1.1.2 Peer learning

Participant Th, who was awaiting his viva date, expressed that the learning sessions he had with his peers during his doctoral journey helped him complete his study on time and with ease. According to him, what they did was to arrange for a particular date and venue for their meeting. During these peer-initiated sessions, they would independently go through different journals and books relating to their research work, discuss whatever area each of them was finding difficult, and how to go about their writing before the next meeting. Even though each peer was working on different topics, their presence as a group served as a motivation to want to study as well as write more:

.... after you finish, you doubt if what you have done is correct or not, so I send it to them (peers) for proofreading because they are better than me in English.... This is, how when I got this help, I finished my work. Another student who didn't get this help or who didn't contribute in that discussion, they're still struggling to choose a topic - Th

Cl's statement also helped to confirm this:

..... that kind of peer learning where people go, oh I'm doing qualitative methods. So, am I. Have you had a look at this where they may be using focus groups? Have you seen this new book that's out, that kind of peer learning that's going on at the same time? – Cl

Just as described above, the peer learning that took place between participant Th and his colleagues helped him finish his course on time and with satisfaction. This is because the students organised themselves based on a mutual understanding of improving each other's research capabilities. They did this by reviewing each other's work to give honest feedback on how to improve upon it. Apart from giving more confidence to the reviewer, it helps everyone involved to learn different approaches to solving research problems. It also helps to identify errors or non-feasible research questions at an early stage before it gets too late. Furthermore, it helps peers feel confident about the state of their work with no pressure attached since the feedback is basically peer-to-peer and not from a higher authority such as the supervisors.

Many of the extant literature has confirmed the important role played by peer learning especially linking it to an improved academic achievement just as described by participant Th. The finding here is closely related to the conclusions by Meschitti (2019) even though the peer learning in her study was organised by the supervisor or tutor while the one in this study was organised by students with similar interests. Whichever approach or description is given, what is the most important is the improved academic achievement attached to this form of peer relationships (Boud et al., 2014).

Even though Devenish et al. (2009) described it as a study group, there was an emphasis from their study just as found here; that the process is less threatening when compared with the official sources.

4.1.1.3 Peer mentoring

This is another aspect that unified all the participants of this study be it the PhD and DBA participants as they all expressed the importance of having someone who could serve as a role model for them during their doctoral journey:

I've tried to contact my colleagues. But to be honest, I didn't get the right expectations from them. But I still remember when I asked Kh (higher cohort), it was so helpful, you feel that they have some knowledge to share with you -Ad

Since then, I'm in regular contact with that person..... In fact, recently, I discussed my thesis with him, and he gave me invaluable advice because, you know, he's been through that. – Ra

.... that PGR student started his journey two months earlier than me..... and more experienced, say for, when I just arrived in Scotland, support for opening bank account, support for searching, renting a house. Even support for the library resources and how to rents, and to submit book, even where is the gymnasium, student lab – Mo

From the excerpts above, it would be seen that things were a lot easier for participants Mo, likewise participants Ab and Ra. With their access to a peer mentor, they could easily run their academic issues past them and hope to get reliable help. In terms of confirming a peer mentor's role on non-academic issues, participant Mo, an international student, succinctly described how a senior helped him settle into Scotland. According to him, settling would have been very tough for him and his family due to the differences in culture, a situation Laufer and Gorup (2018) also confirmed to be a big challenge for international students.

The participants' descriptions also reflected the features expected of a peer mentor. Even though the mentor does not have to be years ahead of the mentee, they expect him/her to be at least above them in terms of experience and, perhaps, knowledge to be able to give top-notch guidance to the mentee. This may explain why most of the participants insisted that they prefer

to seek only general help from their colleagues and seek academic help from a senior peer or supervisor/ University:

So, I'm not gonna get a mentor from my class because we are all like at the same level of knowledge, we have more academic skills rather than experience so for me, I need a mentor who has more experience in the field

- Ch

*..... I think we do lookout for people who are further down in the process to know what is the next steps that they took and how we are going to kind of learn from their processes, their mistakes, and how we can save ourselves a little less by just walking the path they have already cleared. - **Ku***

*I believe that you know, when you're in your second or third year, you are in a perfect position to help out new PGRs because you have been through all that – **Ra***

It could be seen from the extracts above that the participants do not necessarily feel that their peers are not able to mentor them but just as pointed out by participants Ch and Ku, they needed someone who can guide them on how to prevent avoidable mistakes, and they believe the best to fit that description would be a senior peer. For example, participant Ra expressed that she would prefer someone in year two or three to mentor new entrants as these people would have completed key doctoral activities such as annual review, transfer events, research proposal approval (for DBA cohort), and possibly have their ethics application approved as well. With these in place, these seniors would have adequate experience on how to guide the students in their early phase. Although the literature has not specified the level of education ideal for peer mentoring to take place there is an understanding that whoever would take up this role should

have more experience than the mentees (Collins et al., 2016; Lee et al., 2017) just as described by the participants for this study.

Another key point to note is that even though peer mentoring may take place informally; achieving its full potential would require a formal approach. Drawing reference from the PRF, the participants seem to hope that the university could organise a mentoring scheme where interested senior doctoral students help to guide one or two new students for a specific period and in return, the mentor receives an award for the scheme completion. This would be similar to Collins et al.'s (2016) study, where the researched university organises a scheme in which the senior students served as a mentor to doctoral students in their early phase. This type of scheme is still in its infancy at UWS when this study was conducted.

The descriptions by the participants of this study clarify the key concepts in the Kram (1983) definition of peer mentoring. Firstly, it states that peer mentoring occurs between two individuals of similar experience – note the use of similar and not the same hence, the reason the participants insisted on having a mentor who is not only a doctoral student but in a higher cohort. The definition went on to state that the process helps to improve psychosocial functions and career-related functions further confirmed by Terrion and Leonard (2007) and Lee et al. (2017) with a conclusion that a peer mentor should be able to give emotional support as well as guide the mentee through on-time completion of the study. The position of Kram (1983) and Lee et al. (2017) is evident in the extract above where the participants expressed that this type of peer relationship helps in their overall next steps.

From the descriptions given by participants Ch, Ku, and Ra, it could be said that the type of peer mentoring that currently takes place at UWS is informal where they randomly meet a 'senior' and create a peer mentoring type of relationship from there. However, to actualise the full potential of peer mentoring as described in the PRF by Kram and Isabella (1985), this study

maintains that peer mentoring, managed by the university or department is preferred. This is because each doctoral student is engrossed in his/her project that they might not tend to meet or interact frequently but being managed by the university or Doctoral College would allow the mentor to be committed to helping his/her mentee due to the recognition attached. This position also helps to emphasise the convenience attached to the use of MIMs for this type of peer relationship where the mentors do not have to travel to meet their mentees and vice versa. Likewise, the other types – peer support and peer learning could also take place via the MIMs even when COVID-19 restrictions are over. This is analysed in detail in Chapter Five of this study.

In terms of the interchangeable use of these terms flagged in the literature review, the extracts above show that doctoral students perceive the terms to be different. Firstly, they believe peer support is more of basic emotional support (informal; non-academic) – i.e., deadlines for assessment; viva information; timetables; guidance for ethics application while peer learning involves academic activities such as peers meeting up to learn about research areas such as methodology or analysis tools as well as reviewing each other's work. It could be initiated by peers as seen in this study (informal) or by the university/supervisor (formal) just as highlighted by Meschitti (2019). On the other hand, peer mentoring is a formal process where the mentor is expected to have some seniority or experience with adequate technical skills than the mentee. That means this mentor should also be able to guide the 'junior' doctoral students on the right path to achieving success (formal, academic, or non-academic) - see Figure 1 in Chapter Two.

When asked to reflect on what might have happened if at least one of these peer-to-peer supports was not there, the participants used words like 'panic', 'depressed' and 'almost quitting' as seen in the transcript below:

If it wasn't for the support? I don't think I would still be here. I think I would either be on interruption of study.....the support has really kept me going – Cl

I wouldn't have survived this thing (PhD journey). I would be the loneliest person ever because I don't ever initiate any conversation or anything. I would have been so lonely, so depressed - Ta

But without my friends' support, I think I will be very depressed for a long time and I might be drowned in the middle of depression lake for a long, long time -Nt

... definitely, I felt low about my studies many times and very low to about almost quitting my PhD but...two of my very close friends at UWS, they motivate me to carry on doing my work properly. And I also motivate them – Kh

These strong expressions indicate what scholars such as (Berry, 2017; Boud and Lee, 2005; Hadjioannou et al., 2007; Lee et al., 2017; Lovitts, 2002; McPherson et al., 2018) emphasised regarding the role of peer relationships. Just as these authors have posited in their various studies, the participants clarified that the support they received from their peers have not only helped them stay on the course but has also helped them reduce depression as well as curb loneliness which, overall, improves their well-being. An excerpt from participant Ta confirms the fulfilment that comes with having a relationship with peers:

And whoever you ask, they're so friendly, so helpful, like they knew me for ages, which is not the case. They probably have just had only one email from me, and they just helped me with their heart. Yes, I asked for help from my colleague all the time, they helped - Ta

The downside of this is that being informal, the participants would have to ask for help in order to benefit from the relationship. This is expected to be a normal routine however it implies that some with introverted personalities or those not very comfortable with seeking help from others might not benefit from this type of peer relationship. This is more reason peer mentoring might achieve more success if managed by the university, supervisor, or cohort tutor (for the DBA students in their first year).

As seen from the analysis under this section where peer relationships are perceived as an empowering journey (through support, learning, or mentoring), the analysis shows that even though students may have one or more personal challenges during their doctorate, to the point of even considering dropping out as stated by Williams (2019), interactions with peers will help to boost their confidence to complete the course or, at most, seek extension rather than giving up entirely on the journey. This is the position of most of the researchers (i.e., Boud et al., 2014; Byl et al., 2016; Flores and Nerad, 2012; Lee et al., 2017; Lindsay, 2015; Meschitti, 2019) that have worked on these three concepts of peer relationships (peer support, peer learning, or peer mentoring).

Also, since there is a clear distinction between these types of peer relationships, scholars in the field need to ensure they are used distinctively (Chao, 2009).

4.1.2 Trivial

Before this study, arguably no other study had explored peer relationships among doctoral students from this perspective. Most of the attention has been on the empowering nature of peer relationships. Yet, some doctoral students feel that their relationship with their peers is trivial (Chui et al., 2014).

The participants, under this subsection, believe that there is a limitation to what could be learned from their colleagues: grouped as 'Trivial'. They do not believe their peers could

enhance their developmental functions in any way. For someone like participant Mr, she would not bother her colleagues too much on academic issues as she feels they would only be able to give her basic information:

Well, there is a limitation on what you can learn from your peers because for somebody to be in your peer group, it means..... you're both probably discovering things together” - Mr

Participant Cr supported the assertion above by adding that she stopped trying to seek information from her peers due to the response she got from a few of them:

.... when I spoke to my colleague about how to approach a literature review, the feedback that he gave me was something I already knew. It had no impact on my studies, on my doctoral work... [skipped].... So, I think it's because they were maybe the same level as me – Cr

Both participants Mr (PhD) and Cr (DBA) may be on different doctoral routes but their opinion about their peers are similar in that they are not willing to seek more than basic peer support from colleagues, nothing in-depth such as emotional support or even academic help. While participant Mr does not believe peers could have the level of knowledge to significantly improve her work, participant Cr explained that she does not bother to ask anymore because it was more like a waste of time for her. She added that apart from her supervisor, she would rather get her help from books, journals, and other academic platforms. Based on their perceptions, these groups of students would only get involved in peer relationships if it is managed by the university or their supervisor/tutor suggest it for them.

4.1.3 Overwhelming

One aspect that is often neglected is the negative impact of peer relationships on doctoral students as it is mostly assumed that student to student relationships would always give a

positive result (Chui et al., 2014; Lindsay, 2015). Just as pointed out by Jairam and Kahl (2012), students may feel competitive or pressurised when engaged in peer relationships. Here, the relationship is no longer mutual as the receiver of the support might be benefitting in terms of their developmental functions while the giver is often negatively affected. This kind of negative experience was shared by Participant Ab, a year 3 doctoral student:

*“You know, they kept calling us and saying, Oh, so what should we do?
Like everybody's doing this programme, we all have challenges. So, we
have somebody overbearing you with certain issues, when you need
support yourself, then it becomes, you know, unbearable” - Ab*

Someone like participant Ab constantly felt pressurised due to his colleagues' demands. According to him, his peers had refused to understand that he is also in a similar situation as them and that he would also be needing time and guidance around his project. He added that this pestering behaviour was the reason he avoided joining any MIM platforms that required sharing of mobile numbers with peers because access to his mobile number meant they could call him at odd times without his permission. Drawing reference from Kram and Isabella's (1985) framework, the developmental function here is one-sided as the giver feels negative about the whole peer relationships experience. Albeit not tagged as overwhelming, Gronseth and Hebert (2018) who examined peer to peer relationships via the MIM platforms concluded that some students do find the constant notifications on their phones annoying. Participant Ab added that even though he would be happy to join short conversations with his colleagues, he would not like to engage with them through MIM apps such as WhatsApp as this would be too personal. Rather, he would prefer MIM apps such as Zoom and Microsoft Teams as this does not require sharing personal details or getting to that intimate level with one another.

The three positions analysed under the developmental functions show that not all doctoral students feel positive about peer relationships despite the aim of encouraging peer relationships among doctoral students being to enhance the positive aspect of it. Therefore, the trivial and overwhelming aspect of it should not be ignored. This is because an establishment of what they are would adequately inform the recommendations to give on how to support these groups of students throughout their doctoral journey.

4.2 Theme 2: Self-disclosure

This is the second function highlighted by Kram and Isabella (1985) as being an important factor influencing the type of peer relationships that exist among work colleagues and it is explored as a theme among the doctoral students as well. Three phases of peer relationships emanated from this function: early phase, where students are just learning about one another; middle phase, where self-disclosure described by Kram and Isabella (1985) is developed; and the third phase, where disclosure declines or returned to the basic, similar to the early phase.

The subordinate themes below address the different types of relationships formed among the doctoral students according to these three phases.

4.2.1 Early phase

This phase typically represents year 1 and is characterised by doctoral students focused on getting used to the new system as well as gradually learning about their colleagues. For students who participate in the induction processes, their relationship may start there but for those who do not participate, it may start during the first meeting with their tutor/supervisor. Under this phase, there is usually no attempt for students to want to self-disclose to one another as they are more focused on understanding how things work in their environment as well as '*shadowing*' each other in terms of knowledge, friendliness, and attitude towards the doctoral journey. The '*shadowing*' is a lot easier to do when the doctoral programme has the first year

for lectures and seminars (e.g., DBA) compared to doctoral training like PhD where there is no form of regular interaction among the peers. However, this could still take place among students under the same supervisors.

As these students move towards the end of year one to early year two, there is a gradual acquaintance among the like-minds and likely neglect of others. That is, these doctoral students start to affirm their thoughts on what type of relationship they want to have and with whom among their peers. Participant Th, a third-year DBA student, reflected on his experience on how the early phase gradually faded out into the middle phase for him:

Firstly, you know, the first year of DBA is introduction year. So, we actually discussed everything about the assignments, presentations and that was good. In the second year when we started our research, it starts to be like personal communication and not about study anymore. So, I had to create a closed group (WhatsApp) out of this big group to be in just for the study only. So, I picked up my team.... – Th

According to this DBA student, they started by learning about each other and their new course. As they settle into the year, they were encouraged by their year tutor to join a WhatsApp group created for enhancing peer relationships among that cohort. Through this MIM app, the student's self-disclosure to one another started improving for the purpose of getting to know more about one another.

As the participants approach the middle phase, the types of peers described in the PRF gradually emanates. For example, participant Th mentioned that he began to get uncomfortable by some of the conversations taking place on the group chat while at the same identifying some people who he thinks have like-minds. This led to him creating a closed group chat with the latter. Again, confirming the descriptions given by Gronseth and Hebert (2018) that even

though some students would like to take part in activities involving their peers, they are not often happy with joining a group chat due to their inability to control the number of messages that enters their mobile (without blocking them). On the contrary, the experience of the PhD participants was a little different since, for this group of students, there is no introduction year. Participant Mi, who was in his first year of doctorate described his programme as:

So, certainly, there's no structure or sort of routine or timetable really to follow. Like when we were at the campus, it was a bit more fragmented, people just maybe sat at their desks more I suppose. And just got on with their work and then maybe had some lunch together but definitely, there wasn't as much interaction. - Mi

From this excerpt, it would seem as though there is no formal opportunity for participant Mi to get familiar with his colleagues. It is important to have that opportunity where peers get to gradually learn more about each other either physically or online, as this is the stage for building trust/distrust which would then determine how much of a self-disclosure takes place among the doctoral students (Proudfoot et al., 2018). Not having this opportunity may affect the level of self-disclosure that may take place in the next phase. Students under the same supervisor may try to get familiar with one another during a general meeting (if at all this takes place), adequate *shadowing* is unlikely as they might just be seeing one another for a short period and may not meet again for months. Perhaps, the more reason findings reported loneliness among doctoral students, who are mostly PhD students (see Bettinson and Haven-Tang, 2021; Doody et al., 2018; Hadjioannou et al., 2007; Mason and Hickman, 2019.)

4.2.2 Middle phase

As a follow-up on what was described by the research participants above, different types of peer relationships emerge as the doctoral students move fully into the second year of a doctoral

study which is typically three years in the UK. As the relationship progresses, self-disclosure also increases. While referencing Kram and Isabella's (1985) model, the different types of relationships developed among these peers and their features are highlighted below:

4.2.2.1 Special Peer

In this group, there is a high level of self-disclosure due to the high level of trust and a low level of distrust in most aspects of the discussions; the participants here are usually emotionally and academically supportive of each other and could also discuss personal issues to a large extent. This is referred to as '*Special Peer*' by Kram and Isabella (1985). Special peer is characterised by friendship; personal feedback; emotional support and confirmation. The extracts below are from two participants who identified that they have special peers among their colleagues:

.... we both understand what the other is going through because we're in a similar situation, we're studying part-time and our progress in the PhD is connected to our jobs. – CI

... I have like three or four people that I know; they can even answer me at one o'clock, two o'clock(am)..... It's not like even colleagues, we are family now. If someone gets married or having kids or whatever, we are the first to know. So, it's more like family – Ch

Being a part-time student was already difficult for CI as she had to combine managing family with work and her project, but with her peer relationships with someone going through a similar situation, she was able to feel motivated to want to continue with the study. Participant Ch made this even more explicit. She said she trusts her special peer so much that they would even answer her at 1:00 am. That is the kind of trust that must be present before the peer(s) could be tagged special. The feeling of being emotionally supported and knowing that you would always

have sincere feedback from your peers, as described by the participants above, fits the description given by Kram and Isabella (1985) on special peers. Referencing Lewicki et al.'s (1998) model of trust, it is stated that these colleagues must have a high level of trust and a low level of distrust to be this close to each other. There is also that high level of friendship and honest feedback where again, participant Ch used the term 'family' to describe the advanced level of the relationship that exists between her and her colleague.

4.2.2.2 Collegial peer

This group is characterised by a basic level of self-disclosure as the peer relationship is majorly focused on studies or emotional support but not characterised by the level of intimacy described under special peers above. In terms of Trust/Distrust, described by Lewicki et al. (1998), this type of peer has either a high trust in academic support and high distrust in emotional support or the opposite of this – high trust in emotional support and high distrust in academic issues. While the former believe they do not know each other well enough to discuss personal issues, the latter believe they do not know the level of knowledge in their peers enough to seek academic help from them. Kram and Isabella (1985) described these types of peers as the 'Collegial Peer' with features such as feedback; career strategising as described by participant Sa below:

...if I'm stuck in something, we discuss it in the group (general group) and maybe someone from the group knows about the subject, he or she shares that in the group, or even like mental support like we always keep in touch with each other if they're doing all right. They also message us. Like if you're doing all right, we are still getting in touch with all my colleagues, most of them – Sa

As described in the transcript above, participant Sa has peer relationships with most of her colleagues, but it is on a basic level. There is not much self-disclosure between them as they just discuss general issues around their studies as well as check on the well-being of one another. Most of their discussion is done on the general group created for the whole group or cohort. Even if they share personal numbers, the discussion would be issues relating to their studies and nothing more in-depth than that. As also described by Lee et al. (2017), she also mentioned that they show some level of care to each other but they seldomly send each other personal messages when compared to special peers.

The collegial type of peer, especially the one with more focus on academics is found mostly among the PhD students, compared to the DBA students, as they prefer to check on each other's academic progress with a brief check up on each other's well-being rather than discussing in-depth any family or personal matters.

With these descriptions given, it is affirmed that collegial type of peers is found among the UWS doctoral students although it may be more among the PhD than the DBA students.

4.2.2.3 Information peers

Participants in this group tend to just have a relationship only because they are colleagues with the other peer with almost no level of self-disclosure. These groups of doctoral students tend to not have any interaction apart from when this is organised by the university, supervisor, or tutor such as class sessions, conferences, supervisory meetings among others. Even though they may say hello to each other, it tends to not go beyond that, their interactions are mostly for a purpose and often brief (Lee et al., 2017). The information peer is described by participant Cr and Ku below:

... we just kept in touch via WhatsApp when it comes to anything to do with coursework or assignments. Anything else apart from that? We wouldn't do

it - Cr

... we have less communication than we were in the class. We talk about more issues while we were in the class because we had lots of assignments

and deadlines – Ku

From the transcript from Cr, she mentioned that they just kept in touch on the main group chat and that only happens when it is about their academic work as that is the only thing connecting them as peers, apart from this, they do not have any interaction whatsoever. Participant Ku (DBA) re-emphasised this by stating that most of her conversations with colleagues happened when they were in the classroom, which understandably will be when they had to perform a task as a group or simply about just saying hello to each other before and after sessions (only when it is unavoidable). Self-disclosure is not expected here as again, it is expected to only start developing as interactions gradually develop among peers (McKenna et al., 2007). As summarised in Kram and Isabella's (1985) PRF, these types of peers are referred to as *information peers* – showing little or no emotional support or feedback to each other. When Lewicki et al.'s (1998) trust model is explored to describe the type of trust that exists among information peers, it would be seen that they are characterised by low trust/low distrust in both academic and non-academic issues. In sum, the absence of interaction leads to no self-disclosure and invariably causes little or no tangible peer relationships.

Since the features stated in the extracts above fits well with the description proposed under PRF information peer, it could be said that this type of peer relationship does exist among the doctoral students of UWS.

4.2.2.4 Dysfunctional peers

The dysfunctional type of peer relationships was not identified by the Kram and Isabella (1985) framework. However, it was first discovered by Lee et al. (2017) during the cause of adapting the PRF to explore peer relationships among doctoral students. As it was not the focus of their research, these authors proposed that further examination by future researchers in this area is necessary.

The unique feature of dysfunctional peers is that self-disclosure is not only absent, but the peers involved also have negative feelings towards each other. The participants of this study confirmed the presence of dysfunctional peers among them. They stated that some colleagues are either unfriendly or unhelpful or are just not compatible with the way they do things due to their completely different views. As a result, they would avoid having any form of peer relationships with each other:

if I asked someone for help.... maybe he forgets or whatever like I'll just put him in this category that he may not help. And yeah, like, I don't want to waste my time. - Ch

But there are so many people who don't have anything in common with you because they are on completely different paths – Kh

...first, because I know that they don't know and from your experience, you know, that this guy or this girl, maybe, is not very committed to studying or the third thing is sometimes you know that he will not even try to help – Ka

The extract from participant Ch reveals that she would categorise a peer as being dysfunctional if they are the type of person not always willing to help others. She feels that person is selfish, and it might negatively affect her if she creates any relationship with that kind of person as she

would always feel sad around them. Likewise, someone like participant Ka feels some of his peers belongs to this sub-section due to their non-committal attitude which means he would not be able to trust them for anything. When asked about this type of peer, participant Kh believes that it is normal for her not to agree with some of her colleagues as they may be on a different path from hers. These submissions suggest that these peer relationships are characterised by a *low level of trust* described by Lewicki et al. (1998) as being characterised by hesitance, passivity, no hope, no confidence, and no faith and a *high level of distrust*, made up of cynicism, vigilance, fear, watchfulness, and scepticism (Lewicki et al., 1998). From the descriptions given by the participants, it can be confirmed that the type of peer described fits well with the features of low trust and high distrust. Therefore, it could be said that *dysfunctional peers* exist among the doctoral students of UWS.

Comparing the types of peers reviewed under self-disclosure shows that dysfunctional peers are the opposite of special peers since special peer is characterised by a high level of self-disclosure, friendliness, regular feedback on academic progression. On the other hand, the dysfunctional peer is known for *no self-disclosure, no feedback* and *unfriendliness*. This is not surprising as Moktar (2012) and Guerin, Jayatilaka, and Ranasinghe's (2015) studies insist that not all doctoral students would get along since their motivations are different. While some enrol to meet a requirement at their workplace; some are doing the programme for self-fulfilment while others embark on the journey to make a scholarly contribution. For these reasons, it is normal to not always agree with each other as mentioned by Moktar (2012) and Guerin et al. (2015).

It should be noted that due to the level of education and exposure of these groups of students, having a dysfunctional type of peer may never lead to any confrontation because as participant Mo said, *'I think the PGR students are senior, and they know their rights and responsibility. And I personally do believe that PGR students abide by the UWS rules or personnel ethics.'*

This is possibly why it had not been discovered by other researchers aside from Lee et al. (2017). Nonetheless, this study affirms Lee et al.'s (2017) position that a dysfunctional peer relationship does exist among doctoral students at UWS.

The findings from this study confirm the outcomes from Kram and Isabella (1985) and that from Lee et al.'s (2017) studies. However, there were other things to note. One of them was the fact that the participants placed more priority on friendliness and being approachable when it comes to peer relationships even though this was not clearly stated in the two studies referenced above. Perhaps, this is because the participants' environment was already academic, and knowledge might no longer be a scarce feature to find around them. A typical representation of their opinion was provided by participant Cr who said, '*... if there would be a colleague who was very knowledgeable, but we don't have a good rapport, I wouldn't have approached him. I would say rapport is key, then intellectual capacity.*' For Cr, knowledge is also crucial as proposed in Kram and Isabella (2017) however, for her and her colleagues, they would approach someone more friendly and accepting first before they would consider the person's intellectual capability.

4.2.3 Late phase

The late phase is characterised by the final stage/year of the doctorate programme. The stage also constitutes the writing phase towards completion for these students and, as they approach this stage, there is that feeling of wanting to re-organise one's life ahead of post-doctorate life. Participants Sh and Ni extracts below helps to elucidate more on this phase:

...then you come into the last stages of your PhD I think compared to first year and second year, third year and fourth year are different. That time you really don't want to meet a lot of people anyway because we have

explored so many options... I wanted to restrict myself you know limited friends whom you can really talk in detail about my PhD journey - Sh

I think I would have quit earlier but now; I know how to manage and how to get support. So, I would not quit easily compared to my first year and second year – Ni

As described by participant Sh, new peer relationships are rarely developed at the late phase, rather the students would prefer to maintain their existing relationships or even sometimes reduce it which means that the level of self-disclosure would depend on the relationship they have right from the middle phase. Participant Sh explained that at this stage, she was more focused on how to complete her studies hence self-disclosure might be minimal for her.

Understandably, and as participant Ni described it, there is no likelihood of dropping out at this stage due to the commitments that have been put in place (Lovitts, 2002). In addition, it is also possible that participant Ni is now mentoring students from 'junior' levels (i.e., year 1) therefore it would be a shameful thing to drop except when the circumstances are inevitable (Ampaw and Jaeger, 2012). In terms of the financial investment mentioned by Lovitts (2002) participant Ni, a self-funded international doctoral student at UWS would have spent over £30,000 on tuition fees by this late phase therefore dropping out would not be a good choice for her at this stage except for unavoidable reasons. The home students who have an opportunity for a tuition loan are not exempted from these considerations as well as they would need to pay the government back. This must be why even though Wegener et al. (2016) submitted that doctoral students often find the writing stage (especially the late stage) daunting, this rarely translates to drop-out. Rather, they would consider an extension or a break in the study except if the reason for dropping out was absolutely beyond their control.

Another participant who described his late phase said:

I think what I did (at this stage), I did self-reflection, rearrange everything in my life during this time and I set a plan for myself and then I went for some online, you know, motivation speaking something like that or TED

Talks. -Th

For him, it was a case of reflecting on his journey and doing some self-learning on how to ensure he was ready for the challenges ahead of him. This preparedness attitude may be due to the high expectations people normally have on an academic doctorate in terms of attitude and ways of life since this is the highest level of degree anyone could acquire. Therefore, it was just normal for the doctoral students at the late phase to want to engage in what was described by participant Th.

4.3 Theme 3: Trust/Distrust

Trust is central to all peer relationships; it is what determines the level of developmental functions and self-disclosure among peers. Apart from its influence on the type of MIMs used for supporting each other, it also determines who the students seek help from. In a nutshell, it is the chain that connects all the functions of the project's conceptual framework just as succinctly described in the PRF by Kram and Isabella (1985). This theme has four subordinates used to classify how trust/distrust influences who the doctoral students seek support from.

4.3.1 Trusting peers within the university

The participants in this category believe it is okay to have a high trust for the peer relationships developed within their university (UWS) as this will enable them to support each other using similar resources. This relationship could be with immediate peers or with those in higher-level (seniors) or both.

4.3.1.1 Immediate peers

Although the participants of this study were not emphatic on the word ‘trust’ however, as a concept, a lot of their descriptions such as the use of *close*, *strong-bond* and *understand*, implies the role of trust/distrust and vice versa:

We're good friends, the reason why I go to him is because there's that long-term sort of friendship developed over time. So, I think there's a sense that we both understand what the others going through because we're in a similar situation. – CI

Yes, I asked for help from my colleague all the time, they helped. I don't know if it's like for all cohorts but for us, it was just like family -Ta

These types of high trust are often found among special peers and this group of people are characterised by a low level of distrust. The participants made it known that the relationship did not just become strong in one day but was usually nurtured (as the self-disclosure increases). For example, participant CI chose her friend after a long period of observation to see if the friend was worth being trusted and, after some time, she concluded that they connected easily both emotionally and academically and thus she chose him as that special friend. For participant Ta, shadowing for like-minds was not difficult as she had her first-year session structured for lecture sessions and she was able to use this period to observe and learn about her colleagues. From there, she formed a special bond with those with like-minds and they were able to support each other throughout the journey. Hence, it could be said that even though the PhD students do not have an enabling programme structure that encourages interactions among colleagues, it could still be possible to create a special peer relationship through activities taking place outside of their academic programme.

Unlike those mentioned above, some trust may develop through peer-to-peer meetings organised by a supervisor/tutor to enhance peer relationships. This is the case with participant Mi

and his colleagues who were encouraged to meet through WebEx (during the pandemic) to have a quick chat around general things:

So, every day at nine o'clock, we (PhD students) check-in through WebEx, we check on each other.... kind of just peer to peer support really - Mi

According to him, his supervisor encouraged them to log in to their group page every morning to check on each other as well as get acquainted with their colleagues. As the days passed, the number of attendees dropped as they could not keep up with the daily commitments but before the morning check-in stopped, he had been able to create a rapport with a few he feels he could trust their ideology, and they went on to connect on a more personal level. What to think of here is, based on the PhD structure, it might be a bit of a challenge for the students to engage in peer relationships. That is, if his supervisor did not organise that kind of peer-to-peer interaction forum, participant Mi might never have had the opportunity to meet other peers not to talk of providing support to the others he met through that informal platform.

4.3.1.2 Senior peers

Meanwhile, some participants such as participant Ra said she could only trust (high trust) colleagues from outside her cohort or even from other campuses and usually from higher levels:

So, to be honest, I'm interacting more with other PhD students from other campuses, or like DBA students from other cohorts compared to my own classmates – Ra

This participant who just concluded her second year at the time of the interview has chosen to interact more with people outside of her cohort even if peer-to-peer support was available among her immediate colleagues. Her reason was that she believed they would have more knowledge and experience than her immediate peers and she would like to keep her needs away from her colleagues due to privacy reasons (high distrust).

Even though participant Ra was from London Campus, she related so well with those from other UWS campuses because she has a high trust/low distrust for the help she would get from them than from her immediate peers, therefore seeking all her help from these seniors.

4.3.2 Trusting peers outside UWS university

Some participants chose to seek most of their support from peers outside of the university system for a wider level of knowledge, and also for privacy reasons. Participant Ka said he joined an international group of PhD students on Facebook where he asks for guidance on his project, especially around methodology, and other areas of doctoral education:

I'm a member in various PhD Facebook groups, they will give you a very good Article and how you progress PhD....sometimes I asked a question, and I received a good answer. This is one from PhD from all over the world not only UK – Ka

According to participant Ka, the support he gets from these peers helps him to have a wide range and an enriching level of knowledge as the students in that group are from different countries. He added that he also gains lots of motivation by reading other people's experiences on how they were able to complete their doctorate despite the challenges they went through during the journey.

In a similar context, participant Sa said she maintained her relationship with friends from previous universities in her home country as many of them also moved to the UK for a doctorate. With the existing high level of trust, they created a closed group page on the most famous MIM - WhatsApp (Statista Research Department, 2021b) - where they were able to interact with each other. It was easy to provide help to each other on this platform as they were all at different stages in their doctoral journey, while some of them had completed their studies and were already working, others were at different stages of their research. Below is an extract from participant Sa's transcript:

I have few friends who are doing PhD at the same time, and I have some friends back home who have already finished their PhD and are engaging in teaching at the moment. So sometimes, I talk to them about my research.

– Sa

To the likes of participant Ka and participant Sa, they would prefer to express their vulnerability to someone who was not in the same university as them. This way, they believe, would help them maintain their existing outlook amidst their university colleagues and invariably help to keep their weaknesses away from their colleagues. This might be a good approach if the outside help is able to clearly understand their unique challenges, but most of the time, the issue might be content-specific such that someone at the same level or under the same supervisor would be the best person to give concise help. Nonetheless, trusting outside help is always better than trusting ‘no help’ at all.

4.3.3 Trusting no peers

All doctoral students rely on the support they get from their supervisors, that is a default. They may now decide to combine this formal help with the ones available informally through peer relationships as described previously. However, some students would prefer to maintain only the support they get from their supervisors/university. These are the group of students mentioned by Jazvac-Martek et al. (2012) who do not want to seek help from peers even when they are aware that the support is available to them.

As clearly described by participant Di and participant Li, they do not seek help from any peer relationships because they are satisfied with the formal support they get from their supervisors and/or the university. Secondly, they have an independent view of their studies believing that a doctorate is an individual journey and should therefore remain so:

..... So, oftentimes maybe I thought it was not necessary for me to seek help because all the help I can find they are in the books, I can approach let's say

my supervisor or professor or expert, there was really not much needed for me to go and seek help from the friends(peers) - Di

From my point of view, I'm getting good help from my supervisor. I would say I am quite happy with that... I didn't need that support from my colleagues; you know – Li

Participant Di is of the opinion that the essence of having supervisors is to be able to guide one and he would always prefer to go to them for this purpose and, whenever they are not available or he does not feel like asking them, he would consult other experts in the field or consult books. To him, going to his peer is no good, it does not matter if they are knowledgeable or not, he just does not see any need for it. From a different perspective, participant Li said he does not need any help from his peers because he was getting sufficient help from his supervisor so going to peers for support was not needed. This invariably means that the supervisor has been able to play all the roles needed by him, thus he sees going to others outside his supervisory team as being unnecessary.

The below responses from participants Ab and Uc further emphasise participant Li's position that if enough support is gotten from a supervisor, there might not be any need to seek help from peers:

.... my supervisor was very good, because he was really more or less like a counsellor rather than a supervisor – Ab

..... she (supervisor) is very helpful to me. Not just about my write-ups, but some personal issues and we just go around some issues and what's happening in our lives, her own life. I think it's been good – Uc

They are typically the four participants (Di, Li, Ab, and Uc) under this subsection and a few others but, these four insist that the support they get from the university is enough for them and

the support from peers is irrelevant. However, an experience later shared by participant Di implies that things could have possibly been better if he had a positive form of peer relationships:

.... halfway through my research, I realised that the work I was doing, maybe was not going anywhere. And I changed my entire research. And what I was left, nine-ten months to finish the whole research and I started all over again. So, the only thing I could do was spend day and night in the library, trying to get through it – Di

To emphasise the relationship between trust/distrust and developmental functions and self-disclosure, this study finds that the peers that see peer relationships as trivial and overwhelming as the same group of students who would engage in little or no self-disclosure and invariably seek outside help or no help from peers at all. Irrespective of the School or campus they belong to, one thing that is obvious from these participants' positions is the fact that they seem to be getting sufficient help from their supervisors, it might be more from one supervisor than the other, but that support seems enough to get them through their doctoral studies irrespective of the School or campus they belong to, one thing that is obvious from these participants' positions is the fact that they seem to be getting sufficient help from their supervisors, it might be more from one supervisor than the other, but that support seems enough to get them through their doctoral studies.

Even though this participant eventually completed his thesis on time, he had to go through a marathon writing – writing a three-year piece of work in nine months. Perhaps, he could have discovered the non-feasibility of the study earlier through conversations with his peer(s) or better still through peer learning described under one of the themes above rather than waiting

until nine months before the end of his doctoral programme before re-writing a three-year piece of work.

A similar situation was also noticed during a follow-up interview conducted with students who mentioned difficulties around their studies during the first interview sessions. The situation further confirmed that every student could benefit from a positive form of peer relationship. As seen in the excerpt above, participant Uc was one of those that stated that they do not trust any support coming from their peers and that the formal support is sufficient for her. She maintained the same position up until the end of the follow-up interview session. Her opinion is provided below:

.... I would say, there's really nothing much that anybody can help me with because... everybody's research area is different from the other person. I think that's why everyone's like just working in isolation because there's really no need to ask any question - Uc

However, what happened immediately after the follow-up interview was different from this view. Immediately after the interview recording was stopped, the researcher decided to ask how the participant was doing, and this single question led to an hour of intense conversation. And after the interview/chat, the participant (participant Uc) sent a message out to the researcher through WhatsApp to say, “... *I enjoyed our chat, felt lighter too, sometimes u can just bottle-up so much pain without knowing... thanks a lot. God bless you*”. From this encounter, it became clear that every student benefits from having a peer relationship even if it just means having someone to listen to your problems and saying a statement as simple as ‘you will be fine’. This could go a long way to ease the stress the student might be facing at that time. No wonder, Jazvac-Martek et al. (2012) posited that every student could benefit from emotional support no matter how self-regulated they were.

In participant Uc's case, two things may be preventing her from wanting to engage with other peers. She might have low trust in the support that would be provided by her peers thus she might want to distance herself from them. Or she might just not know how to ask for help from her peers as described in participant Kh's excerpt below:

Maybe I need that push or something I need the motivation... I want to have some classes where I can get some quantitative stats related guidance.... some support from the university.

Maybe I didn't ask, but I don't know how to ask probably (long silence) – Ku

For her, it is not a case of trusting or not trusting, she just does not know how to ask even though she needed the help as urgent as possible. In contrast to this group of people, some students would not only trust the relationship they develop with their peers, but they would also go all out to explore all the support available to them, be it, supervisors, colleagues, or outside peers. Participants such as like participants Sh and Mo was quite flexible as they were able to attest to the fact that they have explored all available options mentioned under the subordinates above:

So definitely, I got adequate support from my colleagues, my seniors, my supervisors, and the UWS team, including counselling and library staff.

Without that, I don't think I would have been able to cope with

that(journey) soon. - Sh

I'm basically supported by my PGR school, my research centre, and my PhD fellow Students.... also, I connect with some of the PGR students who came from my country, my neighbour countries - Pakistan, Sri Lanka, India. They're culturally almost similar and I'm able to connect to some of

them not only for academic – Mo

Participant Sh, who is currently in her final year, reflected on how she was always going to seek help from any platform available as she trusts that they would be able to help her meet her needs. She was able to form a special bond with three of her immediate colleagues, but this group was mainly for emotional support as their areas of studies were different especially their methodology. Thus, she seeks academic help from her senior peers in the same field who guide her with things like ethics application, thesis structuring, suggestions on books to read on methodology, how to pass viva, and next steps to take in seeking graduate positions. She added that she also used the support available in the university (guidance and counselling) in addition to the help she received from her supervisor. According to her, these supports helped her finish her doctoral training on time and with the highest level of fulfilment. This was also the case with Mo, a first-year doctoral student who seeks help not only from the university but also from his current workplace and colleagues, either immediate or senior. During the focus group sessions, these two participants expressed their satisfaction with all the support they were getting. This is also reflected in their non-verbal expression which could imply that they seem to be getting the necessary emotional and academic support. And, as expected, they had more experience to share during the sessions about peer relationships and their impact than the rest of their colleagues who participated in the study (most especially the ‘trusting no peer’ group’). Although, Gazit et al. (2018) stated that the active participants of online interviews are often extroverted while the non-active was most likely introverts. This may not necessarily be the case as it is believed that people would only want to contribute to what they have the knowledge of, as seen in the participants mentioned above. For this study, those that were speaking more may not necessarily be extroverted, they might just happen to have engaged more in peer relationships compared to the other participants.

As noted throughout this thesis Lewicki et al.’s (1998) position on trust and distrust was the main reference for analysing trust in this study. However, some other trust ideas were also

evident. One of them is the confirmation of Gambetta's (2000) position which presents that trusting does not involve coercion or force as it could be seen throughout the analysis that developing or not developing a peer relationship was solely the students' choice.

From the concept of six degrees of trust highlighted by Dietz (2004), relational-based trust is the closest that could be used to describe the relationship that exists among the interviewed group of students since they mostly function on the mutuality that exists among them. It is not knowledge-based because they do not decide their relationship based on how knowledgeable a colleague is, it is not identification-based because extreme intimacy hardly occurs among them. Neither is it deference, calculus, or institutional-based as they hardly try to prey on each other's vulnerability (see Chapter Two, page 40). Yet again, contrary to Dietz (2004) position, the information gathered from the participants of this study suggests that trust in peer relationships among doctoral students does not occur as a continuum. This is because, according to the views of the participants, the same individual could be trusted for academic support but distrusted for emotional support just as positioned by Lewicki et al. (1998).

From the extracts highlighted above, it is evident that a peer can have high hope, confidence, and no hesitation (high trust) in their colleagues regarding emotional support while having a high level of doubts (high distrust) in the same person's ability to help with explaining grounded theory, among others. The connection between the types of peer relationships and the role of trust/distrust confirms that the inclusion of Lewicki et al.'s (1998) model into the framework is imperative.

4.4 Theme 4: Impact of COVID 19

Even though the study of peer relationships spans beyond the COVID-19 period, the impact of the pandemic could not be ignored as participants continually referred to it. Thus, the reason they are discussed under one theme. Despite having different circumstances, the responses from the research participants during both one-to-one interviews and focus groups were

consistent. The discussion ranged from an increase in the level of their loneliness to how difficult it had been to move all interactions online and the uncertainties involved with everything. The international students also added their struggle with having to deal with all of these in addition to adjusting to a new life in the UK amidst the pandemic.

4.4.1 Uncertainties and Anxiety

There was an overwhelming use of the word ‘challenging’ alongside related words such as ‘difficult,’ ‘struggle,’ ‘depressed,’ ‘frustrating,’ ‘confusion,’ ‘devastated’ when the research participants were asked to describe how they felt about the pandemic. As seen in the transcript extract below, participant Ad developed depression due to the anxiety and uncertainties around the pandemic and the fact that he was thousands of miles away from his loved ones:

So, you know, for me, the biggest challenge for me in this pandemic - you don't know what's gonna happen in the future because of our concern about data collection....so would it be personal interview; virtual interview or just secondary data so we don't know exactly what we want to do. This will make a lot of confusion - Ka

*I start feeling
more depressed... I am still taking some medicines and I'm actually
thinking to finish this DBA as soon as I can and go back to my
country because I think that I'm losing the taste of studies, especially
during the COVID-19. – Ad*

Just like participant Ka, other participants mentioned that they felt uncertain about when the pandemic would be over which meant that they did not have an idea of when they would return to the university campus or get involved in face-to-face University activities and this has increased their frustrations. For someone like participant Ad, he had to worry about how he would pay his tuition fee since the shop he worked for had shut down due to the lockdown. In

addition to this, he worried he might not be able to get enough help from his colleagues as he tended to be considerate of people's busy schedules unless he saw them physically. Above all, he was worried that his older parents might not survive COVID-19 if they should contract it. All of these challenges accumulated into anxiety and fear for him and that made him suffer from depression to the extent he had to be placed on medication. This type of experience was described by Pragholapti (2020) and other researchers as the major challenge students faced during the pandemic. To this extent, Cao et al. (2020) recommended an immediate and regular psychological intervention for students during and after the pandemic. Even though this service may be present at UWS, as can be seen from the comments made by participants Ka and Ad, it could not still change any of their current situations as the lockdown rules were implemented for the whole nation.

The follow-up interview further confirmed the negative effects of COVID-19 on people's mental health and other ways of life. Even though participant Kh was one of those who mentioned having special peers during the first interview sessions when asked how the relationship was going now after eight months, her response was that:

It has reduced a little bit because I think there has been a lot of gaps. And I'm also in a different country, this time zone problem. And I'm also going through a lot of mental health issues. So maybe, I'm not very, you know, I'm not being very proactive to talk about things. – Kh

Participant Kh's situation had deteriorated compared to the first interview and the focus group session due to many factors involved especially poor supervisory support. An extract from the conversation that ensued between the participant and interviewer is below:

Kh: *maybe I need that push or something I need the motivation... I want to have some classes where I can get some quantitative stats related guidance.*

And my supervisor won't help me with that... It's not that I want someone to teach me, but I just want basic guidance

Mod: *What do you think would have helped?*

Kh: *I don't know, some support from the university. Maybe I didn't ask, but I don't know how to ask probably (long silence), I know something from my supervisor definitely would help a lot like some little help, guidance, motivation. It's like, I am forcing him to be my supervisor. It's not, it's not nice.*

Mod: *Especially at this time, we need that extra boost.*

Kh: *(cuts in) forget extra, forget extra there is not even basic. The basic is not there. It's hurtful.*

In addition to the challenges with her study, she also had to deal with the dwindling financial situation of her sponsor (her parents) as the lockdown in their home country also meant that they had stopped working and their savings were depleting faster than expected. All of these made her mental health deteriorate badly to the extent that a special flight had to be organised to return her to her home country from the UK. Reflecting on her current situation, she said:

I'm sorry, I also skipped messages because it's like I do not talk to anybody. And I don't know what I am doing. Yeah, I don't think at all. Like, I just sleep the whole day wake up and that's it. I keep thinking about it(dissertation), but I hardly do a thing whenever I open it, I just sat on my laptop and that is it. - Kh

The truth about the pandemic period was that doctoral students and everyone else was only trying to survive the virus and the different stressor factors attached to it. While some were

mourning the loss of loved ones, some were dealing with financial challenges while being careful not to contract the virus. Therefore, even though it was supposed to be the time when peer relationships via MIM platforms were at the highest, it was understandably at its minimal. This is described further below by participant Ku:

I have not made efforts to talk because... my personal mental health has definitely declined because of this pandemic. I mean, issues at home, I'm not in the right state to talk to anyone.

*So definitely pandemic has played a major role here -**Ku***

For participant was dealing with financial problems as her parents has been laid off due to the pandemic. Above all, she was having challenges with her supervisor, coupled with the fear of contracting coronavirus. Even though she had lots of time in her hand to chat and engage with peers, these internal and external challenges prevent her from doing so (Sverdlik et al., 2018; Wollast et al., 2018).

Another participant, who took part in the follow-up interview- participant Mr - had a different struggle as the lockdown lingered. Unlike the other two participants above, she was a married woman who had to also help her children with their online learning as they were also home-schooling due to the lockdown in the UK. Even though she did not have a problem with supervisory support, concentrating on her academic work had been her major challenge:

I'm back downstairs instead of doing my work in my room. I am coordinating my little one because he's having online school and the teachers just give them tasks forgetting that some of us are not teachers...

*look at my laptop (points to her laptop), it's in front of me I can't do anything, and the day is going. - **Mr***

From the first interview, this PhD student confirmed that she has always had the much-needed support from her supervisors however she had been finding it difficult to focus on her doctoral

studies due to having to engage and supervise her children during their home-schooling. She added that since the start of the year, she had not been able to join the Acwri, an activity she said had been contributing positively to her writing progress whenever she was able to participate.

Reflecting on what she said about being unable to connect with the black community during the first interview, she confirmed a WhatsApp group has now been created for that purpose:

... that WhatsApp page that we formed. I don't know, maybe because of the COVID, it is so bad, everyone is silent...maybe if we meet somehow if we have like a zoom meeting, I don't know if that will help. - Mr

However, as it could be seen from the excerpt above, tangible interactions among the group members were picking up slowly or 'shadowing' so to say being a new group chat platform. This might change as the level of interaction among them improves. Therefore, it could be said that the position of participant Mr coincides with the argument made in the literature review and earlier in this study that self-disclosure, especially among a group, occurs gradually (Gretry et al., 2017). To increase their level of interaction she noted that, perhaps, they could meet more on Zoom as this app is one of the MIM-enabled platforms that encourage live engagement among people.

While these participants have said that things have not improved during the follow-up interview, participant Ad narrated otherwise. According to him, he used to feel incapable of the journey before the follow-up interview as seen in his excerpt above but listening to other students during the focus group of the first session reassured him that it was not about his incapability and that he just needed to improve himself to make things work. He added that,

I think the first thing that changed my perspective about my own research and everything, is after the first interview, and the focus group, I

understood that I'm not the only one that have a problem. I can see that even my colleagues are still struggling in this situation, and they still hanging on. So, I really appreciate that because they give me motivation to stay on track as well. It's like an invisible connection between us - Ad

However, the key thing to note here is that his struggles were not resolved by him alone as it was first identified by his supervisor. It was the supervisor who then introduced him to one of the senior doctoral students whom she thought could help participant Ad. As narrated by him, this 'senior' was able to provide for him what he needed the most: morale-boosting. Invariably, by just paying attention to the needs of his student, the supervisor had saved another student from the thought of dropping out from his doctoral studies. This point is important as it clarifies that even though this study is advocating for an enhanced level of peer relationships among doctoral students, it identifies that the supervisory role cannot be replaced (Berry 2017; Lindsay, 2015; Subramanian et al., 2013). Interestingly, that was not the single act that changed this participant's stand around dropping out because even though the supervisor had played her role, the student would also need to make some efforts as well. For example, participant Ad worked with the senior colleague by requesting to join most of the activities that were being mentioned by other participants while he continued to work on himself. Within eight months of the interview, he was able to come off his antidepressant medication and moved from sounding weak and low in the mood to becoming an energetic, confident, and focused student. This has been no doubt emphasised by the existing literature to be the unique role of peer relationships among doctoral students (Byl et al., 2016; Collings, Swanson, and Watkins, 2016; Devenish et al., 2009; Lee, 2008; Lindsay, 2015, Meschitti, 2019).

In sum, even though the supervisor gave the enabling environment, the student also played a huge role in making sure the peer support worked for him. The conversation also affirmed that peer relationships have a significant role to play in reducing the drop-out thoughts of some

doctoral students. This is evident in the fact that in just two interactive sessions with his colleagues, participant Ad's views about his doctoral journey were changed from being clueless to having lots of confidence. One could only imagine what could have happened if he had not had the opportunity to interact with his colleagues via the interview sessions.

4.4.2 Loneliness

Loneliness has been highlighted to be one of the major problems of doctoral students before the COVID-19 pandemic (Nordentoft et al., 2012); although the pandemic made it even worse. The responses from participants Ik and Nt below further emphasised how loneliness has increased during the pandemic:

Assuming there was no pandemic, I might say, okay, let me go and visit my friend and find out what he's up to..... sometimes you just want to go and make some noise where your friends are, you know – Ik

For someone like participant Ik, he used to spend his free time in his friend's house where they would engage in non-academic activities such as playing games, arguing about sports, or just chatting before the lockdown. However, this was no longer possible due to the lockdown restrictions which meant he was not able to visit his friends and he was forced to focus only on his studies which, according to him, became tiring being the only activity he could engage in. He, therefore, feels COVID-19 had made loneliness even worse for him as he was confined to his room due to the restrictions across the country.

Another participant (Nt) also emphasised the fact that even though isolation was something she would normally experience as a doctoral student, the lockdown that resulted from the COVID-19 pandemic has made it worse. In her words, *'I've been facing a lot of challenges during this COVID-19. Plus, being a doctoral student, it is a big problem to face when you are being isolated by yourself'*. Just like many other students, this participant is a first-generation

international student in the UK, the rest of her family (and friends) reside in her home country (Sri Lanka). Before COVID-19, she was able to manage her loneliness by visiting friends in other parts of the UK such as Swindon and Oxford even though she lived in London. However, this had been made worse by the pandemic as she had to stay indoors as the movement was restricted across the country and internationally. The movement restrictions were lifted by 2021, however, the United Kingdom and many other countries are still conscious of cross border movement to reduce the spread of the virus. The implication of this for students such as participant Nt is that she is not certain about when she would be able to visit her parents in her home country, again increasing her level of uncertainties and anxiety as analysed earlier. These findings further confirmed one of the conclusions made from the large-scale survey conducted by SMARTen (Byron, 2020) and that of Dong and Bouey (2020) that the increased level of loneliness among doctoral students has led to a decrease in their mental wellbeing.

The above excerpts are from the perspectives of international students, and while it has been argued that this group of doctoral students experience more challenges than the home students, this is not to mean that a home student does not feel lonely (McLaughlin and Sillence, 2018). Participant Mi, a first-year home student admitted that although he was grateful to have his family nearby, that made little difference as he could not visit them during the total lockdown. However, he admitted that the feelings would definitely be different for the international students whose family and friends were thousands of miles away because, as the lockdown eased, he was at least able to meet up with his parents while observing the social distancing guidelines. His major worries with the COVID-19 pandemic were around his data collection which was supposed to take place within a care home:

So, because of the Coronavirus, there's been a lot of changes to that (research) because I wouldn't be able to visit really, because of how they are devastated in care home environments. So, it basically involves me

changing the timelines of my studies or I start working on a systematic

literature review – Mi

This participant has almost completed his methodology chapter and had already sent out letters of invitation to the manager of his preferred care homes (his research area was around dementia in the elderly people) when the pandemic started. So, his data collection was stopped abruptly following the 2020 lockdown announcement by the UK government. Even after the total lockdown, he could not go on to complete his data collection as care homes were one of the worst-hit by the pandemic, and thus, were dealing with issues more emotionally intense than engaging in research work. Therefore, he was left with no choice but to seek an alternative approach that would best suit his work.

During this sensitive time, the use of MIM apps played a significant role in helping peers stay in touch with each other for both academic and non-academic purposes. During one of the focus group sessions, two of the participants mentioned how the MIM apps had been a great alternative for them:

Sh: *I think it's a blessing to have these platforms, at least we are connected, we're adequately supported too.*

Ka: *Very good alternative. Yes, I agree with you but not 100%. But thank God we have this kind of platform to share information to help each other.*

The conversation above was the prevailing opinion among the participants of this study. It appears from their statements that the use of MIM apps might not be their number one choice for peer relationships, but it was the best alternative for keeping them connected with family and friends during the pandemic. Moreover, there was no other alternative for students at that time as argued by Aucejo et al. (2020) that students and universities needed to adapt to the rules proposed by the government, whether they were happy with it or not. Invariably, leading

to the growth of an online community of practice (Wenger-Trayner and Wenger-Trayner, 2015) among the doctoral students which to an extent helped in managing the mental well-being of students.

4.4.3 Struggling with virtual learning

The literature confirms that the use of MIM apps had helped doctoral students stay connected, however, it appeared that this might only happen when these apps are used voluntarily and for a short period (Gronseth and Hebert, 2018). When used for formal learning, doctoral students seem to have a different opinion about the app. Perhaps, this is because, with formal learning, students are expected to engage for a restricted period while dressed and sat in an area considered appropriate for learning. Doctoral students found this strange as they were used to physical meetings be it for conferences or any other academic session hence a 100% switch to online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic became a challenge for most of them. For example, participant Ch had been used to visiting libraries to search for academic resources for her research work. She was also used to just going to meet her supervisor in the office for any part of her work that needed some clarifications. As expected, it became a challenge for her to rely on online resources and virtual connections with her supervisors:

Well, it's been a struggle trying to get the resources I need, since we are not allowed to go to campus because of the lockdown. They (university) try to do as much as they can online but, for me, it's not been so helpful in terms of getting the resources for my work – Ch

Meanwhile, the worry of participants such as Mi and Uc (excerpts presented below) was about the boredom attached to engaging online with peers. Although students like participant Uc and participant Mi are what Jazvac-Martek et al. (2012) described as being self-regulated as they do not seem to have an issue with studying independently, however, they could not withstand

sitting in a constant position for long for virtual interaction due to the absence of other communication enhancers such as body language:

..... it's a bit difficult to have that communication and I'm better off with it when I'm seeing you physically, this whole online stuff, chatting is not really my thing. So that's why it's a bit difficult – Uc.

I definitely think this (online chat) is tiredness, somethings are quite difficult to sit for such long period of time off, and in one position and things. – Mi

Another participant who also admitted struggling with virtual learning was participant Ad. The lockdown came when this participant was just completing a one-year lecture session for DBA students. That means it was the first time he would have to be alone without any face-to-face interaction with peers and tutors. This became a huge concern for him. He said, *'to be honest, I struggled a little bit during these tough times in terms of, how to do the whole work by yourself.* The only option he had was the use of MIM for connecting with peers for support as mentioned above. The struggle of these participants appears to reflect Hill and Fitzgerald's (2020) findings who also lamented how they, as postgraduate students, struggled to switch to online resources as it was all new to them. As the students do not feel confident that they may ever get used to virtual learning, their concern about when the pandemic would be over increased exponentially. Like the rest of his colleagues, participant Ad was left confused on how to get started with his project, and in no time his anxiety increased to a depression level that he had to be placed on anti-depressant medication.

4.4.4 International students

Some challenges, such as paying tuition which is almost times twice that of the home students, adjusting to life in the UK, alongside coping with other doctoral studies challenges, is unique to international students. Challenges Participant Mo relayed:

Basically, I just started to cope with all the situation with the new country, new environment, I'm here with family. Then it started the global pandemic.

*Unfortunately, the (UK) government did not give us any support. So, you cannot live without working – **Mo***

*Like there is loads of student feeling the same...international students are even more worried about finance as there are no support from the government, about the safety of those in their home Country on top of how to go about my research. These are not making things easier- **Fa***

Someone like participant Mo had only been in the UK with his family of four just for three months and was just settling down with the help of his colleagues. While he was trying to settle down with his family (i.e., applying for an NI, DBS certificate, opening a UK bank account, sorting schools out for his children among others), the UK government called for the first lockdown and alas, all his plans had to be on hold. To make the matter worse for him, the income he relied on from his university job in his home country could not continue as they also went into lockdown in his country.

Even though the challenge was from different perspectives, the situation was similar for all participants. For participant Sh, her challenge was on how to deal with writing up her thesis coupled with homeschooling her children as well as worrying that her husband, who was a frontline worker, would contract the disease from work:

*Of course, it was really challenging, especially me being a full-time student and having two children. My husband works full time. So, everything was upside down...- **Sh***

Apart from having to deal with the issue of COVID-19, the excerpt from participant Sh goes to show the challenges faced by women who are making efforts to balance their academic life with their personal life. Similar to participant Sh's situation, Hodgson and Simoni (1995) and Jairam and Kahl (2012) also found that female doctoral students experience more stress and do

not have enough time to engage in social activities due to the other activities they tried to engage in such as managing home, looking after children (if they have one), and being emotionally present for their parents etc. Thus, they tend to rely on intrinsic motivation and perseverance to enable them to complete their studies and this may not often work in their favour (Castro et al., 2011). Thereby, resulting in the high attrition rate Bowen and Rudenstine (2014) lamented to be more present among female doctoral students than their male colleagues.

From an international student perspective, participant Ta added that the challenges faced by doctoral students go beyond the doctoral training, rather it has to do with how to deal with a completely different and new lifestyle. In her words, “*Thinking about problems in our lives as international students.... it's very hard like it's not really the doctorate but it's really the life in the UK*”. By ‘life in the UK’, she was pointing to things like having to make new friends in the UK, dealing with the academic writing style which may be different from what they were used to, and above all having to overcome the barrier of communication that may arise due to the differences in accent etc. No wonder, Laufer and Gorup (2018) maintain that the struggle of an international student goes beyond on-time completion of studies as they had to deal with other factors which may be grouped under Financial Othering, Foreign Othering, Social Othering, and Academic Othering also highlighted in this study. Even the NSF (2015) reported that when compared to their British colleagues, the non-white students have lower attainment of degree due to challenges that are beyond academics.

It should be noted that although the challenges of doctoral students especially those of the international students were grouped under this theme: the impact of the COVID-19 theme, it spans beyond the pandemic. It was grouped here because the data collection stage for this study was during the pandemic and the participants naturally discussed the issues alongside the effect

of the pandemic on them. However, as seen in the existing literature, most of the topics had been in discussion before COVID-19, the pandemic and lockdown had only made it worse.

4.4.5 Positivity around the COVID-19 period

Despite the negative impacts, some students were still able to find some positivity during the COVID-19 pandemic. During a focus group session, participants like Uc and Ch mentioned that although the COVID-19 period was challenging, there were some positive things in between. While participant Uc said it has helped her to write more, participant Ch mentioned that with the lockdown, she was able to have more time with her family:

Obviously, it's not been easy, but looking at my writing and my monthly deadlines, I was able to put down a lot in my writing. So, the pandemic has its own disadvantages, but it also has the good sides as well - Uc

[skipped] I'm actually happier that I'm home with my kids. You know, I'm not at work. I'm on furlough. So, for me, it was a good time I really needed so I'm grateful for it - Ch

Although participant Ch admitted that she was not able to write as much as how participant Uc was doing, she was happy as she was able to spend more time with her children; something she was only able to do during her annual leave. As illustrated by participant Cl, who is a staff member of UWS as well as a part-time doctoral student, the pandemic helped her to feel like part of the doctoral community more since all activities were now being conducted virtually:

....as a part-time PhD, you're not the same as you're in a full-time cohort, I feel very detached. And what's been really interesting, especially during the time of COVID, has been the move to online support.... because it's given me a chance to feel more connected to the PGR community – Cl

Someone like 'CI' would normally not have the time to join activities organised for doctoral students as she would mostly be at work during those times (9 am -5 pm). However, with the pandemic, she was able to schedule her day such that all her work and PhD activities did not interfere with each other and, according to her, by joining these activities, she felt more motivated to engage more in writing her thesis than previously.

From the discussion and analysis above, there is no doubt that COVID-19 led to a lot of instability in people's lives as seen above. Similar to Aucejo et al., (2020) and Sahu (2020) conclusions, the extracts presented here also confirm that the impact of COVID-19 has not been a great one, either on mental health; loneliness or others. Before COVID-19, some studies (see Ali and Kohun, 2007; Cantor, 2019; Levecque et al., 2017) proposed helpful solutions to social isolation among doctoral students such as peer to peer support. With the additional effect of COVID-19, the situation has worsened to the extent those proposed solutions may no longer be sufficient to curb these problems especially among international students (Greener, 2020; THE, 2020).

Apart from confirming the outcome of existing literature, this study is unique in the sense that it identifies that some doctoral students found some positivity in the pandemic/lockdown especially with their ability to write more, reduction in transportation, and being able to spend more time with family (children). Again, supporting another perspective to COVID-19 submitted by Lee et al. (2021) that the lockdown period should not all be seen from the negative aspects of mental depression, anxieties etc because some students were able to put the period to positive use, as seen by some participant here. A report by Lee et al. (2021) was also published with the argument that the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic was not as bad as it is being reported. Thus, when researching this period of students' lives an opportunity should be given for them to reflect on their true experience without a pre-existing conclusion.

4.5 Theme 5: Role of gender in peer relationships

The role of gender reviewed above was around how the concept affected females compared to males especially during COVID-19 while the one under this theme explores how gender influences peer relationships. Even though gender was not included in the objectives of this study, it was reflected in the discussion with the participants both during semi-structured interviews and focus group sessions just like the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. After several contemplations, it was agreed to be included because Jeong et al. (2019) indicated that the role of gender in peer interactions is still limited. Out of the 22 participants for this study, three doctoral participants mentioned that they prefer to seek support from a similar gender; two participants expressed that gender does not matter while the rest of the participants freely use the pronoun ‘he’ or ‘she’ to describe whom they seek support from, which also reflects that they are not particular about gender:

.... I got children so, I have a female friend whose children are same age studying in the same school, so of course, we were at closer level because we were understanding each other talking about children, work and everything.

– **Sh**

Participant Sh mentioned that she was deliberate in choosing whom to have as a close friend for support as she needed someone who was not only married but with children so that this peer would clearly understand her worries around children and know how to support her. Similarly, participant Nt also emphasised that she would rather go to a female student for emotional support as they will understand her the most:

If I need some emotional support, I tend to go to my other two friends because they are female. I mean, If I go to my male friend, he gives me support, but he

*just sometimes doesn't understand the extent of that emotionally feeling like
this – Nt*

She added that although she has male colleagues from whom she seeks academic help (high trust), that is all that she could seek from them. According to her, she can never ask them for emotional support (high distrust) as they might never understand how to help her in that sense. However, with her female colleagues, she could discuss any academic and non-academic issue with them (high trust/low distrust) with the confidence that they would know how to help her the most. Coincidentally, participant Nt was one of those whose relationship was categorised as *special peers*, and this means that the peers in that closed group must all be females because one of the criteria for them becoming her special peers (high trust/low distrust). That is, even if they had all the characteristics she needed, if they were not females, she would not be confident or free enough to share some emotional issues with them. Similar expectations were also stated by the male participants. For example, participant Ik maintained that he would always feel more comfortable seeking support from a male colleague than his female colleagues, '*.... when I'm talking to a guy (male), it is different to when I'm talking to the ladies, you know*'.

However, gender does not seem to matter to some of the participants for this study as participant Ku and participant Ch maintained that they do not mind seeking help or creating a close peer relationship with the opposite gender:

*So, it doesn't matter who it's coming from, it can be a man or a woman. So,
the gender really doesn't matter if you can get a working relationship. It
doesn't matter – Ku*

..... it (gender) doesn't matter for me. So, (we're now) like, brother and sister.

The rest like yeah, female, married, not married. Yeah, I don't choose my

close friends, the command is the energy - Ch

Just as it is hard to determine the actual role of gender from this study, the existing studies on the role of gender on peer relationships are also found to be contradictory. While Jeong et al. (2019) posit that gender does not seem to play a pronounced role in how doctoral students support one another Mouakket (2019) found that students of similar gender types tend to disclose more to each other especially female to female due to the emotional connections they may have just as found with participant Nt and participant Sh.

From the COVID-19 perspective, Cao et al.'s (2020) study found that females were more expressive in terms of the emotions around the pandemic than their male colleagues. However, all the participants of this current study clearly describe the impact of COVID-19 on their wellbeing as well as their doctoral studies. The difference between these two outcomes may be due to the cultural differences that existed between the location of this study (UK) and that of Cao et al. (2020) (China), succinctly described in the revered work of Hofstede (2001) - while people in the UK are encouraged to express their emotions irrespective of gender, expression of emotions is generally considered a form of weakness especially among the male gender in China (Liu, 2014). This could thus explain why Cao et al.'s (2020) findings went in the direction mentioned here.

One aspect of gender role that could not be analysed through the current study was the position of Bowen and Rudenstine (2014) who stated that the attrition rate is higher among women since all the participants of this study were still enrolled as students at the time of the study even though about four participants of them were already thinking about the likelihood of quitting their studies.

4.6 Chapter summary

This chapter addresses part 1 of the conceptual framework by exploring the perception, attitude, and experience of doctoral students on peer relationships. It was found that the types of peers formed depend on the level of trust or distrust between the students. With the inclusion of Lewicki et al's. (1998) model of trust, the findings agree with the concepts presented in the PRF proposed by Kram and Isabella (1985) and adapted by Lee et al. (2017). The study found that although peer relationships are famous for their positive impact (empowering), some students may not feel their effect (trivial) while some could be negatively affected (overwhelming). Also, it found that this is a major determinant of the level of self-disclosure that takes place between these students. The period of COVID-19 had a major negative impact on students' lives even though some students were able to use the period to their advantage. In terms of the role of gender on peer relationships, this chapter revealed that some doctoral students prefer to seek support from similar gender while others do not seem to mind at all.

In the next chapter, the various instant messaging (MIMs) apps used by doctoral students for supporting each other and how trusted these tools are is addressed, while Chapter Six focuses on students' suggestions to the university on how to enhance their peer relationships among its doctoral students.

CHAPTER 5 – FINDINGS: USE OF MIM APPS AND THE INFLUENCE OF TRUST/DISTRUST

This chapter builds on the previous chapter (Chapter four) which explores the concept of peer relationships among doctoral students of UWS. It outlines the different types of MIMs used for peer relationships by doctoral students regarding the few literature available within the education system. The influence of Trust/Distrust on the use of these apps, from the perspective of interpersonal trust and trust on the actual apps, are also examined. Due to the limited literature in this area of research, the current study could only rely on articles conducted on the general concept of trust. Therefore, exploration of this aspect of Trust/Distrust as it relates to the use of MIMs among doctoral students is essential as it will help the university to understand the concept from the perspective of their students. Furthermore, the outcome from here would not only start a new discussion among scholars in this field, but it will also encourage more studies to be conducted on it. Two themes emerged under this chapter and it is represented in the diagram below:

Figure 14: Summary of the main themes for Chapter 5

The final part of the result section is analysed in Chapter Six while Chapter Seven focuses on recommendations and conclusion.

5.1 Theme 1: MIM apps as supporting tool

The participants affirmed that the MIM app is an important tool for their day-to-day activities due to the major role that it plays in connecting them with their supervisors, colleagues, or the wider academic community without having to travel anywhere. This is confirmed by participant Ra below:

I'm here (outside London) but I'm contacting with my supervisor on Skype, I'm contacting my class on WhatsApp, sometimes emails and lately I created a group on my PGR group as well - Ra

Even though she lives outside London, she was able to connect with her networks whenever it was needed. That has not only saved travel costs, but it also spares her sometimes to be able to work on her research as well. She is also able to connect via MIM apps to her supervisor once a month for her progress check instead of having to attend the university face-to-face. Another reason the MIM apps are supporting tools is the ability to help connect peers at any point in time due to its portability as succinctly described by participant Ik:

I think almost everybody has it on their phones. I can't be carrying my laptops. You know, 24 hours going everywhere. I think the phone is so portable. I can easily connect when I'm in the supermarket, or even walking on the road – Ik

Having these apps installed on their phones means that they could respond to enquiries as well as seek help even when they were in the laboratory, library, supermarket, among others. This particular feature was also emphasised in So's (2016) study to be the major difference between MIM apps and desktop IM apps in that the latter could not be moved about due to its size. That means, once away from the desktop or PC location, no matter the urgency of the message, it will have to wait until the student returns to the computer again.

Another reason for accepting the MIM apps as supporting tools is the fact that each of the apps has some functions which are unique to each of them thereby, making them appealing and relevant to different kinds of doctoral students. Participant Fa described this as:

They're really good everyday technology with their own charm. WhatsApp can do what cannot be done by Facebook. Microsoft Teams can accept a group learning, but zoom doesn't have it, but zoom has other options as well. Everything has good and bad – Fa

For example, Zoom does not require registration with a mobile number (Zoom, 2021), when compared to WhatsApp which requires a peer's mobile number before any connection could take place. This feature of Zoom would appeal to doctoral students who are not willing to constantly be in touch with their colleagues, as well as those who want to be able to manage how and when they connect with their peers – most likely information peers. Meanwhile, WhatsApp allows for more intense and longer interactions at no extra cost than being connected to the internet (WhatsApp, 2021). Thus, making it ideal for those who are interested in having a personal connection with their colleagues, as well as a longer conversation – special peers and to an extent, collegial peers. This is because WhatsApp accommodates an unlimited length of conversation for free while Zoom is only free for the first 40 minutes, anything longer than that will incur some form of payment.

These statements from the participants confirm that MIM apps portability makes it relevant for connecting peers with each other anytime and anywhere. It also affirms that each of the apps has unique functions that make it appealing to all kinds of doctoral students. These unique features are discussed in detail in the next section:

5.1.1 Types of MIM apps used for peer relationships

The participants mentioned a few MIMs that they use for communicating during peer relationships. They mentioned platforms such as WhatsApp, Microsoft Teams, Zoom, Email, and rarely WebEx, Gmail meet, and Skype.

5.1.1.1 WhatsApp

Most of the participants were particular about how WhatsApp has been useful for supporting each other. They confirmed its important functions such as speedy response when compared to traditional routes such as emails, and a guarantee of instant messaging due to its accessibility to all doctoral students. They also mentioned its ease of use and wide acceptance, all contributing to its ability to enhance their peer relationships. This position was echoed by all the participants irrespective of the location of the campus.

(i) Easy to use

Apart from the fact that the London campus students were introduced to this MIM app. from the beginning of their doctorate, all participants agreed that it is preferred due to its ease of use as well as its easy installation on their smartphones. Participant Uc and participant Ka emphasised that these characteristics, such as speedy and instant messaging, are the main reasons they prefer WhatsApp,

I think you know WhatsApp is the most accessible and easy to use platform now not only for PhD students, for everybody. You know, even on every side of life – you, your friends, your family - Uc

Always, WhatsApp is the fastest, easiest, doesn't require too much technology to be downloaded. It's something that's easily accessible.” – Ka

To support their position, participant Ta gave a comparison between WhatsApp and the traditional routes of communication such as emails, insisting that WhatsApp is preferred

because its responses are easy and speedy, and most importantly for her, the app. does not require too much data to install or use:

My preferred one is WhatsApp because sometimes, you send a mail and you wait and no answer but WhatsApp, just like that, you'll get a high, speedy response, and it is easy to install – Ta

From these statements, it is believed that the 'ease of use' feature is one of the reasons WhatsApp has remained the MIM app with the most users (2 billion people) in the world as of October 2021, based on the statistics submitted by Statista Research Department (2021b).

(ii) Wide acceptance

In addition to its ease of use, the app is also popular among doctoral students as it is generally an app used for connecting with family and friends outside the university community. This wide acceptance makes it even more convenient to use among the participants for peer relationships. Participants Nt, Kh, and Fa noted that:

...mostly used is WhatsApp because all my peers are using this platform, so it's easier for us to communicate on the platform - Nt

I prefer WhatsApp because it's trending; everyone has it and it's easier to connect no need for ID ...it's also private - Fa

Everyone has it and we find it the most convenient. It's almost taken over from texting. So, I find WhatsApp faster than even texting, I don't think anyone sends messages or texts anymore on their phones. It's all about WhatsApp. – Kh

The wide acceptance can be further confirmed by the understanding that even students from countries where this app is banned (Radcliffe and Bruni, 2019) are likely to install it while in the UK, to connect with their UK doctoral colleagues.

(iii) Enhances interaction

Due to the app's easy accessibility and its wide acceptance among doctoral students, the participants added that they were able to use it for enhancing their interactions with one another. Since the majority of doctoral education is done in isolation, the students often appreciate when they could virtually engage in conversations with their colleagues as a short break from their screen, either individually or as a group. For this purpose, WhatsApp is the first choice to go for, as seen by the excerpt below:

I usually use WhatsApp because it's easier and I can have like a daily conversation and sometimes we use WhatsApp Video, to have a better insight and look at our friends when we haven't met them for a long time. And who you know, to feel better -

Nt

In terms of asking for help from colleagues, I usually use WhatsApp because it's more personal. And it's more direct as well. And I think most people use WhatsApp as well

- Li

WhatsApp helps most because it has group chat. And if I ask one question, I will ask to all of them actually and somebody will help, it makes you feel happier than when you use only emails independently because we really chat all together - **Fa**

Coincidentally, the points made here by the participants were also the key findings by Oyewole Animasahun, and Chapman, (2020) who posit that WhatsApp is preferred among students due to its wide acceptance, and its ability to encourage people to share knowledge. Likewise, the findings in this study also correlated with that of Willemse (2015) and Abiodun et al. (2020) who independently confirmed that students connect with their colleagues via WhatsApp to share their worries which invariably helps to reduce loneliness. From these extracts, it is also believed that WhatsApp helps isolated doctoral students to stay connected with their peers to

encourage and motivate one another. This is especially true for the period between 2020 and 2021 when physical interaction became limited due to the coronavirus pandemic.

During the focus group, there were contrasting opinions among the participants especially the PhD students regarding connecting with peers on WhatsApp. While some doctoral students such as participants Mi and Sh stated that they were open to improving their relationship using the MIM app, participants Ab was sceptical due to the privacy issues that may be involved. An extract from their conversation is seen below:

Mi: *...maybe this thing can add a new element to the friendship and natural conversation stuff so maybe you know, split off into smaller groups like WhatsApp, shared interest or something that'd be quite interesting.*

Ab: *Perhaps if they can be something that can you know, be a replica of that wouldn't necessarily have you given out your numbers probably, maybe routine Skype meeting.*

Sh: *The purpose of this (WhatsApp) group is just to provide the platform for supporting each other, so most of the people I knew, it was from there, it was kind of a motivational feeling of being connected.*

The unifying thing is that these three participants would like to be engaged in peer relationships however, someone like participant Ab would want to be able to control how much conversation he gets involved in. This may be difficult to do once the other peers have your number, and it is, therefore, one of the reasons some participants would not like to engage with their peers via WhatsApp, especially the *information* or *dysfunctional* peers. Despite not being that popular among the PhD students, participant Sh, who has *special* peers, mentioned that she was able to join the WhatsApp group created for cultural/religious purposes and that was how she developed a special bond with three colleagues from that group. The findings from Hill et al.

(2020) and Corpuz (2019), that WhatsApp is a leading MIM app for student-to-student support, is similar to the position of this study especially as revealed among the London campus students. As seen above, some PhD students also find a way to create pockets of WhatsApp groups to support one another, however, this is mostly based on the same ethnicity or cultural group when compared to the DBA students whose purpose is for enhancing peer relationships among the whole cohort.

5.1.1.2 Zoom

The COVID-19 pandemic has led to the popular use of some MIM apps for peer-to-peer support among students, even though some of them have been in existence for a long time. Zoom is a great example of such an app. Despite that it was developed as far back as 2011, it did not become a household name until 2020 when the pandemic started getting more intense across the world. Since some students were already looking forward to apps that would not require any form of registration, Zoom became popular among them. Although not yet the number one choice for engaging in peer relationships as of when this study was conducted, its mention by some students confirms its gradual usage and acceptance among the doctoral students as of June/July 2020, three months to when the first lockdown in the UK was announced:

*So, a major thing really, we use things like **Zoom**, and we use Skype and*

*Microsoft Teams so, we update each other on that. - **Mi***

We chat on WhatsApp, then we send messages to each other.....

*[skipped]we have **Zoom**. Just recently I used Gmail (meet)..... - **Ik***

Anything available, like, if you ask me about you want to contact me on

Zoom**, I'm here, I'm connecting with my supervisor on Skype..... - **Th

As seen in the excerpt above, the participants included Zoom as one of the various platforms they use as MIM apps for supporting each other. However, the other two MIM apps mentioned (Skype meet and Gmail meet) have not received the kind of acceptance received by Zoom as at the time of writing this thesis. Perhaps this is because *Skype meet*, and *Gmail meet*, performs similar functions as the MIM function of Zoom. Only one student confirmed the use of Gmail meet while most participants were just hearing about Skype meet for the first time when it was mentioned to them by the researcher during the interviews. Participant Fa added that they prefer Zoom to other MIM apps such as Teams, or Skype because it does not include the need for their details such as a mobile number.

I prefer zoom because it's easy to operate and it allows for connecting with friends for the purpose of learning during that period only, no further commitment unlike teams or Skype where after that interaction, you could still contact each other again - Fa

In a similar context, Wang et al.'s (2018) investigation on the use of Zoom in a blended synchronous learning environment (BSLE) confirms that students could easily use the MIM app for online learning. Although the participants here have not stated that the app is particularly used for learning, it is confirmed to be used for connecting with other peers for support.

At this point, this study might not be able to predict whether the doctoral students would accept the MIM function of Zoom as one of their main supporting tools in the future when compared to apps such as WhatsApp. However, it can confirm that it will always be a preferred choice for doctoral students who will not want to be too involved with their colleagues as mentioned above.

5.1.1.3 Microsoft Teams

Some participants, especially the PhD students, stated that they prefer the Microsoft Teams for supporting one another. Even though it is a multi-purpose app, the participants' justification for preferring the MIM function of Teams was around security issues, emphasising that they would always prefer the app because it is supported by the university:

.... during the lockdown, the Microsoft Teams was very good. I will prefer it over Zoom because everyone is there and UWS email is used, and oh universities looking into it and it's supported by it – Sh

Participants Sh compared Microsoft Teams with Zoom and insists that she would always prefer the former simply because it is supported by the university. By being supported, she was referring to the fact that the university uses its resources to ensure the app is safe for them to use at all times. Her statement asserts Kristof's (2020) claims that Microsoft Teams is the most recognised platform for online learning by universities and their students. Likewise, upholding Liu et al.'s (2020) conclusion that Microsoft Teams remains one of the most reliable and secured supporting tools for online learning. This then means that Teams is not only popular among the doctoral students concerned with privacy, but it is also preferred when it comes to an interaction between the university and its students especially for online learning. This position refutes the outcome by Serhan (2020) that Zoom and not Teams is widely accepted for the above-mentioned purposes among universities. Perhaps, this disparity is due to the uniqueness of UWS's choice of platform or possibly the geographical differences between the two studies because while the current research was conducted in the UK, Serhan's (2020) research was conducted in the United States where the education system is completely different.

5.1.1.4 Others

The apps here were mentioned once or twice by the participants which must be because it is either not supported by the university or recommended by supervisors/tutors. One of the MIM app not very popular as a supporting tool among doctoral students at the time of this study was Telegram. Although it was beginning to gain popularity among the public, it was not mentioned at all by the students as a supporting tool. This may be because the students would always need more time to learn how these MIM apps work before trusting them for their peer-to-peer interactions.

It is interesting to know that even though emails are not necessarily a MIM app, students who prefer a formal relationship with their colleagues still mentioned the use of their university emails as a supporting tool with one another. Participant Mo has an insightful reason for preferring this means of communication over other platforms. In his words:

I think email is more preferable because email is an instant communication, what you thought to convey with me is what will be recorded. And I can reply on the basis of your needs and emails, so I prefer the email - Mo

This participant maintains that the use of emails ensures original thought is communicated, unlike the other apps where this could be adjusted or deleted thereby distorting original intention/plans. The other platforms mentioned by the participants as a means of peer-to-peer support were Facebook (messenger) and Skype. During the last few decades, Skype and Facebook messenger were at the heart of non-physical communication among everyone including students. To this extent, Baset and Schulzrinne (2004) confirmed that the two apps had boasted to be better than any IM apps available during those times (such as Yahoo IM and MSN). This perception still lingers in the current doctoral students who were students when those apps were at their peak. For example, participant Li (now in his late 30s) still believes that Skype is better for connecting with others especially if it requires a video connection:

But you know, if you want to go for like video chatting internationally, you know we go to

Skype – Li

This is similar to participant Ka's (now in his mid-forties) perception of Facebook. He believes that Facebook messenger is still a major route to accessing peer to peer support from other PhD students from all over the world:

And if you want to ask about information or receive information internationally, of course,

this Facebook is number one. We want to ask about something, you go to the

Facebook group and you ask as they are all PhD students - Ka

While the international connection mentioned by participant Ka remains true just as mentioned by Cheung, Chiu, and Lee (2011) and Dholakia, Bagozzi, and Pearo (2004), as the years pass by, these MIM apps are being replaced by easier and more accessible ones mentioned above when it comes to creating peer relationships. This is not to mean that they have lost their value with the public as Skype is still the preferred method for conducting non-physical interviews (see Krouwel, Jolly, and Greenfield, 2019; Sipes, Roberts, and Mullan, 2019; Teo, Markwardt, and Hinton, 2019) while Facebook still upholds its value for being one of the fastest means of connecting to the global world (Ainin et al., 2015). However, Microsoft Teams and WhatsApp are the two main apps mentioned by the participants of this study for virtually engaging with one another.

The follow-up interviews conducted after the lockdown (March 2021) further helped to affirm the popularity of WhatsApp among the students especially the DBA students. They reiterated that WhatsApp is very popular with them because other MIM apps such as Skype, are not easy to access when compared with WhatsApp thus making them reserve those apps only for the purpose of connecting to others on a formal level such as their supervision while WhatsApp continued to be used for more personal connections:

...we still like communicating on WhatsApp. And on Skype when we have a supervisor meeting.... there's no need to go to, for example, zoom to ask for something. You can just like, text him (on skype) what you want. Then when he has time he will reply. - Ad

During the first interview, participant Mr's reason for using only Microsoft Teams to seek support from her colleagues was because it was the only platform, she was introduced to on joining the university as a PhD student. Her position changed during the follow-up interview (eight months later) as she says she now only uses Microsoft Teams for official purposes while WhatsApp is used to connect with her peers:

.....I have her personal number I reach out on WhatsApp. Nothing is happening on Teams except for meeting with my supervisor. And then when I log on to the power writing app, that's the only time Teams function for me. - Mr

Just as posited by most of the literature, Teams remains the recognised platform in most of the universities, including UWS, for any official interactions, however, as the students develop some kind of peer relationships, they advance their interaction to more easily accessible MIM apps such as WhatsApp. To ensure that the participants' position was not influenced by the lockdown or the pandemic, a follow-up interview was conducted eight months later, and the same conclusion was reached. The new students during the first interview confirmed that she now uses the WhatsApp app to connect with her colleagues on a more personal level, while Teams remains for connecting with her supervisors or with those colleagues who have not shared their contacts with her.

From this study, it is posited that the three most popular MIM apps used as supporting tools among the doctoral students of UWS are WhatsApp, Microsoft Teams and Zoom. However,

when the specific acceptance level of these three MIM apps is compared, it is seen that it might take some time before Zoom is fully accepted among the doctoral students of UWS as a supporting tool. On the other hand, WhatsApp is popular among the London campus (DBA) students and some PhD students while Microsoft Teams is the main app used among the Scottish campuses (PhD) students for peer-to-peer support.

It should, however, be noted that irrespective of the MIM app chosen to engage with peers, the level of interactions that take place between them depends largely on the level of Trust or Distrust present among these peers.

5.2 Theme 2: Role of trust/Distrust in the use of MIM apps as supporting tools

Trust/Distrust plays an important role in how peers engage with one another on MIM apps. As a result, this section is grouped into two: (i) Usage of MIM apps based on interpersonal trust/distrust (ii) Usage of MIM apps based on the platform's trust/distrust. To succinctly analyse this, the four Quadrants of trust model by Lewicki et al. (1998) is adopted.

5.2.1 Interpersonal Trust/Distrust

Although this may sound similar to the concept of trust/distrust analysed in Chapter Four, they are explored from two different perspectives. The concept of trust/distrust in Chapter Four focused on how trust influences who and where to go for peer-to-peer support either via MIM apps or physically, while the one analysed under this section focuses on how interpersonal trust/distrust influences how people engage in peer relationships on MIM apps.

The participants under interpersonal trust/distrust are more concerned about the person they will be interacting with through the MIM apps than the trust/distrust they have for the platforms. That means, they will be willing to engage in self-disclosure if they have a high

trust/low distrust for the person but if their feelings are opposite, then, they are not likely to get involved at all. These concepts are analysed in detail below.

i) High Trust/Low Distrust

This is based on Quadrant 2 of the Lewicki et al. (1998) trust model (see Table 3) where the participants have a high level of trust and a low level of distrust for the peers that they engage with via the MIM apps. These doctoral students are willing to invest their time and other commitments to using these apps for peer relationships however they have the hope of positive expectations in return. As emphasised by Lewicki et al. (1998), a low level of distrust does not mean no distrust; rather, it means these doctoral students would still have a little bit of caution with using these apps. For example, participants Nt, Mi, and Kh stated that they were always happy to use these platforms for communicating with their peers as well as sharing information and documents that may be useful to these peers. This includes even sharing some parts of their research work. However, they pointed out that these colleagues would have to be someone they have a high level of trust for such as their special peers, or collegial peers to an extent:

It's just about who I'm talking to. So, if I have a very sensitive problem that I want to discuss, I wouldn't go to just anyone. I will go to my friends who I really trust because I know that they wouldn't stab me from the back or steal my idea – Nt

I think it depends really on the person and how close the relationship is for me; you would hopefully trust a person enough that they wouldn't sort of plagiarise your work – Mi

I think they're always you know privacy issues regarding this, but I think for me, it would be that I trust the person more and if I trust the person, I think I'll share the (sensitive) information – Kh

It is not surprising that some of the participants here accept that they could share sensitive information with their peers as they were the same group of students that identified with either *special* or *collegial* peers as analysed in Chapter Four. Participant Nt, for example, was categorised under *special peers* which means that she has been able to develop a strong bond with some of her doctoral colleagues to the extent she is able to have an intense self-disclosure with this person(s).

Similarly, participant Mi and participant Kh were willing to share part of their doctorate work as they would have built the needed confidence that the peer will not plagiarise their work. Therefore, this study posits that the use of MIM apps for supporting each other cannot happen in one day; the peers would have had several interactions which will then convince the trustor that it is worthy to be vulnerable with the information being sent to the receiver (Mayer et al., 1995).

ii) Low Trust/High Distrust

These groups of doctoral students also rely on interpersonal trust/distrust as described above. They are of the opinion that they can only engage in peer relationships on the MIM apps at a general level, with the mindset of never sharing any sensitive documents with peers on the platform. They are categorised under Quadrants 3 of Lewicki et al.'s model because they are always suspicious of what their colleagues might do with the information shared with them on these platforms. Extracts that explain their position is below:

Well, I don't think I would share such things. If I would help my colleagues, I would recommend some articles. I will help only in a way that we sit together, you can read it, but I would not share my introduction or my abstract by WhatsApp or email, I wouldn't do it - Ni

I think as doctoral students once you share your work with somebody else, it could even be your family member, it reduces the originality.... and part of the criterion for each work that you do goes down to originality at the end of the day – Ab

For this group of people, the main reason for being on the MIM apps is because it is recommended by their supervisor/tutor, not because they want to be able to interact on a personal level with their peers. Therefore, they would only get involved in the conversation briefly without being close to anyone to the extent of having an in-depth conversation or sharing sensitive information with them via these platforms. Participant Ni gave an instant of her doctoral work, and she maintains that she would never be able to share this with any of her colleagues although she could support a peer by suggesting articles or showing her academic work to them if that would help their studies. From a similar point of view, participant Ab insisted that sharing a doctoral work that has not been published is not wise as the other person may be tempted to fabricate, falsify, or even plagiarise the work just as warned by Singh (2012). Both participants' position here represents either *information* peer but, most likely found among *dysfunctional* peers - those who engage with their peers on a general level or with negative feelings respectively. To show the consistency in participants' opinions, participant Ab was one of the students who perceive peer relationships as overwhelming thus it is not surprising that he has a high level of distrust for his colleagues when it comes to sharing confidential documents via the MIM apps. Just as the analysis of *information* peers stated, these participants are willing to engage their colleagues on these platforms but would not share sensitive data such as personal information or any part of their academic work.

One of the participants whose type of peer assigned to her in Chapter Four almost contradicted her perception about the use of MIM apps as supporting tools is participant Sh:

I always prefer to use my school ID, email ID if I need to ask or send any documents to my friends. Other than that, I'm not a person who would be happy to share things. I'm always worried I would not share my children's photos on Facebook. Even with this (university)

Security, I don't feel comfortable with it - Sh

As seen above, despite having *special* peers, she noted that she prefers to use her student email to provide or seek support from her peers, especially when it involves sharing confidential information. This fits well with Kramer's (1994) suggestions that some people just have a high level of distrust in others and, no matter what, they will always have a suspicion, doubt, and concerns about things. When probed further on how she engages her special peers, she clarified that she does this through face-to-face meetings or phone calls. In her words, *'these three people (special peers), we meet to have a group session to feel like oh we are all together, and we are still connected, to get a feeling of boosting up and getting into work'*. This interprets to mean that the type of interpersonal trust/distrust doctoral students have for their peers does not necessarily align with the type of interpersonal trust/distrust found among them when it comes to the use of MIM apps. Again, confirming that these two aspects of trust/distrust (the one analysed in Chapter Four and the one analysed under this chapter), must be addressed separately. Another person with a relatively similar perception to participant Sh is participant Ku. She confirmed that even though she has *special* peers, some issues are not to be discussed with peers:

...it's about you know; you talk to different people about different problems.

So, for my financial problems, you know, I mainly discuss them with my

family, so I think that is the thing with me. – Ku

According to her, her financial issues are meant to be discussed with her parents and not a colleague. This is possibly because she believes the only person who should know about this

aspect of her life is her financial sponsors who are her parents. Thus, seeing the sharing of such issues with even her special peers as a waste of time.

From this section, it could be seen that while some participants would engage in in-depth peer relationships on the MIM apps, based on the high level of interpersonal trust, some would only be involved in a general conversation on these platforms due to the high level of interpersonal distrust they have in their peers when using those platforms.

5.2.2 Trust/Distrust based on the actual MIM apps

While some participants are of the opinion that their engagement with peers via MIM apps would be dependent on the level of interpersonal trust/distrust as analysed above, the peers under this section rely on the trust/distrust they have for the platform itself.

iii) High Trust/High Distrust

The participants here are grouped under Quadrant 4 of Lewicki et al. (1998) trust model. This is because even though they would have a good level of engagement with their peers using the MIM apps (high trust), they have a concern that the owners of the platforms could engage in a data breach, or there may be technical problems during the MIM apps' usage (high distrust). Participant Ta expressed her concerns as shown below:

I don't like to share my personal details on any platforms, because platforms can be hacked, and can be dismissed..... even though we can trust the person but it's still a machine, we cannot really trust them (MIM apps) so much- Ta

For this participant, it is a case of not even trusting that these MIM platforms would not breach the confidentiality agreement to give private information away to third parties. For instance, Facebook was sanctioned in 2018 for using people's data without their permission (Isaak and Hanna, 2018). History almost repeated itself in 2021 when the same company updated its

WhatsApp terms and conditions for a so-called marketing strategy (this was later reversed) (Irish Times, 2021). These separate acts further reduced the trust people have in them and made the level of distrust increase exponentially. The assertion here reflects in the increase in number of people seeking more secure alternatives to these apps (i.e., Telegram) around that time (Irish Times, 2021). Participant Ta also acknowledged that MIM apps are just machines, and they could shut down at any time. Her worries were verified about 15 months later when the three of the major MIM apps used for peer-to-peer support - WhatsApp, Facebook messenger, and Instagram (Statista Research Department (2021b)) crashed. For at least 6 hours on the 4th October 2021 (Downdetector, 2021), these three apps were unavailable, disrupting the communication of their users who are in their billions. Participant Ta's level of distrust for these apps was also supported by participant Kh:

And definitely, there are always technical issues with these platforms. Sometimes you can't see the other person, sometimes you can't hear their voice – Kh

What makes the technical issues even more challenging is its unpredictable nature especially since its connection effectiveness relies on the internet network that the apps are connected to. This is especially true when using the video call function as this requires more signal strength than other forms of interactions on the platform (Taylor et al., 2015). For example, a student who lived on one of the university campuses has been having a text conversation with one of his busy senior colleagues on the conceptual framework he has been stuck with for weeks. For more clarifications, this senior colleague agreed to help him via a video call meeting and alas, the call kept reconnecting to the extent they had to reschedule to another time in the future. Even though these students believe that these apps would help them engage in peer relationships, the unpredictable nature is what makes them have a high level of distrust in the use of MIM apps as supporting tools.

(iv) Low Trust/ Low Distrust

These participants are categorised under Quadrant 1 of the trust model by Lewicki et al. (1998), because to them, it is not really about the level of trust or distrust for the individual or the apps, but about their preferences. This group of doctoral students do not have any negative opinions about using MIM apps for engaging in peer relationships, neither do they have many positive things to say about them. However, they clearly stated that online engagement with peers is not equivalent to physical support for them. They provided a number of factors that informed their decision, and they are presented below:

I definitely think this (online interaction) is tiredness, sometimes, it is quite difficult to sit for such long periods of time off, and in one position and things. – Mi

According to participant Mi, the online interaction forces him to sit in one position for a long time and he gets tired of this as he is one person that gets uncomfortable with sitting at a spot for a long time. Perhaps, this is due to his scientific nature where he spends most of his time investigating facts through experimentation and other hands-on methods. The other reasons mentioned by these participants include body language, clarity of intentions among other factors. Participant Uc and Ik's opinions about this is provided in the excerpts below:

I prefer to speak with someone face to face. I will understand more what the person is trying to say, what image you're trying to portray rather than on the phone or on the video call. – Uc

I really used to love seeing my supervisors when I was on the campus, he might just be passing through the corridor. And say, hey, there's something I just want you to look at briefly. Less than two minutes, you know, Done, and then we're off – Ik

For example, when all student support was moved online, aside from the technical challenges, many non-UK students who had just moved into the country struggled with

understanding the accent of their tutors and that of the home students. This may have contributed to the reason these international students might not join most of the online events as they would prefer to be absent than sit in the session for about an hour or more without understanding one thing that is being discussed. This is what Laufer and Gorup (2018) describe as 'Cultural Othering' where the student's interactions with their new environment are influenced by the differences in culture. Participant Uc thinks that a face-to-face peer relationship would make her understand the true intentions of her colleague when compared with that of the online platforms. One of the prominent scholars who wrote about not understanding true intentions on online platforms is Toma et al. (2019). He said that it might almost be impossible to detect the truth or lies in what people say when communicating via online platforms because everyone is writing from behind the screen where true emotions or body language is difficult to be detected.

The various positions of the participants in this low trust/low distrust section were made based on their general experience with online interactions (before, during and after the COVID-19 pandemic). However, all participants understood that they needed to adjust to the new normal of using online peer to peer support after the lockdown in 2020/2021. Moreover, there was no other choice for students at that time as argued by Aucejo et al. (2020) that students and universities needed to adapt to the rules proposed by the government at that time.

The overall perception from this study is that there will always be some level of caution when using the MIM apps to engage in peer relationships. As presented by Bandyopadhyay and Mehta's (2017) and Greene's (2020) studies, it is normal for people to be cautious when using these apps due to issues such as invasion of privacy, use of personal data without proper informed consent, among other reasons. However, what makes one doctoral student different from the other is the level of their interpersonal trust/distrust or the level of their trust/distrust

for the app itself. Gretry et al. (2017) noted that the level of self-disclosure with one another is dependent on the level of trust/distrust that exists among doctoral students.

5.3 Chapter summary

This chapter focused on understanding the various MIMs used by doctoral students for supporting each other. It found that MIM apps such as WhatsApp, Microsoft teams, and Zoom are famous among UWS doctoral students for engaging in peer relationships while other platforms such as Skype, emails, and Facebook are also in use but not very popular for peer relationships. Zoom and Teams were some of the MIMs that became popular among doctoral students during the COVID-19 pandemic. Microsoft Teams was the most popular online platform used among the Scottish campus especially the PhD students for engaging with peers while WhatsApp was widely used among their London campus (DBA) colleagues for the same purpose.

There was also an exploration of how trust influences the kind of support the UWS doctoral students seek from their peers. The findings from this chapter show that the level of interpersonal trust/distrust is a determinant of how some doctoral students engage with their peers on MIM apps. The others base the level of the support that they seek or provide on these platforms on how much they trust/distrust the app itself. These findings are important as it helps to identify the key MIM apps used by the UWS doctoral students for engaging in peer relationships. Also, it emphasises the role of trust/distrust in how these students use the MIM apps as supporting tools.

The next chapter – Chapter Six, which is the result chapter, focuses on the various recommendations given by the UWS doctoral students on how to enhance peer relationships among them. This will then be followed by the recommendation and conclusion chapter (Chapter Seven).

CHAPTER 6 – FINDINGS: GUIDELINES FOR ENHANCING PEER RELATIONSHIPS

This is the last of the three result and analysis chapters. The previous two chapters covered the concept of peer relationships among the UWS doctoral students and the various MIMs used by these students alongside the role of trust during their usage. This chapter addresses the various suggestions given by doctoral students on how the university could enhance peer relationships among them. To achieve this, the participants were asked for suggestions either based on past or present university activities that they found interesting or new ideas they thought would be useful.

It is important to have these guidelines coming directly from the doctoral students as this would help the university understand how best to enhance this type of student support, which is the primary purpose of this study. Under this chapter, two themes emerged and are in the diagram below.

Figure 15: Summary of the main themes for Chapter 6

6.1 Theme 1: Past and present peer relationships activities

There are some past activities the doctoral students wish could be returned by the university, and there are some ongoing ones the students hope will continue as they help them to connect with their peers for peer relationships. These activities are examined in detail in the sections below:

6.1.1 Past activities

The participants mentioned some of the past activities that they wish could be re-introduced due to the important role they played in peer relationships. Participant Di and participant Ra mentioned some peer learning activities that the supervisor used to organise in the past at the London campus and the Scottish campuses respectively:

Teach meet, basically, was in Paisley campus (Scotland) and was about peer learning. So, they (doctoral students) would meet every month and then they would learn from each other. You know, whoever is good with one thing they would support other PGRs, and so on. - Ra

*In the first year, every week, there used to be two classes and one extra day which was called the **Action learning group**. So, it was to develop an environment where a student can work and support each other to grow.*

And I don't know, for some reason, it was taken off - Di

Even though participant Ra was a London campus student, she heard about the *teach meet* programme from her friends on the Scottish campus. The programme, which used to be coordinated on the main campus - Paisley, was, according to her, a useful scheme for supporting students' learning. She added that the senior doctoral students who participated in the activity at that time had told her how helpful the programme was towards their doctoral journey especially with finding the motivation to start writing up their project (Lee et al.,

2017; Laidlaw et al., 2016). She said she was disappointed to hear that it would no longer be available as she would have also gained some knowledge from it through her Scottish campus peers. Similarly, participant Di, who had just completed his doctoral study, added that he benefited from the *Action learning group*, and he was disappointed to hear that the programme would not be available to the newly enrolled students of that time, as it was cancelled before his final year at the university. He lamented that the study group was a great opportunity for his type of person who does not like to associate with peers on an informal level. This is because the learning group allows them to teach and learn from each other irrespective of their level of peer relationships (he was categorised under *information* peers in Chapter Four). These two participants (participant Ra and participant Di) could not place the reason why those peer learning activities were taken off because, according to them, it would have been one of the key approaches for students to have improved their research skills by learning from other peers. These forms of activities suit the description of peer learning provided in this study as well as by scholars such as Boud et al. (2014) and Meschitti (2019) since they involve doctoral students learning academically from each other. As expressed by the participants, if these activities were returned (post-pandemic of course), it would serve as a motivating factor for students to want to learn from each other to improve their academic capabilities. Part of the main findings from Meschitti (2019) was that the process of peer learning improves the diversity of knowledge among peers as the participants are likely to bring on board different areas of expertise. Hence, making it easier for peers to seek and receive informal support on areas that are unclear to them, as well as gain enough confidence to want to continue their research independently. From another perspective, this process is a good way for increasing socialisation among doctoral students and invariably, reduce loneliness (Cantor, 2020). All these invariably enhance the timely completion of the study.

Based on the position above, it is believed that the re-introduction of the activities mentioned by these doctoral students would help to enhance their peer relationship and specifically, improve the students' research skills, boost their morals, and reduce loneliness through socialisation

6.1.2 Current activities

The participants mentioned some key activities that the university currently manages and confirm that this has not only helped in connecting them with other peers but also improved their academic progression. One of the events is the Acwri, available through Microsoft Teams. This is a group event where UWS doctoral students are invited to an hour-long session to draw, jot, or write something down on their thesis. As reflected by participant Mr:

*... I belong to the **Acwri writing group** that's just a new one I joined online, in fact, I had my first session two days ago. And it was quite helpful and everybody there is... from different parts of the world. And the group is flowing, well, I like the support I get from the group as well – Mr*

Someone like participant Mr, who had to combine her study with looking after her children, emphasised how helpful the Acwri writing group has been for her. She narrated that the one-hour session was the only guaranteed time of her day dedicated to writing her dissertation. Therefore, there was no doubt that the activity has been helping her make steady progress with her dissertation.

The only setback of this event is that it is only popular among doctoral students from the Scottish campuses (PhD students). This setback became more obvious during the focus group sessions when this part of the study was discussed. While the Scottish campus students were giving suggestions around the event, the lost expression on the London campus students revealed that they do not know about any of these programmes possibly due to the difference

in the geographical location. This reason might not seem acceptable since these events have always been conducted virtually via Teams, and one of the advantages of MIM apps is the ability to connect anytime from anywhere (Quay-de la Vallee et al., 2016). Nonetheless, the London campus (DBA) students all expressed that they look forward to joining the programmes mentioned by their PhD colleagues. If these events are also well spread among the London campus doctoral students, it will be a good way to connect a wider range of doctoral students thereby, reducing the issue of loneliness or isolation as commonly found among these students. Apart from Acwri, the participants (from Scottish campuses) also mentioned some other events organised by the university for enhancing peer to peer relationships. However, they expressed their concern that this became overwhelming and distracting for them as they were receiving too many updates about these activities. They added that although the information sent may be useful when it becomes too much, it gets irritable:

I went to something like a coffee break. But I mean, it was a bit kind of hard to speak, it still felt quite formal, it was hard to introduce yourself and you can't really break off into smaller groups – Mi

There is one that was initiated last year,[skipped], like an open source, you know, a discussion where anybody can talk about anything but even for someone like me, the emails just keep coming all the time. I don't actually check it because there are too many people talking. – Ab

As participants Mi and Ab have stated here - although they would always want to be engaged with peers through these activities, at the same time, being *collegial* or *information* type of peer (as analysed in Chapter Four) means that they would like to regulate how and when they receive updates about the events. Otherwise, it discourages them to the extent that they just delete or ignore any incoming messages from that platform no matter how relevant it is. It can, therefore,

be argued that as much as some doctoral students would like to be involved in peer relationships activities, they will like some control over their level of involvement.

Similar to the efforts by the university on establishing different peer relationships activities, doctoral students also set up platforms for supporting one another. An example is the peer reflection forum created by one of the participants of this study - participant Ra:

Peer reflection forum. It's basically whoever is good in academic writing, they can help the rest, you know, arrange a webinar or workshop, like a very informal one and share their resources, share their experience with others –

Ra

Through this virtual platform, doctoral students were able to post things like requesting a good book on methodology or sharing information such as ‘how to pass your Viva with ease’ and organising trips for smaller groups. Since its creation in 2019, the forum had been of great use to many doctoral students as this was confirmed from how engaged students were with this platform. On many occasions, students who engage with this platform go on to interact with one another on a personal level, thereby creating a positive form of peer relationships outside of the online platform.

The current study also benefits from the forum as most of the participants recruited for the project were through this platform, reiterating the importance of having a platform where students could either seek or provide help to one another. The likes of (Laidlaw et al., 2016; Lindsay, 2015; Wolff et al., 2013) have been serious advocates of platforms such as this, due to its less pressured, informal, nature, and, most importantly, its ability to enhance on-time completion of studies among doctoral students.

From the analysis, this study proposes two ideas. Firstly, the university should continue to provide the current activities mentioned above. However, the notifications about these events

should be done in moderation so that it does not become irritable to some groups of students. Secondly, these activities should be introduced to all doctoral students irrespective of their campuses so that some groups of students do not feel neglected. Again, the findings in this study reiterate the fact that these activities help to increase socialisation among the students therefore, an early introduction of all UWS doctoral students to these types of platforms would help in improving their doctoral journey.

6.2 Theme 2: New suggestions for enhancing peer relationships

Having examined the past and current activities stated by the doctoral students to be relevant for enhancing peer relationships, the participants went on to give opinions on how the university could further help. These are examined under the sub-themes below.

6.2.1 Hiring a fellow doctoral student to manage doctoral activities

The participants suggested hiring one of the current UWS doctoral students to take up the role of connecting students with one other as a way of formalising the support of the university. This person could probably be called the doctoral student ambassador. In addition, there could be one volunteer representative from each of the schools to assist the hired ambassador in carrying out this task. Participant Th summarised his opinion as seen below:

..... I would just suggest a group of students, I'm not talking about the students' union. I'm talking about a group of students who will be responsible for communicating with all the cohorts. Someone who is like connecting, we are missing the connection – Th

Having fellow doctoral students and not university officials manage the activities will ensure that the students do not feel like they are being assessed and they would always be free to seek help from these assigned students (Laidlaw et al., 2016; Wolff et al., 2013). Therefore, serving as a reminder that the support is by them and for them. Also, having someone assigned to the

role ensures that a specific person is held responsible for managing that unique aspect of doctoral education. Invariably, this will help new students know that there is a designated person to go to when seeking information and guidance as they settle into the new academic environment. This would prevent the kind of situation experienced by participant Mr when she newly started her PhD, two months before the first interview:

.... I've told everybody, please anybody you know, who is doing a PhD in Law, just let me know, I'm not even so particular about my level right now... but unfortunately, I haven't come across anyone. I don't know if it's because I am not reaching out the way I should. So, I don't know, I'm not really getting it as I was hoping for more support really, since this is just my beginning, my first year. I'm not really happy” - Mr

It is seen here that participant Mr felt lonely and confused after having to deal with one of the most crucial times in the transition period of an international student. This is because she is not only new to the people around her, but she would also need help with crucial things such as renting an apartment, knowing about transportation among others. The university currently has a unit assigned to help with this, but as maintained in previous chapters, students are more comfortable with supports provided by their peers than someone from the university authority. Therefore, the suggestion of having a fellow doctoral student manage these activities is crucial especially for helping the new students (especially the international ones) settle in, appropriately. This idea was also supported by participant Cl, who doubles as a UWS staff member and a part-time doctoral student. She emphasised the need to formalise all the pockets of activities ongoing at the university with a reminder that university staff should not be too involved as doctoral students would feel uncomfortable as soon as a member of staff becomes part of the activities:

Yes, we could formalise it more by actually training our existing PhD cohorts to provide this level of peer-to-peer support, instead of it being done on an informal basis. And I think there's definitely more that we could be doing on a campus-by-campus basis. And especially for the London campus, which is such a strong cohort of doctoral research students. - CI

Putting this into context, the participants admitted that the events being organised by the university are a great way for enhancing peer relationships among doctoral students, however, the institution needed to appoint one of them to help in keeping in touch with colleagues across all campuses and organising events based on the students' needs.

6.2.2 Creating an enabling environment for formal interaction and knowledge exchange

The participants believe that having an enabling environment will help create an avenue for interactions among students and possibly learning from each other. For participants such as Ch, visitation to places outside of the university as a group would go a long way to enhance her interaction with her colleagues. Examples of these types of places include art locations, museums, or even attending conferences together:

It depends on the subject as well, but I still think that if we're doing DBA, we could have probably gone together to visit a museum, to see a conference together. So, I think we needed more of the day outside, the group activities outside of the university, external activities – Ch

For this participant, organised visitation to places like these would help doctoral students interact more with one another thereby, enhancing their peer relationships. This, in a way, would encourage them to want to connect on a more personal level. Another participant -

participant Sa suggested having a student room where doctoral students with a similar project could meet to brainstorm on their work together to improve their research or writing ability:

They can create student rooms, something like people who are researching on leadership things can go in there and share their ideas, knowledge with each other- Sa

Having a student room dedicated to doctoral students is a great way for enhancing peer relationships but, this would only benefit those peers that are willing to work with their colleagues - special and collegial peers. In consideration of the other groups of peers - information and dysfunctional peers, these study rooms could be made bookable through the university library system as they may like to engage with their research work alone within the university

From a different perspective, participant Nt suggested that partaking in inter-university conferences or get-togethers would also help to set the scene for not only connecting to immediate colleagues but also colleagues from outside the university. According to her,

It will be nice if doctoral students from other universities can have a platform to meet up or to discuss things or just to exchange thoughts. Sometimes it's good to get insight from other people - Nt.

The adoption of this suggestion would not only enhance the doctoral student's knowledge but also increase their level of exposure to doctoral students outside of UWS (Meschitti and Carassa, 2014). This would also encourage the UWS doctoral students to be familiar with their Community of Practice (CoP) which according to Wenger (2011) would only take place when the people involved interact and learn together. Having a community such as this would go a long way to meet the needs of a larger population of doctoral students irrespective of where their campus is located.

6.2.3 Informal interaction among all doctoral students across the five campuses

The London Campus participants (DBA students) were particular about this as they were hoping to have more events that would enable them to interact more with their Scottish campuses' colleagues. Participant Ch expressed that there should be activities that would connect them with the student in the remaining four campuses located in Scotland:

We feel like sometimes in the London campus, we are just a little bit far away from the university (main campus). If I tomorrow meet someone from Paisley, we're not going to have the same discussion, it could be really helpful if the university manage to do this – Ch

We (London Campus DBA students), with the University, are like Island now. So, we need to build bridges, not only inside the university but outside to the others – Th

The idea of organising more informal activities came up when suggestions based on the current activities provided by the universities were being made, and the London campus students could not give one example, as stated earlier. Based on this, the doctoral students gave examples provided in the focus group excerpts provided below:

Mr: We could have like a group connection, we could have like a sit out or hangout, maybe once in a month, or twice in a month just connecting, all the doctoral students, connect on this level.

Ad: Yeah, I think I would appreciate it if they could organise group discussions about things like recent news or actualities...

However, care must be taken in providing too many informal activities since part of the doctoral journey is about becoming an independent researcher/academic so staff should not be too involved in the journey outside of the academic part. Also, some doctoral students might not be interested in these kinds of activities due to other things going on for them at that time. For example, participant Kh, a DBA student, stated that engaging in university-related activities such as class group presentations might be enough to encourage interactions among peers because too many social activities would not work for her:

I think group projects, group presentations, a little bit of group time together, making people sit together and bouncing ideas to go with each other is enough... I don't believe that too many social occasions are going to kind of bond you, at least I don't think it will upon me. – Kh

The position of participant Kh might be influenced by many factors. Number one is the fact that she was a working (part-time), married woman with children. This means that apart from what is directly important to her doctoral work, she might not be willing to take part in any extra-curricular activities as she would rather spend that time on other important commitments. These other commitments might be one of the major influences on her level of interactions with her colleagues (she was grouped under information peers in Chapter Four). Referencing the literature reveals that participants Kh's situation has been analysed by Bowen and Rudenstine (2014) and Jairam and Kahl (2012) to be the major challenge of a female doctoral student and was one of the main reasons for having higher dropout rates among the females than their male colleagues. Therefore, it is important to balance the views of these students before embarking on any social activities to prevent a low turn-out at such events. This point is further confirmed when the participants gave examples of online engagements when they were asked for the kinds of support, they would attend the most. For example, participant Mi suggested having a

WhatsApp group where interested doctoral students could join to chat about different informal things, emphasising that engaging through forums are outdated:

I think if you had something that was easy to use, like WhatsApp, or more groups that are more informal, and people can just ask questions. Kind of forum things are a bit more outdated and you kind of get lost, really, so maybe organising WhatsApp groups and things - Mi

The participants' suggestions indicate that they wish to have that sense of community with other peers during their doctoral journey where they would be able to express their concerns as well as their successes with their colleagues. They want to be able to connect, communicate, and show care towards their fellow peers at any time but on the condition that it is flexible. Just as mentioned by participant Mi, WhatsApp is one of the popular MIM apps today that would enhance that intimate level of interaction among doctoral students; a position that was also attested to by the likes of Abiodun et al. (2020) and Oyewole et al (2020). However, as stated by participants Mi, these participants would like to be the determinants of their entry and exit times into these platforms. As an alternative for those students that may not want to get too personal with their colleagues, Microsoft Teams could be considered for these kinds of online interactions as this is also known for helping to build a sense of community (Radha et al., 2020). Moreover, in terms of security, Teams is currently being supported by the university. Based on the excerpts above, interactions on these platforms would help develop a relationship, therefore creating an avenue for students to approach one another for support. Without these interactions and an established peer relationship, there is no assurance that the students would want to interact with other students whom participant Th referred to as strangers. According to him, ‘.... *If I don't know anyone of them, how can I share my problems, you know, it's not logical*’.

From the comments above, it is posited that organising informal events tagged with coined names such as ‘Lunch Together’, ‘Teatime’, ‘Knowing More About You’ would be a great way for the university to encourage peer relationships among doctoral students who have consistently expressed that they would like a platform that encourages regular interactions with their peers.

6.2.4 More organised and precise formal support from the university

Here, the participants (especially the Scottish campus students) identified with the fact that the university regularly makes efforts to enhance peer to peer support however, according to them, this requires more coherence. Participants Ra and Mi suggestions on how to ensure more organised support included having access to online learning on research skills as early as a student resumes for a doctorate:

.... maybe a more structured series of courses on methodology or things like that, you could even get like a certificate or some form of qualification to say that you attended - Mi

If we are introduced to the supporting material provided on Moodle right in the beginning, that would motivate students to spend some time on that and then they would realise how important it is. I'm not denying the importance of all the taught modules but it's literally of no help when it comes to writing the thesis – Ra

According to them, online learning should include key areas such as ‘methodology’ among other research essentials as this would encourage having a common academic point to discuss when interacting with one another. Participant Mi added that the issuance of an electronic certificate could encourage more students to participate in the training even though it would be voluntary. In addition, being a synchronised form of learning means that all students would be

able to have access to it irrespective of their location. This flexibility is one of the advantages of including the latter in a programme of study as they will be able to learn the course at their own pace with no pressure from anyone (Alshammari, Parkes, and Adlington, 2017). In addition to this, there could be a comment section under these online training where students could also comment and know more about one another. It is believed that this would not only help increase the students' research knowledge, but it will also enhance their confidence to want to engage with their study independently as well as gradually introduce them to their academic community.

6.2.5 Encouraging peer mentoring between 'senior' and 'junior' doctoral students

Under this subheading, the participants emphasised how useful it would be to have a peer mentoring scheme where a more experienced student is able to guide the new students during and even possibly after, their doctorate. They gave suggestions on how the university could make this a reality. Participant Ta suggested having a list of senior students available to junior students through their departments so that they know whom to go to whenever they need help. Below is an extract describing participant Ta's position on the idea of peer mentoring:

So, the university could do one thing like... don't give their (senior students) personal details, but at least give their names and email addresses on the board. For me, I never knew which person to approach but like I am doing bilingual education research. If someone approached me about interest or anything, I would be happy to actually respond – Ta

The idea proposed by participant Ta would help guide students in the right direction around their studies and their overall doctoral experience. However, it is important to ensure that only the senior students that are interested partake in the scheme. This is because some senior

doctoral students may not like to be involved in such schemes due to many factors described in the earlier chapters of this study. Another doctoral student, participant Nt gave a more time-bound suggestion to the approach.

In Indonesia, we have this peer mentoring. So, students who are in year three must be a mentor for the new student for six months, I guess. So, students on your cohort must be a mentor for students in year one and it's really important for me as a new student who doesn't know anything – Nt

This participant believes some doctoral students in later years of study could help others by dedicating at least six months of their time towards peer-mentoring others. In this case, the mentees will be able to access the mentor for support regarding different forms of their needs, be it academic or non-academic issues. This means that the 'senior' must fully consent to the idea, and the mentee would have to ensure he or she does not overwhelm the senior at any time.

Irrespective of the approach taken, peer mentoring is an important form of peer relationships that does not only improve students' sense of belonging but also helps to enhance the wellbeing of the mentor and the mentee. The work of Collings et al. (2016) and that of Lee et al. (2017) are among the studies that emphasised the role of peer mentoring in both peers' mental well-being, satisfaction, and improved academic achievement. Terrion and Leonard (2007), one of the earliest scholars to have adapted Kram and Isabella's (1985) framework to students' lifestyle, also confirmed that truly peer mentoring leads to psychosocial improvement of students. Therefore, UWS would be able to increase the overall well-being of its doctoral students by adopting this idea of enhancing peer relationships, a goal that is at the forefront of the university's agenda for all students enrolled at the institution (UWS, 2021).

The data presented here confirm that engaging in peer mentoring is a great way to enhance peer relationships among doctoral students. However, it must be done with the mutual agreement of

the students acting as the mentors so as not to become the ‘overwhelming’ type of peer (described in Chapter 4). From the perspective of self-disclosure and trust, it is important to ensure that the students involved are interested in working together, otherwise, the whole process might become a waste of time for the students involved.

6.2.6 Reviewing the existing supervisory arrangement

There is no way peer relationships for doctoral students will be discussed without mentioning supervisory support due to the unique role it plays in their doctoral studies (Lindsay, 2015). However, literature has confirmed that as much as this role could be a great achievement for the parties involved, it could also lead to anxiety and exhaustion among the supervisors (Elliot and Kobayashi, 2019). This is because, in addition to these roles, the supervisors also have other university duties to fulfil (González-Ocampo, and Castelló, 2019). The excerpt from participant Ku below confirms the expectations of a doctoral student and the reality of their supervisor:

And to get him on call is also difficult. When I asked him earlier, he just told me straight away that, you know I'm only allowed to devote certain amount of time to the student...that's what he told me – Ku

From this conversation, it could be seen that participant Ku expects more than she is getting from her supervisor, while the supervisor is possibly frustrated about the fact that the doctoral student does not understand that she is only allocated limited time per week/month. Even though this is a challenge that would need to be sorted by the university management, the participants gave their opinions on how to reduce the supervisory exhaustion of supervisors. Participant Ra suggested that:

I think if like the number of students under each supervisor's group is reduced then they are able to read what we send to them, and they are able to listen to us- Ra

From the extract above, participant Ra believes that reducing the number of students under each supervisor might enable them to have more time to attend to the needs of the doctoral students under their supervision. However, interpreting what participant Ku said was the response from her supervisor indicates that the main issue might be about the insufficient time allocated to supervisory support as students tend to demand more in reality. This could then be seconded by the number of students assigned for supervision. To reiterate, the university would need to be more considerate that these supervisors are humans who have the tendency to break down when the workload becomes unbearable (Mason and Hickman, 2015). This is again, why it is important to have a general platform where these students could engage in peer-to-peer support as most general enquiries would have been sorted via these platforms without having to take it to the supervisors. Participant Ab narrated how his supervisor was able to encourage peer relationships among the students under his supervision in the excerpt below:

... there's something that my supervisor introduced, he started organising general workshops for the whole cohorts. So, he would bring the previous year and the present year altogether, and then we would just talk, I think he did it like maybe every two, three months. So, if you feel comfortable enough to share your number with anybody, then you can share your number with them - Ab

As described by this participant, his supervisor organises informal gatherings as simple as a get-together once in two or three months where students just chat with each other discussing their challenges and how to solve them. Through this approach, new students were able to

informally meet existing students with the likelihood of extending their discussions beyond the meeting.

The supervisory role has been emphasised to be at the forefront of all factors that determine the successful completion of doctoral studies (Becher et al., 1994; Subramanian et al., 2013). Therefore, whatever actions are taken by supervisors to enhance peer relationships would go a long way to make or mar the success story of these groups of students. It will also reduce the constant demand of support request that they would have been receiving by students who want to ask for help but has no other alternative.

6.2.7 Increasing the visibility of the BME peer support group on campus

This is one of the challenges unique to the Black and Minority Ethnic (BME) participants for this study. They mentioned that even though they would like to be engaged in peer relationships groups established for doctoral students, they would also like to engage specifically with fellow BME students. Participant Mr reflected on how she made efforts to connect with other African students when she first arrived at UWS as a PhD student, but it was difficult. She added that she felt lonelier as she was not yet confident enough to approach other ethnic groups due to what Laufer and Gorup (2018) referred to as Othering. According to her, having someone of similar ethnicity to guide her in the first few months of her arrival would have helped to make her transition from Nigeria to the UK a more interesting and relaxing one:

I don't know if it's the university that is supposed to do this or the groups are supposed to come out like, I remember when I came in, [speech unintelligible], I didn't know where I went to online, but I know I saw different groups, one from my place - Nigeria, but there were no contact details. But I saw that the Asian culture, they had a well set up system. They had an office; they had their contact details. They had a contact person... I

noticed that there were about three groups that had it all together. So, I think the university could do more by creating an enabling environment for other minority groups to be comfortable enough to reach out to the other members. If they cannot assign offices, like the cafeteria, they could put signboards, so and so is meeting, at so time and day. People go through there at least once a week, you could see that and then you just go, and you find your people and you'll, of course, be more comfortable. You'll get more support – Mr

As seen above, having the guide of someone from the same ethnic background helps the students feel safer in their new environment and, as a result, guarantees a high level of trust because people tend to identify more quickly with someone of a similar race (Robinson et al., 2016)

Based on this understanding, the researcher took the move to create a WhatsApp group to connect a few black students, including those that participated in the study. As of the time of this writing, 14 Nigerian doctoral students have joined the group, with the hope to continue to add more new students as they settle into their various UWS campuses. However, it should be noted that this would only solve less than half of the problem for this group as the university would still have to take the central position so that more BME students would be aware of the platforms to join for peer-to-peer support.

This aspect is crucial as it spans through the period of the global 'Black Lives Matter' movement (Taylor, 2016). Therefore, it will be a big win for universities to take the lead by ensuring that not just the Black people's needs are met but also ensuring that the minority groups in their institution are well-represented up to the teaching staff members' level, an action UWS prides itself in.

From this study, it is observed that even though most doctoral students are independent with their academics, they still need some level of support which could only occur when peer relationships have been established. Another participant, participant Uc, posited that the university should ensure they provide the necessary support that would enhance the well-being of their students as this is the only time students would even feel motivated to join any other activities organised by the university. In her words:

... we paid a lot to be in the school so the focus should be on achieving value for each student. Having a department for academic purposes, mental wellbeing, emotional wellbeing, different things, not just you come to school, and you go back home. Like for example, I don't know any other lecturer apart from the lady who taught us. Doesn't make sense, because when you're stuck, you are stuck. – Uc

According to participant Uc, she has paid a lot as an international student, and she was hoping that she would get more non-academic support than she was currently receiving. This participant expectation seems different from the plans of the university for doctoral students which is to train them to become as independent as possible ahead of their academic or professional careers (see doctoral college book for 2020/2021). In addition, the university expects that for specific help, doctoral students, and all students for that matter, should use the available support services (i.e., counselling unit, student support services, student union among others) to help them. While this is the norm for many students, the university needs to consider that some students are Lurkers. As described by Gazit et al. (2018), Lurkers are those who may never be confident enough to seek help even when they need it. Therefore, the study believes that while some students could just walk up to different individuals or available services whenever they need help, some might need a bit of interaction before being free to discuss their needs. This may be specific for many international students who may become Lurkers as they

settle into their new academic environment, therefore the university needs to strategise on how to help these groups of students. And the truth is Lurkers do exist among all doctoral students. They may be in the minority, but they do exist and ignoring them might be one of the reasons for the drop-out rates experienced among doctoral students.

6.3 Chapter summary

This chapter, which is the concluding part of the result and findings section, has highlighted the various suggestions given by the UWS doctoral students on how to enhance peer relationships to support one another. It revealed that some relevant events need to be reintroduced while some existing ones should be made aware to all doctoral students across the university's campuses. The doctoral students also proposed some new ideas on how the university could help to enhance peer to peer support among them. Finally, it was found that supervisors have a key role in actualising the proposed ideas.

The findings from this chapter show that providing an enabling environment where doctoral students could voluntarily engage with each other without much interference from the university would go a long way to not only reduce the pressure on the supervisors but also makes the students feel fulfilled and happy. This is simply because this will enable them to make decisions on when and how to be involved in the whole activities, which is what is preferred by these groups of students. Understandably, it might be a difficult task for the university to aim at fulfilling all the unique needs of its doctoral students. However, just as posited throughout this study, and in this Chapter, the provision of an enabling environment that will enhance peer relationships would allow the students to be able to help each other based as much as they could, based on their terms.

The next chapter - recommendations and conclusions - succinctly explore previous chapters of this project - ranging from the reviewed literature to the results and findings and makes a

contextual recommendation from them; one that would be suitable for the specific needs of UWS doctoral students and that could be adapted to other universities in the UK.

CHAPTER 7 – DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The conclusions and recommendations derived from this project are discussed in this final chapter as this ensures that the research aim, and objectives were achieved. To begin with, the chapter describes how the study has achieved each of the four research objectives. Afterwards, the research contributions to theory, policy, and practice are presented, followed by the future implications of the study on peer relationship's research and practice.

7.1 Research objectives

7.1.1 Research objective one: To understand the concept of peer relationships among doctoral students

This research objective explored the three functions of peer relationships among doctoral students of UWS as proposed in the peer relationships framework (PRF). In Chapter Two, there was a review of the existing literature on the types of peers among doctoral students as established in Kram and Isabella's (1985) PRF. Although the framework was based on work colleagues, different studies conducted after that (i.e., Lee et al., 2017; Terrion and Leonard, 2007) showed that the framework has been adapted for doctoral students' study by Lee et al. (2017). Despite being decades apart, the latter's study was able to confirm that different types of peers, as proposed by the former, is present among doctoral students. In addition to the three types of peers identified (Special, collegial, and information peers), Lee et al. (2017) posited that there is a fourth one – dysfunctional peers, where doctoral students have negative feelings towards each other because they have a different outlook on life.

The three functions – *developmental functions*, *self-disclosure*, and *trust/distrust* proposed by Kram and Isabella's (1985) PRF were confirmed in this study. Under *developmental functions*, it was found that doctoral students perceive peer relationships as either empowering, trivial, or

overwhelming. The analysis revealed that although peer relationships are useful as they help the students to keep in touch with one another, however, it could be overwhelming for some others. The empowering group could be either as peer support, peer learning, and/or peer mentoring. The concept of peer support involves activities such as sharing basic information about the doctorate programme, checking on each other's wellbeing to make things easier among other things. Peer learning involves doctoral students helping to improve each other's academic capability while peer mentoring is about peers (mostly senior) guiding the other doctoral colleagues on academic and/or non-academic issues.

The analysis re-grouped the three types of peers identified by Kram and Isabella (1985) and the fourth one mentioned by Lee et al. (2017), as listed above, under *self-disclosure*. This is because it was found that the level of self-disclosure is influenced by the type of peer the doctoral students belong to. The special peers are those characterised by a special bond to the extent that they are able to discuss personal issues with each other. This is more common among the DBA group compared to their PhD colleagues whereas collegial and information peers are common among both groups of students – DBA and PhD. While collegial peers have empathy towards their peers, information type of peer is just for the sake of being colleagues. The new type of peer identified in this study constitutes the negative peer relationships in that these peers do not think highly of each other, and the likely reasons could be because of the different outlook on their doctoral journey itself. Interestingly, it was found that despite these negative views about each other, these students try to keep this thought to themselves, and never try to be confrontational. Since this fourth type of peer was vividly mentioned in Lee et al.'s (2017) study, the findings from this study confirm that dysfunctional peers do exist among doctoral students. With the inclusion of Lewicki et al.'s (1998) trust framework, the analysis also shows that some doctoral students seek and give support to their peers whether within the

university or outside due to their high level of trust, while there are a group of students who would never seek help from their peers due to high level of distrust.

Further, the findings reveal the impact of COVID-19 on doctoral students and how these students were able to support each other at that time. While the literature review established that there are short term and long-term effects of the pandemic (Buheji and Buheji, 2020), this study was only able to find the short-term impact. This is that many students suffered more loneliness and mental breakdown during the pandemic than it was previously recorded before the pandemic (Byrom, 2020). Meanwhile, another study (Lee et al., 2021) insists that the majority of students were able to manage the situation better than it is being portrayed in the literature. The current study, however, supports the position of Byrom (2020) and other existing literature to maintain that most of the doctoral students were destabilised during the pandemic. This is due to reasons such as the uncertainties around when they would be able to resume the practical aspect of their research, among other things. It is true that the doctoral journey is normally tagged as being lonely, but the pandemic made it even worse as everyone had to grapple with surviving the period itself (Marelli et al., 2020).

Another aspect highlighted during the analysis was the role of gender. Findings from this study posit that UWS doctoral students would generally seek help from whichever gender type is approachable and willing to help. Nonetheless, when it comes to more personal issues, students generally sought support from those of the same gender as themselves. It also became clear that women become more stressed than their male counterparts due to other commitments outside their academic work. This is relatable to Bowen and Rudenstine (2014) submission on the negative impact of non-academic commitments handled by female academics than their male counterparts.

From the above, this study argues that even though doctoral students are being trained to become independent researchers or professionals, being human still makes them reliant on each other for support. This might not be as much as it is expected of the lower levels of education such as undergraduate and master's degrees, however, a little help will be needed. The best way to balance these two positions is to ensure there is an enabling environment for these students to support one another at their own pace and convenience through peer relationships. This way, there will be an opportunity for those interested to get involved while those not wanting to engage will not feel they are being forced but at least will know the support from their peers is always there for whenever they need it.

7.1.2 Research objective Two: To comprehend the various MIM apps used for peer relationships among doctoral students

To achieve this research objective, the different MIM apps used by students for supporting each other were reviewed in both the literature and the result and discussion chapters of this study. The literature started by understanding the history of these MIMs and how they have evolved to their current level of effectiveness. The literature found that IM apps have been in existence for decades, but their effectiveness skyrocketed with the invention of the smartphone as this increased its accessibility and speedy response (So, 2016). The main purpose of these apps was to reduce loneliness and share information among other reasons (Luo and Hancock, 2020). From the literature, some of the most popular ones, with billions of users, are WhatsApp and Facebook messenger (Statista Research Department, 2021b) and they are known to be convenient, easy to use, and instant for supporting each other.

The analysis from this study found that doctoral students at UWS use different types of MIMs for supporting one another. These students, especially the DBA students, tend to use WhatsApp for engaging in peer relationships at a more personal level, thereby confirming the popularity of this MIM app for peer-to-peer support among doctoral students (Abiodun et al., 2020). On

the contrary, the PhD students use different kinds of MIMs especially those supported by the university such as Microsoft Teams. By default, the DBA students are introduced to creating a WhatsApp group account for their cohort where all students are obliged to join. Since this MIM app requires the exchange of mobile numbers, the analysis showed that many of the PhD students do not want to engage in peer relationships through this platform due to privacy reasons. Also, for security reasons, the PhD students prefer to use Microsoft Teams to connect with their colleagues, with Liu et al. (2020) also describing the MIM feature of Teams as 'safe and reliable'.

The findings further show that Zoom, a cloud-based video conferencing platform that can also be used as a MIM app, became popular during the COVID – 19 lockdown but it was not yet being used *per se* for peer relationships at the time this study was conducted. Zoom was one of the MIMs that gained its fame for connecting students during the pandemic in 2020 as the need to instantly connect with others be it with family, friends, or business colleagues, intensified across the world. Unlike WhatsApp and Teams, Zoom does not require its users to share their personal information such as phone numbers or email IDs. Rather, a link to the meeting is sent out to the participant(s) which could be used to join the meeting. It made virtual interactions easier especially during the COVID-19 pandemic (Wang et al., 2020). The downside of Zoom is that its users have to pay if the conversation goes beyond 40 minutes when compared to WhatsApp and Microsoft Teams, which are completely free to use once connected to the internet. It was found that some students still prefer to use the likes of emails and Facebook messenger to engage or support one another. None of the doctoral students mentioned Telegram, possibly because it was not popular with the students when this study was conducted.

From the findings, it is revealed that interpersonal trust/distrust and the trust/distrust on the MIM apps influence how people use these platforms as supporting tools. Drawing reference

from Lewicki et al.'s (1998) trust model, it was found that some UWS doctoral students use these platforms to support and engage with other peers due to the high level of trust and low level of distrust they have for that colleague - Quadrant 2 as reviewed in Chapter 2, page 39. Meanwhile, some will not engage in in-depth interactions due to the low Trust/high distrust they have for their peers when it comes to using MIM apps for interaction – Quadrant 3. Contrary to interpersonal trust, some UWS doctoral students are concerned about the actual MIM apps. This group of people are always concerned (high distrust) about data breaches, technical issues among other things, even though they use the apps for connecting and supporting their peers (high trust) – Quadrant 4. The fourth group of students based on Lewicki et al.'s (1998) classifications are in quadrant 1 (low trust/low distrust). The doctoral students are not much concerned about the advantages or disadvantages of the MIM apps other than the fact they would always prefer physical peer-to-peer support compared to the online form for peer relationships.

The analysis from this study shows that the UWS doctoral students are particular about what type of MIM apps they use in engaging with their colleagues, and this is usually informed by certain factors such as recommendations by the university authorities and their preferences based on the functions of the app.

Even when these two has been sorted, the actual level of interactions among these group of students is determined by the level of trust/distrust either on the peer they want to engage with via MIM apps or towards the app itself.

7.1.3 Research objective Three: To understand the influence of trust on peer relationships and the use of MIMs app supporting tools

This research objective focuses on understanding the influence of trust on peer relationships and the use of MIMs as used as a supporting tool among doctoral students. To achieve this, the review started by exploring the definition of trust as given by 16 authors before moving to

critically analysing the different models of trust and finding a suitable model for the current study. This review led to the adoption of Lewicki et al.'s (1997) trust model. The relationship between the various forms of trust and distrust as proposed by these authors were reviewed and its relationship to the Kram and Isabella's (1985) model for PRF was examined. Thereby, revealing the link between trust/distrust, self-disclosure, and developmental functions as illustrated in this study's conceptual framework. Further, it reiterates the role of trust and distrust in determining the type of information or material shared among doctoral students.

The analysis confirms Lewicki et al.'s (1998) position that trust and distrust could exist in the same peer, and that four combinations from the model are possible. Firstly, the *high trust/low distrust* combination is found among **special peers** who are willing to share a lot. As soon as these peers build the needed trust for the relationship, they start having the freedom to self-disclose their challenges and share academic and non-academic information. This type of relationship could involve just two or more peers but mostly not exceeding four students otherwise it gets too crowded. To avoid intrusion from others, they usually create a closed group on one of the MIM apps, and this study found that it is mostly on WhatsApp. This does not mean that they would stop participating in the general group chat (if available), just that they interact more freely through their closed group chat. The direct contrast to the special peer is those within the Lewicki et al. (1998) *low trust /high distrust* quadrant. Typically, they are those that believe peers cannot provide help to them either because they found them either unapproachable or not good enough to help them (**dysfunctional peer**).

According to the findings, **Collegial peers** are classified under *the high trust/high distrust* quadrant. They help each other academically and give basic feedback but there is a general opinion that they cannot share any sensitive issues that are outside their academic work other than just generally checking up on each other. This, in a sense, explains those doctoral colleagues who trust a colleague academically, could join them for peer learning and chat about

general issues and emotional support, but hardly discuss in-depth matters relating to family or finance. The doctoral students whose relationship is just based on being colleagues with no tangible relationship are grouped under the *low trust/low distrust* category – (**information peers**). It is similar to the dysfunctional features but just that they do not form a negative opinion about each other as they have not had any interaction or encounter needed for them to form any judgement about each other. This is more like a borderline of the types of peers because it could change either for worse (dysfunctional) or progress into a better one.

These findings, which were explored under Chapters Four and Five, reveal that the peer relationships between UWS doctoral students could be referred to as semi-formal. This is because even the most intimate of all the types of peer relationships (special peer) still relate with a little bit of cautiousness (low distrust), especially when the support is conducted via MIM apps. Specifically, using the MIM apps as a supporting tool depends on two types of trust/distrust – trust/distrust on the peers with whom to engage (interpersonal trust/distrust) or trust/distrust on the MIM apps where the concern is about technical issues, apps collapsing, or stealing of personal details.

7.1.4 Research objective Four: To propose guidelines on how the university can enhance peer relationships among doctoral students

This objective aims at collating the opinion of doctoral students on how the university could enhance peer to peer support among them through peer relationships. The analysis of these guidelines further confirms the positions of the doctoral participants. Those under special peers, who are likely to belong to the empowering group under self-disclosure, believe that the university could enhance their peer relationships through social activities and events. Meanwhile, the collegial and information peers who are likely to also be trivial in terms of self-disclosure suggest some online activities either through WhatsApp or Microsoft Teams. This is in addition to having access to synchronous learning on research skills.

The findings from this analysis reveal that despite having a dysfunctional type of peer, none of the doctoral students disagrees with having some form of peer-to-peer support. It, therefore, means that all doctoral students would benefit from whatever efforts is made by the university to enhance their peer relationship as proposed in this chapter - be it peer support, peer learning, or peer mentoring. The students specifically emphasise how peer mentoring from a senior colleague would be of great benefit to their doctoral studies. The suggestion for enhancing peer mentoring was to make a list of the names of interested senior doctoral students, their email address, and their research areas either on the university intranet or through supervisors. Doing this will help junior doctoral students avoid unnecessary mistakes in their doctoral journey.

It is believed that having two main types of informal groups will help the students enhance their peer relationships to support one another. The first suggestion is for the lead student (ambassador) and his team (representatives) (see page 190) to organise face-to-face events such as visiting a museum, attending conferences among others as well as online events such as hangouts, chatting sessions around games, artwork, and other activities that may be of interest to his colleagues. The physical activities would help meet the needs of those who want to engage with peers on a personal level and have the time to meet up physically while the online examples are for those willing to engage but not have the time to meet up physically. The second suggestion is having some free study rooms and some bookable ones dedicated to either those students who want to engage strictly for academic purposes or those who want no peer involvement. Even though these guidelines are advised to be run by the students for the students, they still need the approval of the university to be successful.

7.2 Research contributions

This study has made some unique contributions to knowledge on peer relationships among doctoral students. Of which, its adoption would help to advance theoretical understanding and advancement in policymaking and practice on the concept of peer relationships. These contributions to knowledge and the implication of the research are discussed in detail below.

7.2.1 Theoretical contributions

This study drew on the peer relationships framework as developed by Kram and Isabella (1985) and its application to doctoral education by Lee et al. (2017). It builds on the existing body of knowledge to bridge the gaps between theory and practice of peer relationships and the use of MIM apps among doctoral students. Apart from modifying the PRF to include functions relevant to the exploration of peer relationships among doctoral students, this study was also able to confirm the presence of *dysfunctional peers* as suggested by Lee et al.'s (2017).

The adoption of the peer relationships framework with an introduction of the trust/distrust model by Lewicki et al. (1998) has brought to the fore a new approach to conceptualising peer relationships among these groups of students. Also, this study introduced a new dimension to the said concept as it is the first of its kind to interpret peer relationships from the perspective of MIM apps and trust/distrust.

A revisit of the conceptual framework suggested the need to include some key concepts in the final proposed framework such as the impact of COVID-19 and the role of gender. However, this may not be included at this time due to the following reasons. Firstly, the conceptual framework was constructed before the COVID-19 pandemic and it has spanned through the post-COVID-19 period as well. So, the inclusion of what happened during a particular period would undermine one of the main purposes of this study which is about modifying the PRF such that it becomes better applicable to this doctoral study. Secondly, although gender is an important concept when discussing doctoral studies (Jairam and Kahl, 2012), there were mixed

results from this study, therefore there might be a need for further research to ascertain its presence before being included in the modified peer relationships framework. For these reasons, these two are not included in the revisited conceptual framework. The concepts that are included in the modified framework are summarised below:

7.2.1.1 Developmental functions

The PRF as used by Kram and Isabella (1985) indicates that knowledge is one of the key ways for determining the peer relationships that exist among people. The findings from this study align with the framework by asserting that when doctoral students engage in a peer relationship, they could develop perceptions that the relationship is either overwhelming, trivial, or empowering. The empowering could be through peer support, peer learning, or peer mentoring. This, in turn, helps to increase the confidence level required to help in completing the doctoral training as well the overall research skills of the peers involved. Thus, making it an important function of the modified framework.

7.2.1.2 Self-disclosure

Just as indicated by Kram and Isabella (1985) and Lee et al. (2017), the proposed framework maintains that the level of self-disclosure is an important dimension of the framework. It also finds that self-disclosure does not happen suddenly; it is gradual, and it will depend on the type of relationship that exists among doctoral students. Generally, doctoral students tend not to disclose much information about themselves with peers at early meetings (early phase), but as the relationship advances and a possible bond develops (middle phase), they are likely to become freer to share more and more with their peers. This could lead to them becoming special peers; collegial peers; information peers or dysfunctional peers. By the third phase, students are no longer willing to make new peer relationships. They either build on or maintain, the existing one.

7.2.1.3 Trust/Distrust

Just as highlighted in the Kram and Isabella (1985) framework, the concept of trust remains an important function in the modified framework. However, this study has chosen to infuse the Lewicki et al. (1998) concept of trust which also included distrust. This is because the two concepts can independently influence the level of developmental functions and self-disclosure among peers. Based on this level of trust/distrust, some students are happy with seeking supports from peers within the university - immediate and senior peers - while some prefer peers from outside the university. The other group with a low level of trust and high level of distrust seek no support from peers at all rather they are satisfied with the formal support they receive from their supervisors/university only. In terms of the use of MIM apps, this study presents that doctoral students are willing to connect using this platform as well as share basic information that would benefit their colleagues. However, many of them are conscious of sharing sensitive details such as their personal lives or their academic work either because of their high distrust (Kramer, 1994) for their fellow peers or for the platform itself.

Based on the different roles played by trust and distrust, the concept as defined by Lewicki et al. (1998) is considered important thus, its inclusion in the modified framework.

7.2.1.4 Use of MIMs

Even though this was not included in the original peer relationships framework by Kram and Isabella (1985), neither was it considered by Lee et al.'s (2017) work or any known existing work on peer relationship, this study was able to successfully ascertain its importance to peer relationships among doctoral students. Moreover, there is an independent body of evidence in the literature that affirms that the use of MIMs has continued to support students both formally and informally (Abiodun et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2020). With over 3.6 billion users of MIM apps across the globe (Statista Research Department, 2021a), it is imperative to adjust the peer relationships framework to accommodate this vital supporting tool.

The special peers use this medium (mostly a closed group chat) to regularly connect due to the special bond between them. Albeit, collegial peers and information peers connect mainly for academic purposes, the former engage in occasional check-ups on each other during non-term times. These two types of peers are often active on the group chat set up for their cohort as well. Specifically, the UWS doctoral students mostly use WhatsApp and Microsoft Teams to engage in peer relationships, with the former common among the London campus students while the latter is preferred among the Scottish campuses' students.

With the central role of MIM apps in ensuring that peer relationships among interested doctoral students are possible irrespective of their location, it is pertinent to be included in the modified framework.

7.2.1.5 Peer relationships among doctoral students

The concept of peer relationships proposed by this study is similar to how it was presented by Kram and Isabella (1985) and Lee et al. (2017) except for a few advancements as stated above.

This study affirms that different types of peer relationships can develop among doctoral students depending on the level of interactions that take place among them, be it physical or virtual. However, a positive relationship leads to enhanced support that ensures progress in all ramifications while a negative relationship (dysfunctional peers) could include being overwhelmed or having different paths. Care must be taken when referring to it as negative because even the so-called dysfunctional peers could still benefit from the information shared via their group chat. It also confirms that the use of MIM apps (i.e., Microsoft Teams, WhatsApp, Zoom among others) is completely integrated into how UWS doctoral students cultivate their peer relationships. Based on this outcome, it is suggested that the university considers this point for the purpose of building an enabling environment for these groups of students.

The modified peer relationships framework as concluded by this study is presented below:

Figure 16: Modified Peer relationships Framework (original framework by Kram and Isabella, 1985).

7.3 Theoretical implications and recommendations

The theoretical implications of this research are relevant to academic research on peer relationships, the use of MIMs, and doctoral education. This research advanced existing studies by proposing a modified peer relationships framework that considers the situation of doctoral students. Within the modified framework, the concept of peer relationships and the role of MIMs among doctoral students become apparent, and the influence of the concept of trust/distrust in a peer relationship is established. In this project, the features of different MIM apps and the influence of their usage among doctoral students was also affirmed. This cross-discipline research allows for further exploration of the modified framework from different academic fields.

It is also the beginning of an academic debate on the impact of negative peer relationships on doctoral students. Being the first of its kind, more research is needed to further establish the role of trust/distrust in the usage of MIM apps as a supporting tool among doctoral students. To build on this study, there is the need to gain a detailed insight into whether the types of peer relationship is influenced by factors other than those mentioned in this study.

The adoption of the peer relationships framework has allowed this research to critically analyse the different types of peer relationships created among doctoral students of UWS campuses which are novel for the institution. Future research is required to explore the similarities and differences that may occur by studying multiple universities in the UK. Also, this study has adopted the qualitative method only, it will be beneficial for future studies to review this area of study using a quantitative method or mixed-method. Doing a quantitative study will ensure that the outcomes from this area of study are generalisable while the mixed method would help to understand any contradictions between the findings from this qualitative research as well as those conducted using a quantitative strategy. The study ensured to follow Corbin, Dwyer, and Buckle's (2009) advice to make sure the true story of the participants come through during interpretation. However, there is always a reservation of being an inside researcher (Woods, 2019). Hence, future research could be conducted from the position of an outside researcher to further ascertain the findings from this study.

This research was conducted with rigour and high ethical standard however there were a few limitations to it. Firstly, the use of one university reduces its generalisation ability as it is not known if the context of UWS will apply to other institutions. However, this was managed by ensuring that the study explored more than one campus of the institution. Secondly, even though the size of the study was within the recommended size, it would still be considered as being small to be able to generalise the outcome to all doctoral students in the UK, a feature common with most qualitative studies. Nonetheless, two focus group sessions were conducted

to further increase the reliability of the results. Lastly, there was an imbalance between the number of international students and home students (17 to 4 respectively). This could have possibly reduced the voice of the home students while amplifying that of the international students. However, this effect was reduced by ensuring that suggestions from both groups of students were always balanced out. Despite the limiting factors stated here, the concluding points provided below offers important guidelines for managing peer relationships and the use of MIM apps as supporting tools among doctoral students.

7.4 Policy and Practice contributions and recommendations

This research has important implications for future policy and practice to be developed at UWS on how to enhance peer relationships among doctoral students. The guidelines proposed below in Table 11 are produced based on the findings from this study. However, each campus needs to ensure a considerable level of flexibility to accommodate the cultural and geographical differences that may occur among their students. Although this study has explored campuses of one university, the recommendations below could be adopted by other universities but again, ensure they are contextual.

Recommendation 1: To allocate more time to supervision of doctoral students

Despite the literature emphasising the importance of good supervisory supports, some doctoral students still have a challenge with their supervisory team. The data from this study suggest that the problem could be the insufficient allocated time for supervision, thereby making supervisors not able to provide the best support to the student.

The university needs to ensure they review the time allocated to supervision for the possibilities of improving it. The best way to do this is to work with supervisors in the university either through a survey or meeting to understand how to make the process easier for them, as well as make the process fulfilling for their doctoral students.

Recommendation 2: Review the challenge of gender and ethnicity bias

The policies of UWS clearly state its interest in ensuring Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion in its institution, so are other UK universities. Yet, the literature and this study confirmed that female doctoral students and students of minority ethnic groups continue to be disadvantaged due to their circumstances.

The university needs to provide a supporting system unique to this group of people to make their doctoral journey as enjoyable as it could be.

Recommendation 3: Make provisions for doctoral students who are not willing or too shy to involve with other peers

The literature and the data from this study affirmed that some doctoral students would not just want to be involved with their peers due to their preferences or unique circumstances. Despite this, there should also be enabling environment for them.

Bookable rooms dedicated to doctoral students should be made available across different schools or at the campuses' libraries. This way those that prefer to work on their own or engage in peer learning would be able to do so without any distractions. For those who could not ask for help, the university should liaise with the supervisors to identify these students that they think may benefit from extra support. These doctoral students could then be advised and possibly guided on how to use the university support services or referred to a senior colleague based on their preferences. Doing this will go a long way to boost the confidence level of that group of doctoral students.

Recommendation 4: The university should follow the suggestions provided by the doctoral students as shown in Table 11 below to ensure fit-for-purpose supports.

Table 11: Guidelines for enhancing peer relationships as suggested by the UWS doctoral students that partook in this study.

Key issue	Guidelines
<p>Activities to encourage peer relationships</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Irrespective of the campus, all doctoral students should be introduced to all the university’s activities such as power hour of writing; peer reflection forum among etc. as early as they are enrolled. For DBA students and other non-traditional doctorates, this could be done by their year one tutor as they are not assigned supervisors until year two. 2. Supervisors (for PhD) or year one tutor (for DBA) should organise informal events such as having lunchtime together or attending a monthly conference/seminar together at least quarterly depending on what is agreed with their students. For DBA students, there should be at least one visitation to an industry once a year to learn about the practical aspect of running a business environment. 3. There could also be visitations to places such as museums; art centres or other event centres just to get together at least once in three months. 4. Interested senior students could act as mentors for the new students. To avoid the pressure attached to mentoring, the senior students should not be assigned to more than two new students,

	<p>and they could decide how they want to meet or guide each other. Alternatively, names and emails of interested senior students under a particular supervisor could be made available internally or through the university's intranet such that new doctoral students could access these senior students leisurely for guidance. This should be available for all campuses (If the duration is attached, the mentors could be recognised with a certificate of completion as a form of recognition).</p>
Use of MIMs	<p>MIM apps such as WhatsApp group chats should be encouraged among those hoping to connect with peers for emotional supports, and other non-academic activities such as artwork, music, or football among others. A WhatsApp group was created for Nigerians when they expressed their feelings of neglect during this study.</p> <p>Microsoft Teams should be encouraged among those who wish to stay connected but not on a personal level.</p>

7.5 Researcher's Learning Journey

When I began this project, I aimed to understand how peer relationships works among doctoral students and the role of using MIM apps for supporting one another. On commencing the study, it became essential to include whether students trusted these apps or not and exploring that area of research has further improved my ability to review literature outside of my field. By researching as an insider, I became confident that this would give me an edge on accessing participants for data collection. While this was true, familiarity became a challenge as participants tend to chat about things outside of the scope of the study. Nonetheless, whenever

the participants were deviating from the questions, I ensured I steered the conversation with the help of the interview guide I had developed for data collection.

I learned from another challenge I had which was around how to ensure the date and time chosen for the focus group was suitable for at least six of the participants as their free times were always clashing. The first group eventually came and was successful but for the second group, I anticipated at most seven including myself, but we ended up being nine as two more students, who were invited as extra also showed interest. I was worried about how to manage the big group but at the same did not want to turn these participants down. I was in a fix for a while but after realising the number was still within the literature recommendations (Barbour, 2008; Morgan, 2016), I allowed them to join the session with extra preparations on how to manage a big focus group session. Outside academics, I also had other challenges such as finance especially with paying tuition fees, as well as balancing family with academic life. However, I was able to manage all of this by spending extra time strategising and re-strategising, which eventually worked with some help from the university.

In addition to the above, I also learnt the importance of purposely leaving the completed work for a few days and revisiting it as this helped me to see my work from a fresher perspective. Not doing this until during my VIVA preparations made me panic and confused as I identified some avoidable errors. If I have the opportunity to conduct a similar study again in the future, I will ensure I take note of the shortcomings I had during this thesis and put better plans in place on how to avoid them.

With these various experiences during my doctoral journey, I am now a well-grounded researcher in conducting qualitative research using both interviews and focus group methods, as well as how to successfully multitask.

7.6 Concluding remarks

This study has critically examined peer relationships and the use of MIM apps as trusted supporting tools among doctoral students. This concluding chapter discusses how the research objectives for the project were achieved alongside the theoretical, and practical, contributions of the study. It builds on the peer relationship framework by Kram and Isabella (1985), while regularly referencing Lewicki et al.'s (1998) trust model. The suitability of using a modified PRF for exploring peer relationships among doctoral students is affirmed in this research. It is established that peer relationships are an important aspect of students' doctoral journey and the use of MIM apps enhances this relationship. Specifically, the three key functions of the original framework (developmental functions, self-disclosure, and trust) were expanded in a way that leads to the following assertions. Firstly, doctoral students who see the impact of peer relationships as empowering are also special or collegial peers who trust the help they get from their peers within the university. Meanwhile, those that perceive their peer relationships as trivial often remain as information peers, and they tend to stick to their supervisor's support, and probably support from senior colleagues. Lastly, those that see the peer relationships as overwhelming are likely to see their peers as dysfunctional, therefore, sticking to support from only their supervisors or the university (i.e., administrative office, counselling unit etc.).

It is concluded that doctoral students of UWS use MIM apps to enhance their peer relationships as these platforms are used to share information around academic and non-academic issues. However, the level of both interpersonal trust/distrust and trust/distrust on the MIMs determines the level of their engagement with this platform. No matter how special the colleagues become, they still have a little bit of cautiousness, thereby referring to their relationship as semi-formal. The final chapter established the transferability of this study and how it could not only be adopted by UWS but also be replicated in other universities with a

consideration of their unique variability. The need to consider other research methods and the importance of reflexivity to an interpretive researcher were discussed.

In sum, this study confirmed that the modified peer relationships framework, which considered the importance of the use of MIMs and includes distrust as part of the trust concept, is an ideal model for exploring peer relationships among doctoral students with a reference to those enrolled at UWS.

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9.0 Appendix A

Table 12: List of the popular definitions of trust and their authors, arranged according to their year of publication.

Author (Year)	Definition of Trust
Read (1962)	Trust is when the trustor has the confidence that his interest is protected and that they could share their vulnerability and be confident that it is safe in the trusting relationship.
Rotter (1967)	Trust is that expectancy held by an individual or a group that the word, promise verbal or written statement of another individual or group can be relied upon.
Barber (1998)	It is a reliance on a person or thing.
Gambetta (1988)	Trust may exist amid the risk of uncertainty, ignorance and could even be based on unknown or unknowable actions but should never be forced to take place.
Dobin (1993)	The willingness to believe an intention.
Mayer, Davis and Schoorman (1995)	The willingness to be vulnerable to the other individual based on their ability, integrity and benevolence.
McAllister (1995)	It is evident that a peer's behaviour is consistent with norms of reciprocity and fairness and that the peer follows through on commitments.
Misztal (1996)	The author maintains that people tend to trust others as they believe in them despite uncertainties.

Mishra (1996)	Trust could only take place when one party is willing to be vulnerable to another group concerning their reliability, concern, openness and competence of which a change in one dimension would trigger a change in the levels of the other dimension
Rousseau et al. (1998)	Trust is a psychological state that consists of the intention of accepting to be vulnerable to others' actions with the belief that the other individual/group have positive intentions towards them.
Lewicki et al. (1998)	Trust is the confident positive expectations regarding another's conduct while distrust is the confident negative expectations regarding another's conduct.
Sheppard and Sherman (1998)	Trust is really about having faith in the actions of the other person(s).
Whitener, Brodt, Korsgaard, and Werner (1998)	Trust takes place only when the agents involved would be benevolent to each other.
Gill, Ramsey, Leberman, and Atkins (2016)	Trust is the expectation that others can be relied upon, demonstrated through one's readiness to talk about issues with which one experiences feelings of vulnerability.

Note: The 54 years review of the definitions of Trust identified that irrespective of when and how the concept was defined, it involves some key features such as vulnerability; confidence in each other and most importantly, involves more than one person.

10.0 Appendix B

INVITATION LETTER TO DOCTORAL STUDENTS AT UWS LONDON CAMPUS

Peer relationships and the use of mobile instant messaging applications as trusted supporting tools: The case of doctoral students at UWS London Campus.

Dear Doctoral student,

I am currently conducting a study as part of the partial fulfilment of my doctorate studies at the University of the West of Scotland (UWS), London campus just like you. May I request that you partake in this study aimed at understanding how doctoral students support each other using Mobile Instant Messaging Apps (such as WhatsApp, Facebook messenger, Imo, Instagram among others) as a trusted supporting tool?

The individual interview sessions would last for about 40-60 minutes and will take place online. The interview would be based on your availability and the time suitable for you. Likewise, a focus group session that will involve an interaction between at least six (6) doctoral students from different cohorts will also be conducted online regarding the same topic stated above, and you can decide whether you will participate in just one of the sessions or the two.

Please be aware that your participation is completely voluntary, and you can decide at any stage of the study whether you want to continue to participate in this research or not. All responses will be kept confidential, and all your details would remain anonymous neither would it be considered for any other use apart from this dissertation.

Even though direct reward might not be attached to your participation in this study, your contribution would help understand how doctoral students can better support each other to boost their morale needed for the timely completion of their studies.

This study has been scrutinized by the UWS committee on research ethics and asserted to conform with the specified principles of conducting ethical research. For more information or clarifications regarding this study, kindly contact me through the details provided here:

Brief about the Researcher

My name is Ayo, a doctoral student just like you. Being a student myself, I understand the positive impact of the support we give to each other using the MIMs platform and I thought it would be important to understand this from your perspective and to have it documented in an academic record. This can only be achieved with your participation in my research in this study and, I am excited about you sharing your experience with me.

Sincerely yours,

Adebayo A .M

Doctorate student, UWS.

11.0 Appendix C

CONSENT FORM

TITLE OF STUDY: Peer relationships and the use of mobile instant messaging applications as trusted supporting tools: The case of doctoral students at UWS London Campus.

(Please tick the appropriate box)

Consent statement	Response	
I have read the information provided and I understand them	YES	NO
I was provided with enough information on this study	YES	NO
I understand that my participation in this study is voluntary and I can withdraw at any time.	YES	NO
I understand that no part of my personal details will be attached to my response.	YES	NO
And I have permitted anonymous response	YES	NO
I voluntarily agree to take part in this study	YES	NO

Signing the consent form

Signature of participant _____

Date _____

Printed Name _____

Investigator

Signature of Investigator _____

Date _____

Contact details of Investigator _____

12.0 Appendix D

INTERVIEW GUIDE

Sign-in Sheet – for your evidence of meeting only

Received Consent sheet for participation?

Code to represent participants:

Is consent form received? Yes _____ No _____

Agreed to audiotape? Yes _____ No _____

Introduction

Researcher: *Please permit me to say a big thank you for accepting to take part in my study on how doctoral students support themselves. None of your personal details will be attached to your response. The audio recorder on my laptop will be used to tape down our conversation. This is to ensure I do not miss any of your comments during the interview. Once again, you will remain anonymous, and our discussion will be kept confidential.*

May I ask if you have any questions before we start our discussion today?

Questions

- 1) a) How have you been fairing during this COVID-19 period?
- b) Did you at some point sought any kind of support from your colleagues either before or after the pandemic? could you give examples?
- c) How would you say these kinds of supports has helped you with your doctoral program?

- 2)** a) How will you describe your relationship with your colleagues? a) Would you say you treat them differently or the same? Could you describe what informed this?
- b) When you need support from your colleagues, how do you determine which peer to go for specific support? Or would you rather go to a specific peer for all your needs?
- c) If you have to think about one colleague you go to often for support, what would you say always attract you to them?
- d) Apart from your cohort, would you say you seek support from other doctoral students? Could you give a bit more explanation for that?
- 3)** a) How will you describe these three terms: peer learning, peer mentoring, peer support? Which one would you say describe the type of support you currently experience among your peers?
- b) If you have to reflect, how would you say your type of program has influenced the level of support you seek from your peers?
- c) Will there be some colleagues that you would not go to for help? Could you tell me more about why you said that?
- 4)** a) What would you say are the platforms you use in communicating with your peers for support? If you have to choose one, which one would you say has been of help the most and why would did you choose this?
- b) Are there some other methods you might have preferred for seeking support from your colleagues?

- 5) a) How do you trust the support you receive via these platforms? Could you explain further? Do you at some point feel concerned about what you share on these supporting tools with your colleagues?
- b) How would you say this method differ from physical support? May I ask why you said this?
- c) What impact would you say this has had on the type of relationship you have with your colleagues? Please tell me more about this.
- 6) a) Would you describe these supports as similar to those being received from the University? Could you describe this a bit further?
- b) In your opinion, what do you think the university could do to encourage more of this peer-to-peer support?
- 7) Are there any more comments you might want to add?

Moderator: *That will be the end of our conversation today. Thank you for participating virtually today, I appreciate it. May I reassure you that the responses you have provided would only be used for this study and none would be shared with anyone? More so, it will be destroyed once the study is completed. Would you like me to send you a copy of this transcript so you can review it in case I missed any part?*

Thank you once again and stay safe!

13.0 Appendix E

FOCUS GROUP GUIDE

Sign-in Sheet – for your evidence of meeting only?

Time from _____ to _____

Participant signed consent form. Yes _____ No _____

Participant accepted to be audiotaped. Yes _____ No _____

TODAY'S AGENDA

- Appreciation for participating
- Introduction of participants
- Briefing on the aim of the study
- Review of ethical issues (confidentiality anonymity)
- Ground rules
- Session starts
- Summary of discussion
- Request additional comments
- Debriefing

Introduction

Researcher: *Hello everyone, I welcome you all to this session which promises to be an interesting one. I appreciate you have accepted to take part in this session despite your busy schedules. This study is being conducted as partial fulfilment for my doctorate programme and*

I say thank you for making it possible. Today, we shall be looking at how the support we give each other as doctoral students especially through MIMs; has helped us; how much you trust these MIMs apps and how to enhance these supports. Being a focus group, the analyses would be done based on all the conversations so please be reassured that none of your details will be revealed in any way. May I seek your permission to auto-record our conversation today so as not to miss any of the discussion during the analysis stage?

Kindly let me know if you would like me to send you a copy of our conversation today

Before we start, would anyone like to ask me any questions?

Group Agreement

I would like to request a couple of things, people, we start the session today:

- May I humbly ask that we put our phones on silent mode, this is to ensure we fully enjoy our conversations today without distractions.
- Housekeeping: even though it is an online discussion, there will still be a few housekeeping.
 - Fire: kindly ensure we are not cooking or preparing things that may alert the smoke detector
 - Please get yourselves some refreshments before the start of the discussion to ensure an easy flow.
 - In case we need to attend to something quickly, kindly send a wave emoji so you can excuse yourself.

- For this session, no answer is wrong or right so please be free to share with us your experiences on peer support among doctoral students at any time even if it sounds odds or different from others' opinions.
- May I say that we will be needing paper and a pencil/pen along the line just to show others some of our thoughts as we will be doing some simple activities in this session? Kindly indicate on your paper the type of doctorate you are enrolled in (i.e. PhD, DBA etc.) and also your gender. Remember not to include any personal details! I will need you to kindly snap it to me as soon as we finish.
- I envisage we would finish within 90 minutes and my duty today is to navigate us through the questions and ensure we try to keep to time. So, please permit me to interrupt sometimes so we can conclude the questions on time.

Doctoral students Focus Group Questions

- Ice – breaker

Hello everyone, I trust we are all keeping safe. I am confident that this too shall pass and in no time, we will all come out of this pandemic even stronger! (a little bit of discussion on the bug). Would you permit me to start by finding out how we are all faring at this difficult time as a student? What type of support do you need at this time and how are you getting them?

- What are the different types of peers in place among doctoral students

- 1) Now, let me take your memory back to a particular day you felt low about your studies. Could you describe how you helped yourself out of the situation? Did you go to a friend, if yes, what determined why you went to that friend?

As soon as one or two persons narrated, the moderator asked everyone else to simply agree or disagree if they would do something different: Can we all decide if we would have acted similarly or differently?

Notes:

- 2) On a normal day, would you approach every colleague with both academic and personal issues? If not, who is that one colleague you will not go to and what is the reason for that?

Notes:

- 3) If we were to reflect on our experience since we started this doctorate program, we might have had both academic and personal issues – how do you decide which colleague to go to for peer support?

Notes:

- **What are the various mobile instant messaging apps (MIMs) apps used to provide support among doctoral students?**

- 4) With the ongoing lockdown, we are all depending on virtual communication and support for each other. If you have to list at least three platforms that you use in receiving and giving support to your colleague, what would they be? Which one(s) would you say you use often? Why is that?

(Moderator asks the participants to list them in their paper and a discussion around that follows)

Notes:

- 5) Thinking about the MIMs you use most often for supporting each other, how do these differ from the face-to-face support with your colleagues?

Notes:

- 6) Take a moment to think about three of your colleagues, one you can easily communicate with on the mobile apps about everything (academic and personal issues) A/ that one colleague you only go to for specific issues B and that colleague you don't go to at all C, could you write down 3 or more features that determine your actions?

The moderator shows an example of what the participants are expected to do and talk more about their various answers.

Notes:

A	B	C	Comments

- **To understand if the experience of PhD students on the use of MIMs for support differ from their DBA colleagues.**

- 7) How would you say the support you receive from colleagues through MIMs has contributed to your progress in this doctorate program?

- **To understand the influence of trust on the use of these apps as supporting tools.**

- 8) With the understanding that people could easily share our information with others, are there some issues we would be careful to discuss via MIMs or are there exceptions with some of our colleagues, why are these?

Notes:

9) Please listen to this fictional scenario and let's discuss what you would do in that situation?

I have been feeling a bit agitated about everything happening around me since the pandemic started especially as my financial capacity began to dwindle, and this had affected my ability to continue to write my dissertation. So, I messaged one of my colleagues called Silver, he was able to lift my spirit to start writing again but I disliked how he advised me on my financial circumstances?

10) From your perspective, would you have been able to discuss this type of issue via MIMs and why? Will you still be able to discuss similar issues in the future especially regarding finance?

- **To highlight the importance of peer relationships and recommend to the university how to encourage more of this among the doctoral students.**

11) How will you compare these types of supports to those you receive from the university and supervisors? (please write them down and show us) Can they be replaced by supervisory support? Why did you say so?

Notes:

12) I will read out some points on how the university could enhance more peer support, and I will like you to indicate your agreement/disagreement using thumbs up or down respectively (*the number of thumbs up/down is recorded for each point*).

	No of thumbs up	No of thumbs down
I will like more support for this type		
Will love to have colleagues that can help review my work once in a while		

I will love to help other doctoral students as well.		
The help/support I receive from my colleagues can also be done by my supervisor.		
Will love more events for social interactions among doctoral students from other cohorts		
I would like to have a student mentor for this type of support		

(The participants' responses were collated into the table above)

16) What would you have love to change about the support you receive at the moment through MIMs?

Concluding question: My final question for the day is to ask by going round the room, among all the things we have talked about today, what to you, is the most important thing that has been said: could be what you have said or what someone else had said (they are asked to indicate this in their paper) – To you, which of the part of the discussion today would you say is the most crucial?

Final remark: The moderator summarises the day's discussion and request any comments from the participants

Moderator: *And that is the end of our discussion today, once again, thank you for attending this virtual group session. I wish everyone the best of luck and let us not forget to continue to support each other, especially at this difficult time. Thank you. Bye*

(Moderators tidy up all that was discussed as soon as the participants had left the virtual meeting room).